

The Relationships Between Organisational Orientations, Financial Resources and Scottish SMEs Performance

By

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Declaration

I, hereby declare that this Doctoral Thesis is the independent work of the author. This research project is original and never been submitted previously, in whole or in part, for any other academic award. The material that has been acquired from other sources has been duly acknowledged in the thesis.

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Abstract

The Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) are enormously vital in an economy as they are highest in the numbers of businesses (OECD, 2017a), major sector for economic growth, a key source of employment, innovation, technological development (Ahmad et al., 2017), and enhance industrialisation (Majama and Magang, 2017). SMEs contribution to employment is the largest as compared to other business sectors (Ayyagari et al., 2011). A total of 99.7% of firms are SMEs in OECD countries (OECD, 2017a) and 99.3% in Scotland (The Scottish government, 2020).

Building on the resource-based view theory, this study identified that three key organisational orientations; entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientation (LO) and market orientation (MO) positively affect SMEs performance (Khan et al., 2020; Morgan and Anokhin, 2020; Lonial and Carter, 2015; Wang, 2008). Since, SMEs have limited access to financial resources (Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, 2015), their level of access to financial resources may influences these relationships. Therefore, a gap has been identified to investigate the moderating effects of financial resources on the direct relationships between three organisational orientations and Scottish SMEs performance.

To test the relationships, this study adopted a survey strategy and quantitative data collection method in a cross-sectional time horizon, underpinning positivism research paradigm. Established measurement scales were utilised to develop the survey questionnaire instrument and 7-point Likert scale items were used to obtain the responses. A total of 322 responses were obtained from Scottish SMEs; 78 were collected online (internet-mediated access approach) and 244 were obtained by approaching firms personally (traditional access approach), yielding a response rate of 21.38%. A total of 313 (20.78%) responses were found usable.

The data were analysed into four stages, including data screening, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the analysis of structural path model using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique. The findings supported all the direct effect relationships but none of the moderating effects relationships. The study contributed to the field of organisational orientations and financial resources underlying the resources-based view in two ways. First, the study contributed to the

theory by confirming that entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, market orientations and financial resources all have a significant direct and positive effect on SMEs performance. Second, the study contributed to theory by extending the theory through testing the moderating effects of financial resources, in which it was found that financial resources do not enhance the effects of any of the organisational orientations on SMEs performance.

This study guide CEOs/Owners/Managers to develop all three organisational orientations and preference must be given to EO followed by MO and LO. They must also enhance their access to financial capital and improve their financial literacy to allocate resources prudently.

Key Words: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), organisational orientations, entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientation (LO), market orientation (MO), financial resources, performance, Scotland.

Table of Contents

Declaration	ii
Acknowledgements	iii
Abstract	iv
Table of Contents	vi
List of Figures	x
List of Tables	x
List of Abbreviations	xii
1 Chapter One: Introduction	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Background	1
1.3 The Rationale of the Research	4
1.4 Significance of this Study	5
1.5 Research Aim and Objectives	6
1.5.1 Research aim	6
1.5.2 Research objectives	6
1.6 Research Questions	7
1.6.1 Key Research Question	7
1.6.2 Investigative questions	7
1.7 Synopsis of Research Methodology	7
1.8 Research Contributions	8
1.8.1 Proposed Theoretical Contribution	8
1.8.2 Proposed Practical Contribution	9
1.9 Research Plan and timetable	10
1.10 Summary of the chapters	10
1.10.1 Chapter one – Introduction	10
1.10.2 Chapter two – Literature Review	10
1.10.3 Chapter three – Research Methodology	11
1.10.4 Chapter Four – Analysis and Finding	11
1.10.5 Chapter Five – Discussion	12
1.10.6 Chapter Six – Research Summary, Limitations, Recommendations for Future Research and Conclusion	12
1.11 Chapter Summary	12
2 Chapter Two – Literature review	14
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)	14
2.2.1 Definition	14
2.2.2 Importance of SMEs	16
2.2.3 Importance of Scottish SMEs.	18
2.2.4 Challenges to Scottish SMEs	21
2.2.4.1 BREXIT	21

2.2.4.2	Funding issues of Scottish SMEs	22
2.3	The Concept of Firm Performance	24
2.3.1	Business Success	24
2.3.2	Business Failure	26
2.3.3	Firm Performance and Measures	28
2.4	Factors Impacting SMEs Performance	29
2.5	Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory	35
2.6	Entrepreneurial orientation (EO)	39
2.6.1	Dimensions of Entrepreneurial Orientation	40
2.6.2	Relationship between EO and Firm Performance	44
2.7	Learning Orientation (LO)	51
2.7.1	Dimensions of Learning Orientation	54
2.7.2	Relationship between LO and Firm Performance	56
2.8	Market Orientation (MO)	60
2.8.1	Dimensions of Market Orientation	61
2.8.1.1	Kohli and Jaworski (1990) Conceptualisation	61
2.8.1.2	Narver and Slater (1990) Conceptualisation	63
2.8.2	Relationship between MO and firm Performance	65
2.9	Relationship between Organisational orientations and Firm Performance (Combined Approach)	71
2.10	Financial Resources	76
2.10.1	Financial Capital	76
2.10.2	Financial Literacy	77
2.10.3	Relationship between Financial Resources and Firm Performance	80
2.10.4	Financial Resources as a Moderator	85
2.10.4.1	Financial Resources as a Moderator in EO-Performance Relationship	85
2.10.4.2	Financial Resources as a Moderator in LO-Performance Relationship	87
2.10.4.3	Financial Resource as a Moderator in MO-Performance Relationship	89
2.11	Hypotheses Building	95
2.11.1	Hypothesis 1 (H1) - Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P)	95
2.11.2	Hypothesis 2 (H2) – Learning orientation (LO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	96
2.11.3	Hypothesis 3 (H3) – Market orientation (MO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	98
2.11.4	Hypothesis 4 (H4) – Financial Resources (FR) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	99
2.11.5	Hypothesis 5 (H5) - The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between EO and Firm Performance (P).	100
2.11.6	Hypothesis 6 (H6) - The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between LO and Firm Performance (P).	101
2.11.7	Hypothesis 7 (H7) - The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between MO and Firm Performance (P).	102
3	Chapter Three - Research Methodology	104
3.1	Introduction	104
3.2	Philosophical Foundation of the Research	104
3.2.1	Ontology	105
3.2.1.1	Objectivism	105
3.2.1.2	Subjectivism	105

3.2.2	Epistemology _____	106
3.2.3	Axiology _____	106
3.3	Research Paradigms _____	107
3.3.1	Positivism _____	107
3.3.2	Interpretivism _____	108
3.3.3	Pragmatism _____	110
3.3.4	Philosophy of this study _____	111
3.4	Research Approach _____	112
3.5	Research Process _____	113
3.6	Research Design _____	116
3.6.1	Research Strategies _____	116
3.6.2	Data Collection Method _____	117
3.6.3	Time Horizon _____	118
3.7	Measurement of Variables _____	119
3.7.1	Dependent variables _____	121
3.7.2	Independent Variables _____	123
3.7.2.1	Entrepreneurial Orientations (EO) _____	123
3.7.2.2	Learning Orientations (LO) _____	124
3.7.2.3	Market Orientations (MO) _____	125
3.7.3	Moderator Variable _____	126
3.7.3.1	Financial Resources _____	127
3.8	Questionnaire instrument _____	128
3.8.1	Pre-test and Pilot-test _____	128
3.9	Population _____	129
3.10	Sample _____	130
3.10.1	Sample size _____	131
3.10.2	Sampling _____	131
3.10.3	Calculation of actual sample size _____	133
3.11	Gaining Access and collection of Data _____	134
3.11.1	Internet-mediated access approach _____	134
3.11.2	Traditional Access Approach _____	137
3.12	Response Overview _____	138
3.13	Ethical Consideration of the Thesis _____	139
3.14	Reliability and Validity _____	139
3.14.1	Reliability _____	139
3.14.2	Validity _____	141
3.15	Statistical Procedure _____	143
3.16	Chapter Summary _____	145
4	Chapter Four – Data Analysis and Findings _____	147
4.1	Introduction _____	147
4.2	Data Screening _____	147
4.2.1	Data Coding _____	147
4.2.2	Initial Data Screening _____	148
4.2.3	Missing Data _____	149
4.2.4	Outlier _____	150
4.2.5	Normality _____	152

4.3	Collinearity	154
4.4	Homoscedasticity and Linearity:	156
4.5	Response Rate	158
4.6	Non-Response Bias	159
4.7	Descriptive Analysis	160
4.7.1	Demographic Profile of Participants	161
4.7.2	Firm profile	162
4.8	Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)	164
4.8.1	Sampling Adequacy	166
4.8.2	EFA Before Modification	167
4.8.3	EFA After Modification	168
4.8.3.1	Reliability Test After Modification of EFA	170
4.9	Common Method Variance	171
4.10	Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) – Measurement Model	172
4.10.1	Model fit	174
4.10.2	Construct Validity	175
4.10.3	Construct Reliability	177
4.11	Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) – Structural Model	177
4.11.1	Estimation of the Structural Model	177
4.12	Hypotheses Testing	179
4.12.1	Hypothesis 1 - Direct Effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation	180
4.12.2	Hypothesis 2 - Direct Effect of Learning Orientation	180
4.12.3	Hypothesis 3 - Direct Effect of Market Orientation	181
4.12.4	Hypothesis 4 - Direct Effect of Financial Resources	181
4.12.5	Hypothesis 5 - Moderated Effect of Financial Resource on Entrepreneurial Orientation	181
4.12.6	Hypothesis 6 - Moderated Effect of Financial Resource on Learning Orientation	182
4.12.7	Hypothesis 7 - Moderated Effect of Financial Resource on Market Orientation	183
4.13	Chapter Summary	184
5	Chapter Five – Discussion	186
5.1	Introduction	186
5.2	Results of Direct Effect on Firm Performance	186
5.2.1	Direct Effect of EO on Firm Performance (H1)	187
5.2.2	Direct Effect of LO on Firm Performance (H2)	188
5.2.3	Direct Effect of MO on Firm Performance (H3)	188
5.2.4	Direct Effect of Financial Resources on Firm Performance (H4)	190
5.3	Results of Moderating Effect on Firm Performance	191
5.3.1	Moderating Effect of Financial Resources on EO→Performance (H5)	191
5.3.2	Moderating Effect of Financial Resources on LO→Performance (H6)	192
5.3.3	Moderating Effect of Financial Resources on MO→Performance (H7)	194
5.4	Research Implications	195
5.4.1	Theoretical Implications	195
5.4.2	Practical implication.	197
5.5	Chapter Summary	201
6	Chapter six – Research Summary, Limitations, Recommendations for Future Research and Conclusion	204
6.1	Introduction	204

6.2	Summary of the research	204
6.3	Research questions	206
6.4	Limitations and future research.	207
6.4.1	Financial Resources Construct	207
6.4.2	Unite of Analysis	208
6.4.3	Research Measures.	208
6.4.4	Time Horizon	208
6.4.5	Research Sample	209
6.4.6	Data Collection Method.	209
6.5	Concluding remarks	210
References:		212

List of Figures

<i>Figure 1.1 - DBA Research Completion Plan Timeline (2019-2020)</i>	10
<i>Figure 2.1 - Contribution of enterprises, employment and turnover by size of enterprise, 2017</i>	19
<i>Figure 2.2 - RBV framework: A source of sustainable competitive advantage</i>	37
<i>Figure 2.3 - Framework of the Study</i>	94
<i>Figure 2.4 - Conceptual Framework of the Study</i>	103
<i>Figure 3.1 - Research Process</i>	115
<i>Figure 3.2 - Sampling Techniques</i>	133
<i>Figure 4.1 - Scatterplot</i>	157
<i>Figure 4.2 - Normal Probability Plot</i>	158
<i>Figure 4.3 - Measurement Model</i>	173
<i>Figure 4.4 - Structural Mode</i>	179
<i>Figure 4.5 - Moderating Effect of FR on EO → P</i>	182
<i>Figure 4.6 - Moderating Effect of FR on LO → P</i>	182
<i>Figure 4.7 - Moderating effect of FR on MO → P</i>	183
<i>Figure 5.1 - Final Model</i>	187

List of Tables

<i>Table 2.1 - Breakdown of SMEs</i>	15
<i>Table 2.2 - Factors Influencing Growth in SMEs</i>	31
<i>Table 2.3 - Key Factors that Influence Firm Performance</i>	33
<i>Table 2.4 - Summary of the Empirical Literature Review</i>	91
<i>Table 3.1 - 7-Point Likert Scale</i>	120
<i>Table 3.2 - Firm Performance Measures</i>	122
<i>Table 3.3 - Entrepreneurial Orientation Measures</i>	124
<i>Table 3.4 - Learning Orientation Measures</i>	125
<i>Table 3.5 - Market Orientation Measures</i>	126
<i>Table 3.6 - Financial Resources Measures</i>	128
<i>Table 3.7 - Identification of Micro, Small and Medium-sized Firms</i>	136
<i>Table 3.8 - Responses Overview</i>	139
<i>Table 3.9 - Reliability statistics (Pilot Stage)</i>	141
<i>Table 4.1 - Descriptive and Reliability Statistics</i>	149
<i>Table 4.2 - Tests of Normality</i>	154
<i>Table 4.3 - Cut Off Values of Extreme Collinearity</i>	155
<i>Table 4.4 - Collinearity Statistics</i>	156
<i>Table 4.5 - Overall Response Rate</i>	159
<i>Table 4.6 - Independent t-test</i>	160

Table 4.7 - Demographic Profile of Participants	162
Table 4.8 - Demographic Profile of Firms	163
Table 4.9 - Cut-off for EFA Tests	166
Table 4.10 - SPSS output for KMO and Bartlett's Test	167
Table 4.11 - SPSS Output for Total Variance Explained*	167
Table 4.12 - SPSS Output for Communalities and Rotated Factor Matrix*	168
Table 4.13 - Problematic Items Deleted	169
Table 4.14 - SPSS Output of Total Variance Explained (After Modification) *	169
Table 4.15 - Rotated Factor Matrix (After Modification)	170
Table 4.16 - Summary of CFA – Measurement Model	174
Table 4.17 - Cut-off criteria	175
Table 4.18 - Model Fit Measures of Measurement Model	175
Table 4.19 - Squared Root of AVEs and Construct Correlation	177
Table 4.20 - Structural Model Fit Indices	178
Table 4.21 – Parameter Estimates, Critical Ratios and p-values	179
Table 4.22 - Summary of Hypotheses Testing	170

List of Abbreviations

AVE	Average Variance Extracted
CE	Corporate Entrepreneurship
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFI	Comparative Fit Index
CR	Composite/Construct Reliability
CFA	Confirmatory Factor Analysis
DF	Degree of Freedom
EO	Entrepreneurial Orientation
EFA	Exploratory Factor Analysis
EU	European Union
FR	Financial Resources
GVA	Gross Value Added
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
KMO	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin
LO	Learning Orientation
ML	Maximum Likelihood
MO	Market Orientation
MSV	Maximum Shared Variance
NPD	New Product Development
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
RBV	Resources-Based View
RMSEA	Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
P	SMEs/Firm Performance
SMRM	SRMR
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United State of America

1 Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the background and rationale of the study which outlines the prominence of SMEs in an economy. The chapter then outlines the overall research aim, the set of objectives and key research questions. The synopsis of the literature and methods employed, research time scale and a summary of the chapters are also presented in this chapter.

1.2 Background

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are defined as any business that employs less than 250 employees (The UK Government, 2020 and The Scottish Government, 2020) and divided into three categories depending on the numbers of employees; (a) micro-sized businesses that employ less than 10 employees (b) small-sized businesses that employ between 10 to 49 employees and (c) medium-sized businesses that employ 50 to 249 employees (Ward, 2021). SMEs are the highest in the numbers of businesses in an economy and their impact on a nation's economy worldwide cannot be overlooked. As reported by the "Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development" (OECD) that 95 per cent of businesses in all economies are SMEs and their roles in the socio-economic development of a country are enormous (OECD, 2017a). According to Veskaisri, Chan and Pollard (2007) SMEs' enhance the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of a country and provide employment opportunities to a substantial number of members of the public. The contribution of SMEs to employment is the largest as compared to any other sector (Ayyagari, Demirguc-Kunt and Maksimovic, 2011) and they are the base for industrial structure as they enhance industrialisation in the majority of countries in the world (Majama and Magang, 2017).

Ahmad et al. (2017) stated that SMEs are acknowledged as a crucial sector for economic growth, a key source of employment, innovation and technological development in developing and developed economies. Elster and Phipps (2013) emphasised on three key areas through which SMEs contribute to economic growth,

that are: (a) encouraging innovation, (b) strengthening competition and (c) making an excessively large contribution to job creation. Whilst, Gilmore et al. (2013) presumed that SMEs generate vital and innovative ideas.

In OECD countries 99.7% of businesses in the non-financial sector are SMEs. They contribute 60% of employment and generated an average of 50% to 60% of value-added in the region (OECD, 2017b). In the United Kingdom, SMEs are a dynamic part and a backbone of the economy, where the total number of businesses was estimated to be 6 million in 2020, and SMEs represent 99.9% of this total. Whilst, 5.7 million (96%) out of 6 million businesses were categorised as micro-businesses, i.e. the businesses employing 0-9 people, and their contribution to employment and turnover was 33% and 21% respectively (Ward, 2021). The average rate of the annual increase in the numbers of businesses was +3% since 2000 (The UK Government, 2020). In the United Kingdom, the growth in SMEs significantly contributes to future economic growth (Elster and Phipps, 2013).

In Scotland, a total of 364,310 businesses were estimated as private sector enterprises as of March 2020, in which SMEs account for 99.3 per cent (361,875 enterprises). SMEs total contribution to jobs were approximately 1.2 million, 55.7% of the total jobs in the private sector and their contribution to the total turnover of the private sector were 41.2%. Micro and small businesses, employing less than 50 employees, dominate the sector and represent 98.2% of private-sector enterprise. Medium-size enterprises account for 1.1% of businesses and large firms only represent 0.7 per cent of the private sector enterprises (see figure 2.1; The Scottish Government, 2020).

Internationalisation and innovation are two of the Scottish Government's four economic policy priorities (Aiton, Liddell and McIver, 2017). In 2018, a total of 44% of businesses exported to the rest of the UK and 14% of business exported internationally, 85% of which are established exporters (The Scottish Government, 2019). An increase of £1.1 billion (3.4%) in Scotland's international exports (excluding oil and gas) leading to £33.8 billion and an increase of £1.2 billion (2.5%) export to the UK leading to £51.2 billion has been reported in 2018 as compared to 2017. In total, Scotland's export is valued at £85 billion with an increase of 2.9% (£2.4 billion).

Scotland's top international export destination country is the USA which accounted for £5.5 billion of exports in 2018 (The Scottish Government, 2020a).

A total of 40% of Scottish SMEs innovated novel or significantly improved products, services or processes between 2014 and 2017. Twenty-one per cent of Scottish SMEs introduced new or significantly improved processes for producing or supplying goods or services in the years between 2017 to 2019. Medium-sized businesses and the information and communication sector were reported to be the key innovators in Scotland (The Scottish Government, 2017; 2019).

Aberdeen, Edinburgh, and Glasgow are Scotland's three largest cities (The Scottish Government, 2016), however, Glasgow is the economic powerhouse of Scotland and generates £19.3 billion GVA (Gross Value Added) per annum, highest as compared to any other Scottish city. Glasgow has an extremely strong economic performance history and has emerged as the fastest-growing major city economy in the UK with growth significantly outperforming all other core cities, after the 2008 economic crash (Glasgow City Council, 2020)

Furthermore, the strategic management is critical for any business as it leads to gain a sustainable competitive advantage (Grant, 2015), While, the current business environment has become turbulent and uncertain, and firms of all types and sizes are facing constant challenges (Lee et al., 2016). In this type of marketplace, firms struggle to sustain and enhance sales, market share, and profitability (Lonial and Carter, 2015). Nonetheless, the input of SMEs to the economy is outstanding, however, because of their small size, they are vulnerable to the external environment (Vemić, 2017). The market failure and barrier adversely impact these businesses due to their internal management limitations and lack of resources (OECD, 2017a). According to Wang, Walker and Redmont (2007), SMEs owner-managers lack managerial and entrepreneurial skills and have no strategic vision and planning. Therefore, to cope with such challenges they must gain a sustainable competitive advantage (Nghah, AbdWahab and Salleh, 2015). As a result, firms must effectively utilise tangible as well as intangible assets that are valuable, rare, and inimitable (Lonial and Carter, 2015).

1.3 The Rationale of the Research

SMEs are enormously vital in an economy as they are the highest in the numbers of businesses (OECD, 2017a), major sector for economic growth, a key source of employment, innovation, technological development (Ahmad et al., 2017), and enhance industrialisation (Majama and Magang, 2017).

Although, firms of all types and sizes are facing constant challenges in the current turbulent and uncertain business environment (Lee et al., 2016), however, SMEs in particular, struggle to sustain and enhance sales, market share, and profitability (Lonial and Carter, 2015). Despite the fundamental position of SMEs in an economy, they are vulnerable to the external environment because of their small size (Vemić, 2017) and may cease to operate (Majama and Magang, 2017). The market failure and barrier adversely impact SMEs due to their lack of resources (OECD, 2017b). To cope with such challenges, they need to identify and develop those specific resources and/or capabilities that enable them to obtain a sustainable competitive advantage. The resource-based view (RBV) theory of firms argues that not all the resources are important, rather the resources that are valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable (VRIN) generate a sustained competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). Intangible resources (or capabilities) are mostly considered as VRIN resources as they are most challenging to be copied (Zhou et al., 2008).

The literature search found that three key organisational orientations, i.e. entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientation (LO) and market orientation (MO), are those specific capabilities of the firm that are challenging to duplicate and can generate sustainable competitive advantage (Lonial & Carter, 2015). Although, the positive relationships between these organisational orientations and firm performance have been tested empirically (Baker and Sinkula, 1999; 2002; 2005; Cake et al, 2020; Calabrò et al. (2020); Galbreath et al. (2020); Gupta et al., 2020; Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández 2018; 2020; Khan et al, 2020; Lonial & Carter, 2015; McGee & Peterson 2019; Morgan and Anokhin, 2020; Wang, 2008; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003; 2005), however, a gap still exists, particularly regarding the effects of SMEs access to financial resources. Since developing organisational orientations is capital intensive (Cooper et al., 1994) and SMEs have

limited access to financial resources (Brouthers et al., 2015), they may not be able to develop organisational orientations, which in turn, hinder them to generate a competitive advantage and achieve superior performance. The effect of this dependency of SMEs on financial resources has not been fully explored on the relationships between three key organisational orientations (EO, LO and MO) and SMEs performance in general and has never been explored on Scottish SMEs performance in particular. This study will be the first to investigate the independent relationships between organisational orientations on Scottish SMEs and the effects of financial resources on these relationships. Therefore, this study is set out to build on the concept of the RBV of firms to bridge this gap by investigating the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationships between three key organisational orientations (EO, LO and MO) and SMEs performance. This study by examining these relationships on Scottish SMEs will provide new empirical evidence that will lead to the contribution of new knowledge in the field of financial resources, organisational orientations and Scottish SMEs performance.

1.4 Significance of this Study

Although the abundance of literature is available on SMEs performance, however, there is limited empirical literature on the performance of SMEs in Scotland. This lack of literature further justifies the rationale of conducting research on Scottish SMEs performance. This research is focused specifically on Scottish SMEs and sets out to test the importance of organisational orientations (i.e. EO, MO and LO) by investigating their effects on SMEs performance. Furthermore, the effects of financial resources have not been tested before along with simultaneously modelled organisational orientations. This study examines how financial resources might influence their relationships with SMEs performance.

Moreover, the survival of SMEs is essential as their role is crucial for economic success of a country. In Scotland, 99.3% of all private enterprises are SMEs, which significantly enhance employment, technological development, innovation and internationalisation of the country (The Scottish Government, 2019; 2020).

Additionally, BREXIT is a major threat to SMEs in the United Kingdom (UK). As stated by Brown, Zegarra and Wilson (2018) that Brexit may have the worst impact on SMEs

in the UK. In Scotland, 50 per cent of SMEs that import solely from the EU and 80 per cent of SMEs that export to the EU believe that BREXIT is the main problem for their business. In other words, BREXIT substantially and deeply harmful for the success of Scottish import and export firms (Brown, 2018). Scottish SMEs with plans to develop and launch new products/services and recruit new staff (6%), capital investment plans (5%), the introduction of new working practices plans (4%) and plans to increase export or start exporting to new foreign markets (3%) had been affected by BREXIT (The Scottish Government, 2019).

Therefore, it is important to investigate the key resources and capabilities such as EO, LO, MO and financial resources to provide Scottish SMEs with a framework that enables them to obtain a sustainable competitive advantage. Moreover, this research will also help the policymakers in Scotland to set policies that enhance SMEs' performance and encourage young entrepreneurs.

1.5 Research Aim and Objectives

1.5.1 Research aim

The overall aim of this research is to identify the key resources and investigate their effects on Scottish SMEs performance, to provide a framework to SMEs to formulate and implement strategies that will lead to competitive advantage and superior performance.

1.5.2 Research objectives

To achieve the overall aim of this research, the objectives of this study are:

1. To investigate the relationships between organisational orientations and Scottish SMEs performance.
2. To investigate the relationship between financial resources and Scottish SMEs performance.
3. To investigate the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationships between organisational orientations and Scottish SMEs performance?

4. Demonstrate the implications and make suggestions that might help Scottish SMEs to implement the right organisational oriented strategies to improve their performance

1.6 Research Questions

1.6.1 Key Research Question

What are the relationships between organisational orientations and SMEs performance and to what extent financial resources influence these relationships?

1.6.2 Investigative questions

1. What are the effects of different organisational orientations on SMEs performance?
2. What are the effects of financial resources on SMEs performance?
3. What are the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationships between organisational orientations and SMEs performance?

1.7 Synopsis of Research Methodology

The emphasis of this study is to investigate the effects of organisational orientations on SMEs performance and how financial resources influence these relationships. The research questions and three key categories of philosophical foundations of research; i.e. ontology, epistemology, and axiology directed the researcher to adopt the positivist philosophical paradigm. The quantitative research method was used to fulfil the need of this study because it is the most used method underlying the positivist philosophical approach (Tsang, 2017) and in organisational orientations studies (see Baker and Sinkula, 1999; 2002; 2005; Cake et al, 2020; Gupta et al., 2020; Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández 2018; 2020; Khan et al, 2020; Lonial & Carter, 2015; McGee & Peterson 2019; Morgan and Anokhin, 2020; Wang, 2008; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003; 2005). The study engaged in an in-depth literature review to generate deductive hypotheses. To test the hypothesis a representative range of a sample of Scottish SMEs was used to collect quantitative primary data through a self-administrative survey questionnaires instrument in the cross-sectional setting. The questionnaire instrument utilised 7-point Likert scale items to obtain the responses,

and pre-tested and pilot tested before administrating to Scottish SMEs using an internet-mediated access approach and traditional access approach. In the internet-mediated access approach, the SMEs were identified using an online database of companies called 'FAME', which found to be the most appropriate database to gather contact details of the companies. In the traditional access approach, the firms were accessed personally to obtain the data.

The structural equation modelling (SEM) technique was utilised to analyse the primary data. The process of analysis was carried out into four stages, namely, "data screening, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural path model analysis". Computer software including 'IBM SPSS Statistics 25 and IBM SPSS Amos 25' were used to analyse the data. In the data screening stage, the data was coded and run through the initial data screening to identify any errors or mistakes in the data during data entering. Further tests were conducted in this stage to identify and rectify missing data, outliers, normality and multicollinearity.

EFA was conducted to achieve valid and reliable common latent factors. In this process, four questionnaire items were found redundant and deleted. CFA was conducted to approve the structure of the factors obtained from EFA and analyse the measurement model. In CFA overall model fit, construct validity and reliability were achieved and factor scores for the latent (unobserved) variables were obtained using regression imputation. These scores were used to conduct the structural (Path) model to test the hypotheses of this study.

1.8 Research Contributions

This study is aiming to contribute to the development of theory and business practice by investigating the relationship between three organisational orientations, financial resources and SMEs performance. The proposed contributions of this study to theory and practice are as follows:

1.8.1 Proposed Theoretical Contribution

Albeit, this research is specifically focused on Scottish SMEs, however, it is intending to extract the general contribution for theoretical literature on the underlying topic of

this study. By examining organisational orientations and financial resources literature and empirically testing their effects on SMEs performance, this study is proposed to contribute to the fields of entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, market orientations and financial resources. This study is also expected to contribute to the resource-based view (RBV) theory by refining the current understanding of the bundles of resources utilised uniquely. It is projected that this research will layout a more rational representation of organisational orientations, as different orientations are taken in cohesion with each other along with financial resources. Therefore, this will also provide a comparatively more effective framework than the studies that examined a single or two orientations.

Furthermore, by examining the moderating effects of financial resources the theoretical contribution will be further extended, as there is little evidence in the literature for the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationships of organisational orientations and firm performance. The inclusion of financial literacy along with financial capital as an indicator of 'financial resources construct' will derive a robust insight into this construct.

1.8.2 Proposed Practical Contribution

The results of this study are proposed to provide a framework supporting SMEs to identify the significance of organisational orientations and financial resources. The study will provide practical implication to entrepreneurs involved in the strategic planning of their firm. Since the SMEs have limited resources and capabilities, in particular, access to financial resources (Brouthers, Nakos, Dimitratos, 2014), the entrepreneurs must cautiously allocate resources and decide which resources and capabilities are worth investing in. This study may provide CEOs/owners/managers with the knowledge required to make difficult decisions regarding which organisational orientation they should prefer, depending on which aspect of firm performance they want to enhance, by having a clear understanding of their financial resources.

In addition to the practical implication, the empirical evidence of the study may also contribute to government planning in the formulation of policies that support the competitiveness of SMEs. The study may help the policymakers to design a support and initiative program, for SMEs, specifically, in the area of organisational orientation

and financial resources. The findings of this research may enable the related agencies to initiate robust and specific training programs to enhance SMEs access to financial capital and the level of their financial knowledge.

1.9 Research Plan and timetable

Figure 1.1 - DBA Research Completion Plan Timeline (2019-2020)

1.10 Summary of the chapters

This study is organised into six chapters. The detail of each chapter is as follow;

1.10.1 Chapter one – Introduction

Chapter one consists of an introduction to the research. It serves as a foundation of the study and provides direction to the researcher. This chapter first outlines the background with a detailed exploration of SMEs. It then presents the rationale of why this research is conducted and what is the significance of this research. Furthermore, the chapter outlines the research aim, objectives and research questions. An overview of the research design and methodology is then presented. The chapter concludes on the chapter-by-chapter thesis outline and brief chapter summary.

1.10.2 Chapter two – Literature Review

Chapter two defines SMEs and presents the importance and challenges of Scottish SMEs. Furthermore, this chapter presents an extensive review of the literature on each

of the variable of this research, i.e., EO, MO, LO, financial resources and firm performance. Next, the chapter describes the relationship between each of the exogenous variables and endogenous variable, underpinning the resources-based view theory. The literature review of the pertinent theories stipulates a concrete foundation for developing a theoretical framework and hypotheses of the research. The chapter ends with the chapter summary.

1.10.3 Chapter three – Research Methodology

Chapter three discusses and justifies the research methodology used in the research. This chapter presents the research philosophies in detail, outlines three frequently used research paradigms and defends why the positivist paradigm used in the current research. The chapter also presents the research approach and the research process. Next, the chapter presents the research strategy, data collection method and time horizon underpinning research design. The measurement of variables is elaborated next, followed by a discussion on questionnaire instrument, research population and sample. Furthermore, a two-phased survey method is presented, leading to the descriptions of ethical considerations, reliability and validity. The chapter narrates the statistical procedure and ends with a chapter summary.

1.10.4 Chapter Four – Analysis and Finding

Chapter four presents the data analysis process and report research findings. The chapter first presents the process of data screening in which the data is cleansed, coded, and the issues of missing data, outliers, normality and collinearity discussed to achieve accurate results. Second, the chapter presents the response rate and estimates non-response bias. The chapter then outlines the results from the descriptive analysis of the demographic profile of respondents and firm profile. Furthermore, the chapter presents the results of the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) which is conducted to identify common latent factors, ensure validity, reliability and to identify the common method variance. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is then presented which is implemented to confirm the factor structure extracted in EFA and to assess the measurement model based on overall good model fit, construct validity and reliability. Next, the chapter outlines structural equation modelling (SEM) which is

conducted to analyse the structural path model and to test the hypotheses. The chapter concludes with the chapter summary.

1.10.5 Chapter Five – Discussion

Chapter five outlines the discussion of the results of SEM, conducted in chapter four. The chapter discusses the findings underpinning each of the hypotheses followed by the discussion of the research theoretical and practical implications. The chapter ends with the chapter summary.

1.10.6 Chapter Six – Research Summary, Limitations, Recommendations for Future Research and Conclusion

This chapter concludes the current study by reviewing and connecting the key elements of the research. First, the chapter presents a summary of the overall research by revisiting all the stages of the thesis. Second, It links the findings of each of the hypotheses to reflect on the results of the research question. Third, the chapter discusses the limitations of this study, followed by the recommendation for future research. Finally, the chapter ends with concluding remarks.

1.11 Chapter Summary

This study is focused on the role of SMEs in the economy of the countries. SMEs are the highest in the numbers of businesses in an economy. In OECD countries 99.7% of businesses of the non-financial sector are occupied by SMEs, contributing 60% to employment and generated an average of 50% to 60% of value-added (OECD, 2017b). In Scotland, 99.4% of businesses are SMEs, which account for 55% of private-sector employment and 40.1% of private-sector turnover (The Scottish Government, 2017).

The resources and capabilities have long been discussed and considered a key source of competitive advantage for firms (Barney, 1995). The literature search found that the ‘organisational orientations’, a combination of entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientations (LO) and marketing orientation (MO), are those specific capabilities of the firms that are difficult to duplicate and have a positive effect on SMEs

performance (Lonial and Carter, 2015). However, to develop organisational orientations is capital intensive for SMEs and they have limited access to financial resources.

The above discussion provides the rationale to investigate the effects of three key organisational orientations and financial resources on SMEs performance and specifically, to what extent financial resources enhance the effects of organisation orientations on SMEs performance. The research outline three key objectives and three investigative questions underpinning the key research question; to what extent financial resources influence the relationships of three organisational orientations and SMEs performance?

Methodologically, this study proposed a deductive research approach underlying the positivism philosophical paradigm. The study planned to test hypotheses by collecting self-administrative survey-based quantitative data in a cross-sectional setting.

The study proposed to contribute to the theory of organisational orientations, financial resources, Scottish SMEs performance and RBV. It proposed to provide a guideline to CEOs/owners/managers of SMEs to enhance their business performance. Furthermore, the study also proposed to provide a guideline to policymakers to initiate robust and specific training programs to enhance SMEs ability to develop organisational orientations, their access to financial capital and their financial knowledge.

2 Chapter Two – Literature review

2.1 Introduction

The key objectives of this chapter are to review and discuss the relevant literature to identify the key factors that affect SMEs performance. The chapter started with the definition of SMEs in detail and examining their significance in the Scottish economy. It progressed to analyse the challenges faced by small businesses in Scotland and reviews the factors that affect their performance. Furthermore, it reviews the fundamental theoretical foundation of this study i.e. Resource-Based View (RBV) of the firms. The chapter then critically reviewed key influencing factors such as entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientations (LO), market orientations (MO), and financial resources (FR). A conceptual framework and hypotheses were then established to illustrate and test the relationships between the theory and SMEs practices.

2.2 Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)

2.2.1 Definition

The “Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development” (OECD), regarded that despite having enormous importance, SME has no universal definition (OECD, 2017a). The Associate of Chartered Certified Accountants (ACCA) corroborated OECD’s view that SMEs has no agreed common definition as they normally comprehend the businesses of different sectors and jurisdiction (ACCA, 2010). Whilst, OECD (2017b) highlighted that SMEs has been defined differently because a firm’s feature of being called ‘small’ and ‘medium’ is determined by the specific domestic economy.

A briefing paper on business statistics published by the UK House of Commons defined SMEs as any business that employed less than 250 employees and split them into three categories depending on the numbers of employees, i.e.; (a) micro-sized businesses that employ less than 10 employees (b) small-sized businesses that employ between 10 to 49 employees and (c) medium-sized businesses that employ between 50 to 249 employees (Ward, 2021). The Scottish Government (2020) also

defined SMEs based on numbers of employees in which any business with up to 249 employees is considered as an SME and categorised them into three parts as stated by Ward (2021). The European Commission (2015) definition is also consistent with Ward's (2021) definition in terms of numbers of employees, however, the European Commission (2015) also consider total annual turnover or total annual balance sheet to decide if a business is an SME or a large firm. Therefore, if any business employed less than 250 employees but its annual turnover greater than €50 million or its annual balance sheet exceeds €43 million will not be considered as an SME. The classification of SMEs by the European Commission (2015) is depicted in table 2.1.

Table 2.1 - Breakdown of SMEs

Type	Numbers of Employees	Annual Turnover	Or	Annual Balance Sheet
Micro	< 10	≤ €2 million	Or	≤ €2 million
Small	< 50	≤ €10 million	Or	≤ €10 million
Medium	< 250	≤ €50 million	Or	≤ €43 million

Source: - The European Commission (2015)

Although, the European Commission (2015) claim that this definition ensures that the support measures are granted only to those enterprises that genuinely need them, however, they further stated that the size, annual turnover and balance sheet are not the only factors, as a business that is small by size may not be considered as an SME if it has access to significant additional resources. This makes the European Commission (2015) definition more complex and complicated for the researcher to identify if a survey respondent firm is an SME or a large firm. Therefore, this study adopted the Ward (2021) definition of SMEs in which any business that employs less than 250 persons will be considered as a SMEs and further categorised into micro-sized (<10 employees), small-sized (<50 employees) and medium-sized (<250 employees) enterprises.

This categorisation is being used because it is clearer and more concise and also consistent with the European Commission (2015) in terms of numbers of employees. Additionally, Gonzales, Hommes and Mirmulstein (2014) stated that the numbers of employees are the most used variable for defining SMEs and the common threshold

for numbers of employees is 250 employees. Thus, any business that met the condition of the number of employees were considered as an SME in this study regardless of their turnover, balance sheet or any other factor.

2.2.2 Importance of SMEs

There are numbers of considerations behind the motivation of choosing SMEs as a context of this study. However, the most important motivating consideration is the important socio-economic role that SMEs play in a country, alongside being the highest in numbers of businesses in an economy. It is reported that 95% of business are SMEs in all economies (OECD, 2017a).

The Impact SMEs have on the nation's economy worldwide cannot be overlooked. As confirmed by OECD (2017a) that SMEs have a key diverse part in the socio-economic development of a country. SMEs role is becoming increasingly prominent around the world as these enterprises enhance employment opportunities to a substantially wider population and contribute to the gross domestic product (GDP) (Veskaisri, Chan and Pollard, 2007). They are the base for industrial structure as they enhance industrialisation in the majority of countries in the world (Majama and Magang, 2017).

Moreover, Ahmad et al. (2017) noted that SMEs are viewed as a key sector for economic growth, a key source of employment, innovation and technological development in developing as well as developed economies. For example, according to "U.S. Small Business Administration" (USSBA, 2017), in the USA a total of 29.9 million businesses are small businesses and account for 99.9% of the total numbers of businesses in the USA. These small businesses employ 57.9 million people, nearly half of the US employees (47.7%). Similarly, in developing countries, the contribution of SMEs towards employment is up to 60% and national income (GDP) contribution is up to 40% and the contribution is significantly higher with the inclusion of informal SMEs (World Bank 2018).

Elster and Phipps (2013, p. 9) highlighted that there are three key characteristics of SMEs that derive economic development, (a) "Stimulating innovation", (b) "acting as a competitive spur to existing businesses to increase their productivity" and (c). "by making an excessively large contribution to job creation". According to OECD (2017a)

in recent decades the contribution of SMEs to innovations dynamics has increased, however, it has been stated that most small firms that stimulate radical innovations are new firms and thus, they are a key to economic growth.

Similarly, acting as a competitive spur to existing businesses increase competition and create 'churn' in the market, which enhance productivity and encourage economic growth. Churn is a process of continual entry and exit of firms and facilitates 'creative destruction' (Schumpeterian idea). This process increases the entry of innovative firms in the market, replace current firms that are using existing technologies. Thus, churn facilitate innovation and competition, and ultimately drive economic growth (Elster and Phipps, 2013).

OECD (2017a) posited that particularly young SMEs are the key jobs creators and their contribution to employment is two times higher than their contribution to unemployment. Therefore, SMEs not only dominate the private business sector in numbers of business but also have a distinctive role as a source of employment and economic development (Wang, Walker and Redmond, 2007), as they make a disproportionately large contribution to employment (Elster and Phipps, 2013), specifically, since the 1970s in OECD countries (Peacock, 2004). Ayyagari, Demirguc-Kunt and Maksimovic, (2011) researched 99 countries with a sample of 47,745 firms and found that that SMEs are the major job creators in the world.

World Trade Organisation (WTO) reported that empirical evidence shows that jobs in SMEs are less stable and secure as compared to the jobs in larger organisations and there is a lack of training to employees than larger firms. Additionally, SMEs are relatively less productive than large enterprise and thus their contribution to GDP is less as compared to large firms (WTO, 2016). Similarly, Beck (2013) argues that there are mixed views on SMEs being an engine of innovation and stimulate job growth, rather microeconomic to cross country-level studies only confirmed that SMEs are constrained by institutional and market failures.

In OECD countries 99.7 per cent non-financial business sector is occupied by SMEs and they contributed to 60% of jobs and produced an average of 50 to 60 per cent of value-added (OECD, 2017b). In the United Kingdom, the total numbers of businesses were 6 million as of 2020 and 99.9 per cent of the total numbers of businesses were

SMEs. Whilst, 5.7 million (96%) out of 6 million businesses were categorised as micro-businesses, i.e. the businesses employing 0-9 people, and their contribution to employment and turnover was 33% and 21% respectively (Ward, 2021). The average rate of the annual increase in the numbers of businesses was +3% since 2000 (The UK Government, 2020).

2.2.3 Importance of Scottish SMEs.

SMEs are crucial for the economy of any other country and so the Scottish SMEs for Scotland (The Scottish Government, 2017). They are not just the highest in numbers of business but also contribute to employment with their focus on innovation and internationalisation

The Scottish Government (2020) recorded 364,310 private sector enterprises as of March 2020. Micro and small-sized businesses, which employ less than 50 employees, dominate the sector with 98.2% of private-sector enterprise. Similarly, medium-size enterprises account for 1.1% and the rest 0.7% are large companies (See Figure 2.1). A total of 361,875 (99.3%) businesses in Scotland are SMEs, which contributed approximately 57.7% (1.2 million jobs) to employment and 41.2% to turnover in the private sector. Out of the total private sector contribution, the micro to small businesses played a tremendous role by contributing 42.7% to employment and 27.3% to turnover. The total number of private sector businesses in Scotland increased by 7,760 businesses (2.2%) in 2020 (The Scottish Government, 2020). Although a decrease of 88,830 (2.5%) businesses were reported in 2018 as compared to the previous year, however, the numbers of employment increased by 915 (0.9%) as compared to the year 2017 (The Scottish Government, 2018a).

Figure 2.1 – Contribution of Scottish SMEs

Source:- The Scottish Government (2020)

The data show that 73 per cent of firms are family-owned in Scotland, whilst, 15 per cent of firms are run by women. Thirty-seven per cent of SMEs in Scotland are rural-based, 8 in 10 pay the living wage and 70% have a plan to grow their business (The Scottish Government, 2019).

Internationalisation is one of the Scottish Government's four economic policy priorities and thus, international trade a fundamental part of the Scottish Government's economic development remit (Aiton, Liddell and McIver, 2017). In 2018, a total of 44% of businesses in Scotland that exports to other parts of the United Kingdom 13% more than in 2017. A total of 14% of firms exports internationally (outside the United Kingdom). Manufacturing and Business services sectors are the key international exporters representing 37% and 26% respectively, while the construction sector is the lowest in export and only account for 4%. Eighty-five per cent of the Scottish SMEs that export internationally are established exporters, exporting for more than five years. Out of the total Scottish export SMEs, 57% export to both EU countries and non-EU countries, 20% export to EU countries only and 16% to non-EU countries only (The Scottish Government, 2019).

An increase of 3.4% (£1.1 billion) has been recorded in international exports of Scotland in 2018 leading to total international exports to £33.8 billion. Out of the total Scottish export, £695 millions of export was recorded to EU countries leading EU export to £16.1 billion in total, an increase of 4.5%. Whilst, the export of £425 million was noted to non-EU countries an increase of 2.5% to £17.7 billion. Similarly, an increase of £1.2 billion in exports to the UK was also noted, leading total Scotland's exports to the UK to £51.2 billion, an increase of 2.5%. As a result, Scotland's total export valued at £85 billion with an increase of 2.9% (£2.4 billion) as compared to the previous year. The USA was reported to be the Scotland's top international export destination country which alone accounted for £5.5 billion of exports in 2018. Other major export destination country include; France, Netherlands, Germany and Belgium where a collective £9.6 billion of Scotland's export was recorded (The Scottish Government, 2020a)

Innovation and new product (and process) development (NPD) are contemplated as essential for SMEs and small firms that are unsuccessful in NPD face failure (Morgan and Anokhin, 2020). Scotland has four key strategic priorities and innovation is one of them alongside internationalisation, investment and inclusive growth (Aiton, Liddell and McIver, 2017).

Forty per cent of Scottish SMEs innovated novel or significantly improved products, services or processes between 2014 and 2017. Although the numbers of micro to small firms are excessively higher than medium-sized enterprises, however, 57 per cent of the innovation in Scotland is introduced by medium-sized enterprises and thus, are considered as the key innovators. Information and communication sector contribution was reported 66% and thus, dominate other sectors in innovation (The Scottish Government, 2017).

In terms of process innovation, 21% of Scottish SME employers introduced new or significantly improved processes for producing or supplying goods or services in the years between 2017 to 2019. Out of these 21% of employers, 78% introduced process of innovations that were all new to the business and 22% introduced process innovations that were to some extent new. Again, medium-sized businesses were reported to dominate the process innovation and accounted for 39% of the overall process innovation. The information and communication sector were also noted as the

dominant sector with 45% of contribution in process innovation (The Scottish Government, 2019).

In Scotland, seven cities including; Aberdeen, Dundee, Edinburgh, Glasgow, Inverness Perth and Stirling are considered as distinctive cities in terms of gross value added (GVA). The three largest cities of Scotland are Aberdeen, Edinburgh, and Glasgow which attracted investment from all over the world over the past 10 years (The Scottish Government, 2016).

Glasgow is the economic centre of Scotland and generates £19.3 billion GVA per annum, the highest as compared to any other Scottish city. It drastically outperformed the all key cities in the UK. It considered a world leader in precision medicine, quantum technologies and advanced manufacturing and thus, a hub to one of the most collaborative and dynamic innovation economies in Europe. Glasgow has an extremely strong economic performance history and has developed as a major city economy in the UK, after the 2008 economic crash (Glasgow City Council, 2020). Furthermore, Glasgow is the 2nd largest Shopping location in the UK where annual spending of £2.55 billion was recorded (The Scottish Government, 2016).

2.2.4 Challenges to Scottish SMEs

2.2.4.1 BREXIT

Although, there are numbers of challenges faced by SMEs, however, BREXIT may be considered a key challenge for SMEs in the UK and specifically in Scotland. Nonetheless, there will be an impact of BREXIT (UK withdrawal from EU) on large firms too, however, being large they have the resources and capabilities to mitigate this impact. While SMEs being vulnerable will be the hardest hit business sector (Brown 2018).

Brown, Zegarra and Wilson (2018) conducted a study in the UK by using the survey data of 10,000 SMEs gather by the UK government. They found that all the SMEs see BREXIT as a threat to the success of their business, particularly relatively larger, innovative, export-oriented SMEs and the firm in the services sector. Consequently, it may weaken the growth, innovation, capital investment and availability of external finance.

In Scotland, 50 per cent of SMEs that import solely from the EU and 80 per cent of SMEs that export to the EU believe that BREXIT is the main problem for their business. In other words, BREXIT substantially and deeply harmful for the success of SMEs in the UK and import and export firms located in peripheral economies such as Scotland are the worse affected firms (Brown, 2018). The small business survey 2018 highlights that BREXIT most likely have had affected 6% of Scottish SMEs that planned to develop and launch new products/services and recruit new staff. In Scotland, SMEs with capital investment plans (5%), introduction of new working practices plans (4%) and plans increase export or start exporting to new foreign markets (3%) had been affected by BREXIT (The Scottish Government, 2019).

2.2.4.2 Funding issues of Scottish SMEs

Financial resources are the fundamental resources required of the firms to support business growth (Carpenter and Peterson, 2002). According to Dobbs and Hamilton (2007), the availability of funds enable firms to access various kinds of additional resources and formulate a primary resource base which can enhance contributions of other factors, however, the slow recovery of the UK economy after the 2008 global financial crisis elevated distresses of SMEs access to funding, specifically to external finance. As SMEs have limited access to financial resources (Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, 2015, Brown and Lee, 2014), their development and entrepreneurial activities are constrained (Cowling, Liu and Ledger, 2012).

One of the key reasons for limited access to finance is the failure in the financial market due to asymmetric information and agency problem (OECD, 2017a). Access to finance is harder for micro firms as they get charged a higher interest rate and required more strict security conditions as compared to the larger firms (Storey, 2016). For small businesses, the problem of asymmetric information can even be worse as it is empirically approved by several scholars that the investment behaviour of small firms is extremely affected by financial constraints (Carpenter and Peterson, 2002).

There can be several other reasons behind limited access to finance. According to Dobbs and Hamilton (2007), entrepreneurs' own decisions may restrict them to access finance. They may not be willing to give up the part of the ownership of their business

in exchange for equity finance, and uncertainty related to SMEs and a lower level of collateral held by these firms may restrict lenders to provide funds to such firms.

Although, Scottish SMEs make a vital contribution to the Scottish economy, however, to grow, innovate, provide employment opportunities they require access to affordable and appropriate finance (The Scottish Government, 2018a). According to Hamilton and Richmond (2016), Scottish firms are declining in innovation and also there are fewer firms in Scotland seeking finance to grow. Only 17 per cent of Scottish SMEs had persuaded external finance between the year 2016 and 2017. Although, 79 per cent of SMEs seeking external finance did obtain it. however, the majority of SMEs (64%) only applied for finance to meet working capital or cash flow needs (The Scottish Government, 2019). This highlights that most of the firms (83%) are not encouraged to apply for funds, which shows the lack of motivation to grow the business. Similarly, the majority of firms that applied for finance are not high growth firms as they have to apply for external finance for working capital and cash flow. Moreover, out of 17% of firms seeking external finance, 31% of firms either did not obtain any finance or discouraged to apply for external finance, which ultimately restricts them to grow. This in turn, evident that numerous Scottish SMEs are still struggling to raise the required levels of finance, specifically debt finance and equity finance. As a result, the lack of required finance hinders them to grow. Moreover, It is also evidenced that some SMEs do not even apply for the required funds because they distrust that their applications will be successful (Coleman, 2015).

Similarly, some high growth firms that are willing to give up a portion of their business to obtain equity finance also face the issue of 'equity gap'. As highlighted in the economics paper of "Department for Business Innovation and Skills" (BIS) that equity gap exists due to asymmetric information between the investor and the firm seeking equity finance. The investor may also have to incur transaction cost to assess the business proposal and associated risks. In turn, there is a structural gap in the market where investors focus on fewer, larger, well established and lower risk firms for investments. Therefore, businesses with growth potential are not being able to obtain equity finance (BIS, 2012).

2.3 The Concept of Firm Performance

Although, firm performance is a fundamental dependent variable in strategic management research (Wolff and Pett, 2000), however, the consensus on the definition, dimension and measurement of firm performance do not exist (Santos and Brito, 2012; Selvam et al., 2016). A dependent variable is a variable of primary interest of research that is investigated as a viable factor to find research answer or solve a problem (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) and changes in response to change in other variables (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Rauch et al. (2009, p. 765) stated that “performance is a multidimensional concept”, which, Dess and Robinsons (1984) highlighted as a complex phenomenon as it is challenging for researchers to obtain precise measurements. The performance of a business has been divided into three domains by Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986), (a) organisational effectiveness, which is a wider domain, (b) firm performance which comes under organisational effectiveness and (c) financial performance and operational performance which is the subset of firm performance. The firm performance can be determined in two strategic outcomes, mostly referred to as firm success and firm failure in the literature. As argued by Dess and Robinsons (1984), a wide range of empirical studies assessing the relationship between strategic management and small businesses performance used success and failure as a performance measure in their research. Therefore, to identify the factors that impact SMEs performance it would be valuable to examine and elucidate business success and failure.

2.3.1 Business Success

A definition of firm success is required to discuss the determinants of success (Porter, 1991). The decision of being successful depends on the acquisition of wealth, recognition and growth, however, these measures of success to define the success of a business remained ambiguous (Gorgievski, Ascalon and Stephan, 2011). As argued by Rogoff, Lee and Suh (2004) that there is a lack of consensus on the definition, literature and empirical studies on the factors such as business success or failure and this may be due to the individuals’ different views of entrepreneurial success. As stated by Beaver (2005) that it must be admitted that the term ‘success’ has no general definition or measure in business, however, some researchers suggest that each

stakeholder measure it in his/her peculiar way. It is further supported by Praag (2003) that self-employed firms (mostly micro firms) have no distinctive definition of success.

According to Porter (1991, p. 98) “firm success is manifest in attaining a competitive position or series of competitive positions that lead to superior and sustainable financial performance”. In terms of SMEs, the study of Gorgievski, Ascalon and Stephan (2011, p. 209) discovered ten key criteria of entrepreneurial success in an extensive range of literature review. The success criteria include; “profitability, growth, innovation, firm survival/continuity, contributing back to society, personal satisfaction, satisfied stakeholders, good balance between work and private life, public recognition, utility or usefulness”. Personal satisfaction, profitability, and satisfied stakeholders are the highest-ranked measures of success by business owners. This indicates that success can be measured subjectively as well as objectively. Many of the authors emphasise that success must be considered as a subjective measure such as personal satisfaction, work and life balance or reputation. Therefore, the initial point in the process of evaluation of success is the entrepreneurs, owners or managers themselves. The methods of measuring the success of small business in a traditional financial way are insignificant due to the unique nature of the perception of every individual (Simpson, Tuck and Bellamy, 2004).

According to Chong (2008), owner/managers of SMEs use a combination of both financial measures and non-financial measures (i.e. hybrid approach to measuring performance). Financial performance measures include sales and revenue and non-financial performance measures include the firm growth, customers satisfaction and survivals of the organisations. Walker and Brown (2004) stressed that financial measures have been given more attention in the literature.

Furthermore, the difference in age of entrepreneur and size of business shows different criteria of measuring success. Gorgievski, Ascalon and Stephan (2011) state that the younger entrepreneur rated profitability higher than the older entrepreneur. Similarly, the business owners of large size firms prefer continuity and business survival more than the work-life balance as compared to the owners of smaller businesses.

Moreover, the terms survival and growth have been used as a proxy of success. On one hand, the term survival as business success is backed by numbers of authors such as Praag (2003) quoted that a successful business is the one that survives for a longer period. Likewise, continuous business operations are termed as a success by Reijonen and Komppula (2007). On the other hand, growth is considered a key measure of entrepreneurial success. Growth has been given a key role and has been used as a dependent variable in a large number of empirical studies of the performance of small firms (Steffens, Davidsson and Fitzsimmons, 2009), particularly, in a study of SMEs.

Nonetheless, the personal abilities and motivations of the entrepreneur determine whether to grow the business or keep the business small and comfortable size (Walker and Brown, 2004). Subsequently, financial gain is important for some business owners, but this may not motivate the small business owners permanently because success may be measured better by non-financial measures.

2.3.2 Business Failure

To investigate the influence of factors on SMEs performance there is a need for a profound understanding of business failure along with business success. According to Arasti, Zandi and Talebi (2012) the focus of most of the entrepreneurship and SMEs studies is on business success and information regarding business failure is limited. Nonetheless, the knowledge of entrepreneurship is incomplete without the identification of business failure. According to Franco and Haase (2009) studies show a higher rate of SMEs failure and the focus of the research on business failure help SMEs to overcome the factors of business failure. As argued by Storey (2016) that the business failure of SMEs is an extremely important research area to formulate the policies. Therefore, understanding business failure and investigating the causes of poor performance is fundamentally crucial.

There are numbers of studies in different countries focused on the failure rate of SMEs, which shows that the first year of operation has high numbers of business failure. As argued by Arasti, Zandi and Talebi (2012), the intensity of failure within the first year is higher for small firms as compared to medium and large firms. According to Timmons (1994), more than 20% of enterprises fail within the first year of business

and 66% of them cease to operate in the first six years. Disney, Haskel and Heden, (2003) found that after one year 27% of establishments closed and after five years in business, only 35% of the firms survive in the UK. According to Franco and Haase (2009), the failure rate is high within the first year of start-up. The research conducted in Iran by Arasti, Zandi and Talebi (2012) shows that the likelihood of survival of firms for four years is 42% and there is only a 20% probability of firms stays in business for a decade. Whereas, Mohammed (2013) stated that 50% of business ceases to operate in their first five of operations.

In the Oxford dictionary, the term 'failure' is defined as "lack of success, the neglect or omission of expected or required action and the action or state of not functioning". There are numbers of different terms used to state business failure such as death, ceasing to trade, deregister, exit, bankruptcy, insolvency, liquidation, closures, dissolution, discontinuance and organisational mortality (Storey, 2016; Arasti, Zandi and Talebi, 2012). As claimed by Rogoff, Lee and Suh (2004) that there is a lack of agreement on the definition of business failure.

Economically, a business is failed when its return on investment is less than the opportunity cost and it happens when resources are shifted to more profitable opportunities (Fredland and Morris, 1976). According to Everett and Watsons (1998, p. 373), the two most commonly used definitions were (a) "discontinuance of ownership of the business" and (b) "the discontinuance of the business itself". Rogoff, Lee and Suh (2004, p. 365) indicated that studies mostly use the term 'business termination' as an alternate for business failure, however, this definition is "crude" as a business may continue and labelled as successful, but it may not be profitable and a business may cease to exist but still be profitable for the owner.

Gaskill, Auken and Manning (1993) mentioned several reasons for business failure for instance when the owner wants or needs to sell the business, cease to operate to avoid losses, to pay the debts or when the business becomes unprofitable. Although SMEs fail due to several reasons, however, lack of appropriate management skills and inadequate capital stated as two key reasons for business failure (Everret and Watsons, 1998).

2.3.3 Firm Performance and Measures

A substantial amount of empirical studies conducted to examine the effects of different factors on firm performance. Those studies used several different terms associated with performance as a dependent variable due to the lack of consensus on the definition of firm performance. The terms used include **Performance** (Baker and Sinkula, 1999; Calabrò et al., 2020; Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer, 2015; Gupta et al., 2020; Khan et al., 2020; Lonial and Carter, 2015; Lu and Beamish, 2001; McGee & Peterson, 2019; Morgan and Anokhin, 2020; Rauch et al., 2009; Wang, 2008; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003; 2005; Wiklund, 1999; Zahra and Covin, 1995), **innovation** (Coke *et al.*, 2020; Werner, Schröder, Chlosta, 2018), **New product development** (Morgan and Anokhin, 2020), **survival** (Camacho-Miñano, 2015), **competitive advantage** (Kraja and Osmani, 2015), **growth** (Cassar, 2006; Coleman, 2007; Delmar and Wiklund, 2008; Wolff, Pett and Ring, 2015), **success** (Rogoff, Lee and Suh, 2004; Sefiani and Bown, 2013), **internationalisation** (Acosta, Crespo and Agudo, 2018; Lu and Beamish, 2001), **failure** (Arasti, Zandi and Talebi, 2012; Everette and Watsons, 1998; Franco and Haase, 2010; Perry, 2001), **exit** (Harada, 2006).

These terms were adopted as unobserved dependent variables, therefore several indicators (observed/measured variables) were used to measure these unobserved variables. Researchers have used different indicators to measure firm performance underpinning each term depending on the type of their research. This study used the term **performance** as a multidimensional unobserved dependent variable. Vij and Bedi (2016) stated that the literature on business management and performance show no consensus among researchers in terms of measurement of performance, as both subjective and objective types of measures have been used. Similarly, Rauch et al. (2009) stated that empirical literature highlights the use of both financial and non-financial measures of performance.

This study adopted subjective measures of firm performance because numerous authors noted that subjective measures of firm performance are most common (see Santos and Brito, 2012 and Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; 2012) and justified to be used (Vij and Bedi, 2016). Furthermore, both financial and non-financial performance measures were used. The five performance measures were “return on investment,

sales growth, market share, customer satisfaction, and new product/process innovation". These specific five measures are adopted in this study because these are mostly adopted in the previous organisational orientation studies (see, Baker & Sinkula, 2005; Baker & Sinkula, 2009; Lonial & Carter, 2015; Mason et al., 2015; Wang, 2008; Wiklund & Shepherd, 2005; Wolff et al., 2015). Moreover, the established measures are adopted to enhance the validated and reliability of the data (Hair et al., 2014)

2.4 Factors Impacting SMEs Performance

Although, discovering the success or failure factor is one of the key purposes of business research, however, it is still unfulfilled (Rogoff, Lee and Suh, 2004). Nonetheless, the business performance is a multi-dimensional aspect, however, factors that influence SMEs performance are not generally agreed upon by researchers. SMEs performance literature typically highlights numerous internal and external causal factors (Benzing, Chu, Kara, 2009; Sefiani and Bown, 2013). Delmar and Wiklund (2008) also noted that a combination of internal and external factors are the key elements that impact the success or failure of a business. In terms of internal factors, the focus of the researchers were on individual-related factors and firm-level factors, whilst, the external (environmental) factors categorised into general and competitive environments which impact firm from outside (Safiani and Bown, 2013).

An extensive amount of literature suggests that the factors influencing SMEs performance can be divided into three main groups (a) individual-related factors i.e. factors related to owner/manager or entrepreneur, (b) firm-related factors i.e. factors related to the firm or enterprise and (c) environmental factors or macroeconomic factors i.e. factors related to the external business environment. As Argued by Box (2008) that earlier studies pointed out three main categories of factors that impact firm performance, they are; individual-related, firm-related (Microeconomic) and environmental forces (Macroeconomic). While, Simpson, Padmore and Newman (2012) divided the factors into two broad classifications; the business environment and the enterprise, in which the enterprise is further divided into two types, the owner/manager/entrepreneur (Individual-related) and the business (firm-related). Similarly, Watson, Hogarth-Scott and Wilson (1998) also emphasise on the above

mentioned three major types underpinning (a) internal environment which consists of characteristics of the founder/Owner/manager (individual-related) and characteristics of the business (firm-related) and (b) external environment (macroeconomic environment) which consists of the business infrastructure and the business customers.

Additionally, 34 studies conducted on the determinants of small business growth since the mid-1990s, reviewed by Dobbs and Hamilton (2007). They found thirty variables that impact small business growth and classify these thirty factors into four groups namely, entrepreneurs' characteristics (Owner/manager), firm characteristics, environmental factors and management strategies. While, Storey (2016) identifies thirty-five key influencing factors (see table 2.2) and organised them into; (a) the entrepreneur (i.e individual-related factors), (b) the firm (i.e, firm-related factors) and (c) strategy, and ignore environment factor as a separate type and place most of the external factors under the strategy. Storey (2016) stated that the individual related factors are referred to the characteristics of specific individual or individuals who are the key providers of managerial resources to small businesses and these factors can be identified before the establishment of the business. While, firm-related factors reflect the entrepreneur's non-operational decisions at the start of the firm such as the decision of the location of the firm, industrial sector and the legal form of the business. While strategic factors show what managerial actions are the key source of fast business growth. Storey (2016) suggested that a firm should combine these factors appropriately to achieve rapid growth.

Table 2.2 - Factors Influencing Growth in SMEs

The Entrepreneur	The Firm	Strategy
Motivation	Age	Workforce Training
Unemployment	Sector	Management Training
Education	Legal Form	External Equity
Management Experience	Location	Technological Sophistication
Numbers of Founders	Size	Market Positioning
Prior Self-employment	Ownership	Market Adjustments
Family History		Planning
Social Marginality		New Product
Functional Skills		Management Recruitment
Age		State Support
Training		Customer Concentration
Prior Business Failure		Competition
Prior Sector Experience		Information and advice
Prior Firm Size Experience		Exporting
Gender		

Source:- Storey (2016)

Azimzadeh et al. (2013) conducted a study on the identification of influencing factors that play an important part in the start-up of SMEs and proposed a conceptual framework. The framework highlights that the (a) individual-related factors such as characteristics of entrepreneurs, (b) the environmental factors such as political, economic, socio-cultural, and technical and (c) capital factors such as private finance, equity finance, debt financing and internal financing are equally important influencing factors. **Individual-related factors** are found to have the largest effect on small new ventures, whilst, environment factors and firm-related factors impact relatively large firms (Watson, Hogarth-Scott and Wilson, 1998). Box (2008) argued that small firms due to their small size are more vulnerable to the macro environment as compared to large firms and thus, face higher failure risks, however, most of the studies are focused on individual-related factors and firm related factors and there are smaller numbers of studies emphasised on as environmental factors. Since, SMEs operating in different industries and countries face different cultural, economical and geographical environments (Benzing, Chu, Kara, 2009), the comparative significance of each influencing factor is different due to the difference in business environment of each firm.

Furthermore, Lussier (1995) conducted research that examines the key reasons behind the success of some firms and the failure of others. They built a model to predict the non-financial success or failure of a business (Lussier and Halabi 2010). The model has divided into two forms; the full model and reduces model. Fifteen variables (independent variables) were identified from 25 prior studies which are presented in the full model and a hypothesis was developed for each of the variable explaining the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable (profitability). The variables as mentioned by Lussier and Halabi (2010, p 364) include “Capital Record keeping and financial control, industry experience, management experience, planning, professional advisors, staffing, product/service timing, economic timing, marketing skills, age, education, partners, parents and minority”. The models were successfully tested and found statistically significant in three different part of the world North America (US), South America (Chile) and central-eastern Europe (Croatia). In other words, the models were proved to be the accurate predictor of a group of businesses as successful or failed (Lussier and Halabi, 2010)

The study conducted by Chen and William (1999) suggests that numbers of external factors such as sales tax, outstanding debts, corporate income taxes, infrastructure expenditures, university R&D grants and development assistance programmes have a key impact on firm performance. Small business owners accept three types of business risks; economic risk, industrial risk and firm-level risks. The macroeconomic factors impact 30 to 50 per cent of small business performance negatively and individual business owners can hardly impact these economic factors (Everette and Watsons, 1998; Simpson, Padmore and Newman, 2012).

The in-depth literature review of the numbers of studies identified several different key factors that Influence SMEs performance, directly and/or indirectly. The factors are highlighted in table 2.3.

Table 2.3 - Key Factors that Influence Firm Performance

Factors Identified	Sources
Entrepreneurial Orientation	Wang (2008); Rauch et. al. (2009); Lonial and Carter (2015); Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos (2014) and
Learning Orientation	Wang (2008) Lonial and Carter (2015); Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006); Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002) and Baker and Sinkula (1999)
Market Orientation	Narver and Slater (1990); Jaworski and Kohli (1993); Pelham and Wilson (1996); Baker and Sinkula (1999) and Kirca et al, (2005)
Access to Financial Resources	Franco and Haase (2009)
Entrepreneurs' Gender	Binks and Ennew (1996); Beck and Demirguc-Kunt (2006); Bell (1997) and Coleman (2007)
Motivation	Delmer and Wiklund, (2008) and Benzing, Chu, Kara (2009)
Networks/Alliance/External relationship	Arend (2006); Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos (2014) and Lasagni, (2012)
Family Ownership	Massis et. al. (2015)
Information Technology	Rivard, Raymond and Verreaul (2006)
Supply Chain Management	Koh et. al. (2007)
Strategic Repositioning	Mayr, Mitter, and Aichmayr (2017)
Strategic Planning	Majama and Magang (2017)
Training	Whittaker, Fath and Fiedler (2014) and Gibb (1997)

Source:- Extracted from Literature

To examine the intensity of the effect of the factors on SMEs performance and to build a conceptual framework, this study is focused on three organisational orientations; **Entrepreneurial orientation, Learning orientation and Market orientation and Financial resources**. Organisational orientations are internal factors and intangible resources (Lonial and Carter, 2015). In a competitive environment, resources (including capabilities) of firms emerged and have long been discussed and considered as a key source of competitive advantage for firms (Grant, 2015; Barney, 1995). Nonetheless, resources are important for any firm, however, they must have four qualities such as valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable to generate a sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). According to Zhou et al. (2008), intangible resources are mostly considered to have these four qualities as

they are not visible, most challenging to be copied and keep assets of a firm glued together, so they can be deployed profitably.

The literature search found that the organisational orientations are those specific intangible assets of the firm that are difficult to duplicate, and their positive impact on firm performance is also empirically proven (Loinial and Carter, 2015). The positive relationship between each of the orientations and firm performance individually (Wang, 2008; Hult and Ketchen, 2001 and Spicer and Sadler-Smith, 2006; Morgan, Vorhies and Mason, 2009) as well as collectively, via positional advantage, (Loinial and Carter, 2015; and Hult and Ketchen, 2001) has been tested empirically. However, the effects of the relationships between entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, market orientation, financial resources and firm performance have not explored simultaneously. This research is set out to bridge this gap.

To be organisational oriented is capital intensive for SMEs and financial capital, in particular, is one of those financial resources that are the most conspicuous and allows firms to implement capital-intensive strategies (Cooper, Gimeno-Gascon and Woo, 1994). Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013) argues that financial capital is an extremely essential resource for SMEs as they found that access to financial capital is positively correlated with prominent firm performance.

Although Loinial and Carter (2015) conceptualised that organisational orientations enhance SMEs performance, however, to be organisational oriented firms, they need financial resources. As SMEs have limited access to financial resources which may refrain to be organisational oriented and might be a key barrier in achieving a sustainable competitive advantage and ultimately impacts SMEs performance. The effect of this dependency of SMEs on financial resources encouraged the researcher to investigate the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationships between EO, LO, MO and firm performance, which has not been explored. Hence, this study will adapt and build on the RBV theory to fill this gap.

The detailed analysis of each factor is based on the in-depth literature review of organisational orientations, financial resources and firm performance. The key business and management databases have been utilised to examine the literature, for example, Sage Journals, Sage Knowledge, Science Direct, Springer Link, Statista,

Taylor & Francis, Web of Science, Emerald insight and Mintel Market Research Reports. The preference has been given to the Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management journals, which rated 3 or above by of Associations of Business Schools (ABS, 2015). For instance, "Entrepreneurship, Theory and Practice, Journal of Business Venture, International Small Business Journal and Small Business Economics".

2.5 Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory

The RBV was pioneer by Panrose (1959) by theorising about how a firm's resources influence its growth, which is considered as "a very influential force" (Peteraf, 1993, p.179). Runyan et. al. (2006) argued that in management literature this theory has been used extensively as a theoretical modal. The focus of the RBV theory is on the value of the firms' key particular resources (and capabilities) and not on the products (Wernerfelt, 1984). The theory assumes that these resources and capabilities are crucial for firms to generate competitive advantage and achieve superior performance (Rothaermel, 2013).

In the perspective of RBV, Wernerfelt (1984, p. 172) posited that firm resources are a bundle of assets (tangible and intangible) that are "tied semipermanently to the firm". Barney (1991, p.101) defined firm resources as the resources that include "**all assets, capabilities, organisational processes, firm's attributes, information, knowledge etc. controlled by a firm that enable the firm to conceive of and implement strategies that improve its efficiency and effectiveness**". According to the above definitions of firm resources, they can be divided into; tangible resources, intangible resources and capabilities. According to Grant (2015), the tangible resources are the firms' financial resources and physical resources; intangible resources are the firms' technology, reputation, culture and intellectual property, and capabilities of the firms are their competences to utilise their resources for the desired outcome. Teece (2014) stated that the capabilities are the firms' knowledge and skills that they have gained gradually and enables firms to enhance their resources.

Although, firm resources can generate a competitive advantage, however, RBV theory asserts that all the resources are not strategically a source for a firm to achieve a competitive advantage. Barney (1991) introduced two key assumptions for resources

to be the sources of competitive advantage; (a) **heterogeneity** in terms of bundle of strategic resources control by those firms operating in an industry or within the same strategic group and (b) **Immobility** in firm's resources across firms to preserved the heterogeneity for long term. According to Bridoux (2004) resources heterogeneity means that the resources controlled by one firm must differ from another firm, while, immobility implies that the firm's resources must not be transferable perfectly to rival firms within the same industry or strategic group. To meet the condition of immobility Peteraf (1991) posited that resources should either be perfectly immobile, or they must be imperfectly mobile. Tangible resources are comparatively weak recourses to generate competitive advantage as they can be easily identified and copied (Grant, 2015) and thus, they cannot be heterogeneous and immobile. While, intangible resources (and capabilities) are most important, and challenging to be copied (Zhou et al., 2008).

Nonetheless, the above two assumptions are fundamentally important in gaining a competitive advantage, however, they are not satisfactory to sustain that competitive advantage. To gain a sustainable competitive advantage the resources of a firm must, in addition to heterogeneous and imperfectly mobile, have the following four attributes: (a) valuable, (b) rare, (c) imperfectly imitable and (d) non-substitutable (VRIN; Barney, 1991). Valuable resources are the resources that enable a firm to exploit external opportunities and/or mitigate external threats (Rothaermel, 2013). Barney (1991, p, 106) stated that valuable resources are the resources that "enable a firm to conceive of and implement strategies that improve its efficiency and effectiveness". Similarly, rare resources are those resources that are not owned by many other firms in the same strategic group. The availability of rare resources enables firms to pursue a "value-creating strategy not simultaneously executed by many rival firms" and thus, enable firms to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage (Barney, 1991, p. 106). According to Hoopes, Madsen and Walker (2003), the condition of rareness is already met when the resources have other three qualities i.e. valuable, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable. Likewise, Imperfectly imitable resources are those resources that cannot be obtained by competitor firms or at least costly for them to imitate (Barney, 1991). The non-substitutability of resources is met when the resources are not strategically equivalent and "two valuable firm resources are strategically

equivalent when they each can be exploited separately to implement the same strategy” (Barney, 1991, p.111).

In general, firms deploy their resources (and capabilities) in a competitive environment. If these resources of the firms are heterogeneous and immobile along with being valuable to customers, rare, difficult to imitate and non-substitutable, then these become the sources of sustainable competitive advantage(s) and superior firm performance. The RBV approach is summarised in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2 - RBV framework: A source of sustainable competitive advantage

Source:- Barney (1991)

RBV theory plays a critical role in organisational orientations research, as evident by several previous studies in which RBV theory adopted as a key theoretical foundation, such as Cake et al. (2020); Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018); Dada and Fogg (2016); Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015) Lonial and Carter (2015); Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009); Zhou et al. (2008); Wiklund and Shepherd (2003) and Hult and Ketchan (2001). By adopting RBV, these studies found that utilising a combination of VRIN resources or capabilities simultaneously can generate a sustainable competitive advantage and superior firm performance. As stated by Lonial and Carter (2015) that EO, MO and LO have a positive independent effect on firm performance however, they should not be observed independently. Underpinning RBV they found that when EO, MO and LO deployed jointly they work as a unique set of

capabilities for SMEs and provide a deeper and complete assessment of their effect on performance. Cake et al. (2020) also in line with RBV assumption emphasize that firms to achieve successful radical innovation development and launch require a combination of three key capabilities including MO, EO and LO to respond to radical innovation opportunities in a vibrant and unstable environment. Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018) stated that the link between each construct i.e. LO, MO, and EO and performance is more complex than a simple one, which in turn, enhance the importance of RBV and confirm the need to analyse different strategic orientations jointly than separately.

Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015) tested three models (A) independent direct effect of LO (B) partially mediated effect between LO and growth, LO and EO and EO and Growth and (C) fully mediated effect of LO on EO and EO on growth. They found a weak and nonsignificant effect of LO on growth in model A and B and strong and significant effect LO (via EO) on SMEs growth in model C. This implies that the effect of combined capabilities is stronger than the effect of independent capability on SMEs growth. Likewise, Dada and Fogg (2016) found that EO as a strategic resource directly affects organisational learning (OL), however, in the presence of business and university engagement – “alliance that provides platforms for learning” (p. 90) – as a corresponding resource the relationship between EO and OL is even stronger. This, in turn, supports the assumptions of RBV.

Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009) by drawing on RBV argued that MO is an important firm capability, however, their findings show that market-based knowledge assets e.g. MO need a firm's other complementary capabilities to completely comprehended their value to the firm. Furthermore, Zhou et al. (2008) building on RBV examined how firm-level MO culture and leadership quality simultaneously enhance firm performance by affecting unit-level MO behaviour. The results support RBV as findings show that MO culture and leadership independently may not be unique resources. It is the convergence of both that energies MO behaviour and consequently enhance better performance MO culture. Wiklund and Shepherd (2003) also found that the combined effects of resources and capabilities on performance are stronger than their independent effects. They found that EO enhances the relationship between knowledge-based resources and performance and the effects is stronger as compared

to the independent effects of both EO and knowledge-based resources on performance.

Similarly, Hult and Ketchan (2001) also conducted their research drawing on RBV and found that confluence of several intangible resources such as market orientation, entrepreneurship, innovativeness, and organizational learning leads to the creation of position advantage which then has a positive effect on performance. These findings support the RBV argument that a unique set of resources lead to superior performance (Barney, 1991; Wernerfelt, 1984).

As a result, among various firm resources and capabilities, organisational orientations are those capabilities that are deeply ingrained into the everyday routines of an organisation and thus, they are difficult for rivals to duplicate (Zhou et al. 2008). Although, firms may pursue various orientations, however, this study specifically posits that “entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning Orientation (LO) and market orientation (MO)” are the VRIN capabilities that may enable SMEs to generate a sustainable competitive advantage and achieve superior performance. Firms that utilise these three capabilities effectively may outperform the competitors in the marketplace (Lonial and Carter, 2015).

2.6 Entrepreneurial orientation (EO)

The concept of entrepreneurship is still vague as some key issues that constitute entrepreneurship lack consensus, and despite this weakness, the research on entrepreneurship has been developed in certain areas such as entrepreneurial orientation (EO) which is the dominant area of research and shows a significant interest theoretically and empirically (Rauch et. al., 2009).

EO is categorised as a firm-level characteristic (Wang, 2008) and the basic concept of EO was to explain entrepreneurial behaviour inside a firm (Miller, 1983). Covin and Slevin (1991) argued that a firm must have entrepreneurial capabilities before engaging in certain activities, for instance, the introduction of innovative products or expansion to new markets. Lumpkin and Dess (1996, p. 136) stated that the basic concept of entrepreneurship is a new entry and EO is a set of “processes, practices and decision-making activities that lead to new entry”. Rauch et al (2009, p. 763)

described EO as an “entrepreneurial strategy-making processes that key decision-makers use to enact their firm’s organisational purpose, sustain its vision, and create competitive advantage(s)”.

The life cycle of the products and business models in the current business settings are limited and the external environment changing constantly (Lonial and Carter, 2015). While, the uncertainty in the potential profitability of existing firms demanding firms to develop and exploit new opportunities (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005). Wang (2008) stated that the firms that adopt EO are the only ones that can exploit new product opportunities. Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, (2014) contended that the role of EO is even more important in SMEs; especially in the international market, as they hold limited financial resources, technical resources, and managerial resources due to their small size. They added that EO enables firms to creatively discover and exploit opportunities in the international marketplace and helps firms to achieve competitive advantage.

2.6.1 Dimensions of Entrepreneurial Orientation

EO is conceptualised in numbers of ways (Lonial and carter, 2015), for example, EO has been categories into five dimensions by Lumpkin and Dess (1996, p. 140) which are: “autonomy, innovativeness, proactiveness, risk-taking and competitive aggressiveness” However, Miller (1983, p. 771) define EO as “An entrepreneurial firm is one that engages in product market **innovation**, undertakes somewhat **risky** ventures, and is first to come up with “**proactive**” innovations, beating competitors to the punch”, and thus three dimensions emerged from this definition i.e. “innovativeness, risk-taking propensity, and proactiveness”.

There is a moderate-to-high correlation among the salient dimensions of EO. As argued by Rauch et al. (2011, p. 764) that in terms of explaining firm performance, EO dimensions such as innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness are equally important and mostly there is high intercorrelations among them ranging from “ $r = .39$ to $r = .75$ ” and thus, most of the studies combined these dimensions and used EO as a unidimensional concept. Theoretically, following some key previous EO studies, such as Anderson et al. (2020); Lonial and Carter (2015); Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015); Wang (2008); Wiklund and Shepherd (2005); Baker and Sinkula (1999) and Wiklund

(1999), this study adopted EO as a multidimensional concept, as suggested by Miller (1983). Miller's (1983) conceptualisation is the most frequently employed EO conceptualisation and featured in other EO conceptualisations (Anderson et al., 2020).

a) Innovativeness

Innovation is mostly associated as one of the key contributions of SMEs and a tool of entrepreneurs to exploit the change for different businesses or services (Drucker, 1993) and ultimately to enhance firm performance. Innovativeness as described by Lumpkin and Dess (1996, p. 142) is; "a firm's tendency to engage in and support new ideas, novelty, experimentation, and creative processes that may result in new products, services, or technological processes". Entrepreneurs are inclined to involve in creative and experimental activities by introducing new products or services and they are encouraged to be the leaders in technology by investing in new processes and R&D (Rauch et al., 2009). Consequently, firms' ability to innovate is fundamental as innovative ideas are the sources of new products development and improved processes that ultimately enhance firm performance (Lumpkin, Brigham, and Moss, 2010). Lumpkin and Dess (1996) argued that firms' innovativeness can be anything from simply being willing to implement new lines of products to mastering the latest technology

Innovative firms demonstrate innovative behaviour consistently over time (Wang, 2008). Innovativeness is considered as an important component of EO which supports businesses to pursue novel opportunities and hence, leads them to great progress and strong corporate growth (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005), specifically, it enables firms to exploit new opportunities by using a higher level of technological and/or product market innovation (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005)

As competitive advantage has become a must-have element of business in the current uncertain business environment. The characteristic of innovativeness of the firms enhance the profitability of firms and keeps them ahead of their competitors and may enable them to generate competitive advantage (Wiklund, 1999). Nonetheless, being innovative is risky for firms because they may face a loss of their investments in innovations, however, successful development and implementation of innovations can

lead to the generation of competitive advantages and a major source of firm growth (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005).

Stewart et al. (2003) argued that a major portion of entrepreneurship literature discussed the entrepreneur's inclination and ability to innovate. As argued by Carland et al. (1984) that the ability to innovate and being creative are the key characteristics of entrepreneurs, which distinguishes them from managers. SMEs with an ability to innovate can develop strategies and structures that ease their entry into the foreign markets and thus, reduce the liability of foreignness (Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, 2015)

b) Propensity for Risk-taking

Risk-taking was associated with entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship was associated with self-employment in the early literature, as the key factors that distinguished entrepreneurs from hired workers were uncertainty and riskiness of self-employment (Cantillon, 1774 cited by Lumpkin and Dess, 1996, p. 144), therefore, the term entrepreneurship is mostly described by risk-taking (Lumpkin and Dess, 1996). Risk-taking is defined by Miller and Friesen (1978, p. 923) as "the degree to which managers are willing to make large and risky resource commitments - i.e. those which have a reasonable chance of costly failures". Wiklund and Shepherd, (2005) supported this definition of risk-taking by describing that risk-taking in a firm was indicated with the intensity of owners/managers or entrepreneurs' willingness to take risky decisions by pledging huge resources for investment with unpredictable results. According to Forlani and Mullins (2000, p. 309), the risk is "uncertainty and potential loss associated with the outcomes which may follow from a given behaviour or set of behaviours". According to Wang (2008), risk-taking is considered as one of the key dimensions of EO because businesses face high levels of uncertainty internally and in the external environment.

Carland et al. (1984) posited that similar to innovativeness, risk-taking also distinguishes an entrepreneur from a small business manager, as entrepreneurs mostly exploit new (risky) opportunities for the business and would engage in extensive planning as they focus on firm growth and thus, they need a greater risk tolerance, however, small business managers are less risk-takers as they merely

securing regular income. Le Roux and Bengesi (2014) argued that the literature shows the positive relationship between risk-taking and firm performance, however, their research shows that risk-taking moderate the effect of pro-activeness and a firm's ability to attain high performance. Delmar (1996) posits that to enhance the performance of the firm, entrepreneurs must identify and manage risks appropriately in the business environment.

Although, the researchers are strongly agreed that risky attitude support venture creation, however, the influence of risk-taking on the long-term success of a firm is still ambiguous (Kerr, Kerr and Xu, 2017). As observed by Siegel, Siegal and Macmillan (1993) that there is no relationship between willingness to take risks and business growth.

c) Proactiveness

The proactiveness of a firm is the propensity of introducing a new product or service with the ability to make on-time decisions of whether or not to launch a new product or service. As described by Rauch et al. (2011) that proactiveness of a firm is the characteristic of being "opportunity-seeking, forward-looking" to introduce new products and services and predict future demands earlier than rivals. Also, Dess and Lumpkin (2005) quoted that to be a proactive firm, examining trends, anticipate customers' future demands and changes in demand, or predicting emerging problems are not enough, rather firms must also be enthusiastic in taking actions on such information before their competitors.

The ability to be at the forefront of rivals enables a firm to control the access to the market by dominating distributions channels, thus, it enables a firm to gain a competitive advantage (Wiklund, 1999). As argued by Grant (2015) that the firms that occupy a new market or exploit a new technology ahead of their rivals achieve a first-mover advantage. The first-mover advantage can be sustained until the maturity stage of the industrial life cycle (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005). Liebermann and Montgomery (1988, p. 44) argued that first movers can implement "strategies of spatial pre-emption" that dissuade new entry by subsequent entrants. However, careful monitoring and scanning of the environment are required to implement a proactive strategy to gain growth and internal development (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005). As proactive first-mover

firms pioneer the introduction of new product and technology, they can target premium market segments and charge high prices and ultimately achieve sustained high performance and market share (Zahra and Covin, 1995).

Lumpkin and Dess (1996) stated that the proactive firms are the leaders in the industry as they initiate to seize new opportunities and therefore the quality of proactiveness is closely related to innovativeness. However, industry leader may not always achieve a competitive advantage, as leading firms may fail to achieve the expected return on the introduction of a new product (Dess and Lumpkin, 2005).

2.6.2 Relationship between EO and Firm Performance

This study adopted EO as a firm related internal factor that influences SMEs performance. According to Covin and Slevin (1991), the interest in entrepreneurship research is growing as it is believed that entrepreneurship can improve the performance of new as well as existing firms. Wiklund (1999) stated that EO and performance are particularly strongly related, and their relationship pays off during the two following years. Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) supported the argument of Wiklund (1999) as they found a positive relationship between EO and SMEs performance. Therefore, an investment of small firms into EO may be valuable for them as it has a durable and constant impact and not a "quick fix" (Wiklund, 1999, p. 44). However, only the firms that can identify and exploit new opportunities, are entrepreneurial firms (Lonial and Carter, 2015).

It is noted by Rauch et al. (2009) that the numbers of studies conducted on the effect of EO on firm performance in the past decade are five times higher than a decade before and yet, there is a lack of a common body of knowledge. The studies show mixed results about the relationship between EO and firm performance (see e.g., Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer, 2015; Lonial and Carter, 2015; Rauch et al. 2009; Wang, 2008; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; Lumpkin and Dess, 1996). Several key studies on EO including Wiklund (1999) and Zahra and Covin (1995) found that EO directly positively related to firm performance, however, most researchers including Lumpkin and Dess (1996); Wang (2008); Rauch et al. (2009); Wiklund and Shepherd (2005); and Wiklund and Shepherd (2003) found that the EO and performance

relationship is moderated or mediated by other factors. A comprehensive literature review of past studies is as follows:

Zahra and Covin (1995) investigated the potential of corporate entrepreneurship (CE) on business financial performance. They collected data over seven years from 1983 to 1990 from three samples of medium to large size U.S organisations. The study used both; primary data collected through surveys questionnaires of the company executives and secondary data collected through annual reports and other company publications. The details of the initial data collection process and the sample size is as follows:

In sample 1, out of 200 manufacturing firms contacted a total of 69 usable responses were received for a rate of 34.5%. in sample 2, out of a total of 125 questionnaires sent to CEOs of chemical companies, only 55 responses received however, only 50 (40%) were found usable. In sample 3, 199 firms of Fortune 500 industrial corporations were mailed questionnaires. 61 responses received but only 59 were found usable.

From 1983 to 1990 several firms dropped out of the analysis because of executive turnover, merger, acquisition, and bankruptcies and the data on firm performance or environmental hostility and 1983 data on the CE scale was incomplete. This reduced the overall sample size from 178 to 108 usable response which includes 24 responses from manufacturing, 39 from chemical and 45 from Fortune 500 companies. This reduction in workable sample size required the collapsing of all three samples into one sample for data analysis purpose.

Zahra and Covin (1995) found a positive effect of CE on the firms' financial performance and the external environment of the organisation can have a strong and continuous impact (as a moderator) on the entrepreneurial behaviour of the organisation. In other words, CE and financial performance relationship of firms operating in a hostile environment are more significant as compared to the firms operating in a less hostile environment, which grows over time and prominently the CE should not be seen as a "short-term fix but as a long-term strategy for achieving superior financial performance" (p. 55).

Limpkin and Dess (1996) researched to clarify the EO construct by establishing a contingency framework to investigate EO and firm performance relationship. They integrated the prior EO related contingency literature and contended that there are five key dimensions of EO, and all are important to understand the entrepreneurial process. Furthermore, they argued that the EO and firm performance relationship is not a simple main-effect-only rather it is more complex as there are other internal and external factors of the firm that may moderate and help to better understand this relationship. The internal factors include firm size, culture, firm resources, top management team characteristics, structure, strategy and strategy-making process, whereas, external factors include environmental factors and industry characteristics.

Likewise, Wiklund (1999) investigated the sustainability of the EO and firm performance relationship. The data were collected in three years by using a large sample of small Swedish firms from the retail, manufacturing and service industry sector. In the first year, the collection of data of EO were made by telephone interviews followed by mail questionnaire. In the second and third year, the data were collected on performance, through shorter telephone interviews of managing directors. Out of a total of 808 initial sample size, 630 were interviewed by telephone (78%) and 465 firms responded to mail questionnaires for a rate of 58%, which was reduced to 420 in the third year. However, due to the replacement of managing directors, and incomplete answer on performance measures only 132 responses were found usable, yielding a response rate of 16% of the original sample.

Wiklund (1999) found a positive effect of EO on firm performance which improves over time which is consistent with the findings of Zahra and Covin (1995). Furthermore, the results indicate that small firms' investment in EO is valuable because it pays off in the long term. Wiklung (1999) stated that "the effects of EO appear to be long term and persistent rather than short term and a "quick fix" (p. 44).

Nevertheless, Wiklund (1999) found a positive EO and firm performance relationship, however, it is also found that "financial capital availability", has the largest effect on the firm performance, which was even stronger than the effect of EO. Therefore, as indicated by the results, the firms with sufficient access to financial capital performance better than the firms with a lack of availability of financial capital. It is claimed that in small firms, financial capital is a major resources shortage rather than a lack of

management skill. Although, further evidence of the positive EO and performance relationship has been added to the growing body of research, however, this may spur others to further explore the value of firms' entrepreneurial strategic orientation.

Wiklund and Shepherd (2003) adopted a single moderator approach and examine the relationship of knowledge-based resources (an internal factor), EO and performance. They collected data from CEOs of Swedish SMEs through telephone interviews and mail surveys with a time lag from 1997 to 2000 on independent variables and dependent variable to reduce the problem of reverse casualty and to test the effects of knowledge-based resources and EO on performance. In 1997, a total of 2455 firms were contacted by telephone out of which 2034 took part in the interview which then surveyed, however, only 1278 responded to the surveys. In 2000, 2034 firm were contacted again, 240 firms were found out of business. Out of the remaining 1794 firms, 1647 responded to telephone interview and 827 completed the survey. Out of a total of 827, 218 were disqualified owing to an ownership change and 225 responses were found incomplete, leaving a final usable sample size of 384, a response rate of 15.64% of the original sample (2455).

They found that both knowledge-based resources such as organisational knowledge, market knowledge and technologic knowledge and EO have positive and significant effects on firm performance. Also, EO works like a moderator in the bundle of knowledge-based resources and firm performance relationship. This implies that EO and performance relationship is not just simple main-effect-only rather it is complex.

Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) again conducted a longitudinal study on small Swedish firms from manufacturing (labour-intensive and knowledge-intensive), professional services, and retail industries. The data on independent and dependent variables were collected with a one-year gap. A total of 808 firms were contacted from the sampling frame, however, 465 responded to telephone interview and mail questionnaire. One year later responded firms (465) were contacted again for the collection of data on the dependent variable, however, only 413 usable responses were received (51%).

The results indicate that both EO and access to finance have statistically significant positive effects on firm performance i.e. higher performance linked to greater EO and greater access to capital. Inconsistence to Zahra and Covin (1995) environmental

dynamism in two-way interaction did not find as a moderator between EO and performance relationship i.e. EO was not found to increase the Small business at a faster rate in dynamic environments.

Furthermore, access to financial capital was also not found as a moderator in the way that EO enhance small business performance with greater access to finance at a faster rate. Environmental dynamism and access to financial capital were only found significant in the configurational approach (three-way interaction approach), where Small firms with a high degree of EO, greater access to financial capital, and operating in dynamic environments have greater performance.

Therefore, in support of Lumpkin and Dess (1996), they argued that the main-effect approach provides incomplete results and the EO-performance relationship is even more complex. Although the result shows that EO enhances firm performance positively regardless of the type of environment and availability of financial capital, however, in line with RBV, the impact is found even stronger when the environment is dynamic, and firms have a substantial amount of finance. The RBV theory emphasises on differentiation mechanism when there are resources constrains and a stable environment.

Moreover, Wang (2008) examine the relationship between EO and firm performance and believe that there is a missing link between EO and firm performance. The data were collected from senior executives of medium to large UK based firms from the manufacturing and services industries through mailed questionnaires. The questionnaires were sent to 1500 firms selected randomly from the FAME database. In total 231 questionnaires were received for a response rate of 15.4%, however, only 213 were found usable in which manufacturing industries account for 53.5% and service industries account for 46.5%.

The results show that LO mediates the EO and firm performance relationship . In other words, LO must be there to maximise the effect of EO and firm performance. Furthermore, Wang (2008) stated that firm strategy moderates the relationships between EO and LO, and LO and firm performance (EO-LO-Performance). It was found that the strength of the relationship of EO–LO–performance differ in strength between the two strategic types; prospectors and analysers, as prospectors

demonstrated stronger linkages. EO is one of the key ingredients for success (Wang, 2008) and the key area of entrepreneurship research in which the numbers of studies increasing significantly (Rauch et al., 2009).

Rauch et al. (2009) contended that there are over 100 studies conducted on EO, which led them to conduct a meta-analysis on EO and firm performance relationship. They conduct a meta-analysis and identified 134 publications in the initial screening, which reduced to 51 publications reported in 53 samples with 14,259 cases. They found there is a positive and moderately large effect of EO on firm performance with a corrected correlation of .242.

Furthermore, they found a substantial variance in the scale of EO and performance correlation and in line with numbers of other researchers the results show that various variables, in particular, industry, size and national culture, moderate the strength of the EO and performance relationship. Their finding shows that EO-performance link is strong in micro firms than small firm and industries with high technological intensity benefit more from EO than less technological intensity industries. Rauch et al. (2009) suggested that as the firm size is normally used as a control variable, therefore, the size of a firm should be tested as a moderator in an individual study to draw a definite conclusion. In general, the results highlight that practising an EO is most likely a valuable strategy for firms and recommend that other variables should be examined as moderators in future research.

Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015) investigated the effects of learning orientation (LO) and entrepreneurial orientation (EO) on the growth of SMEs. They tested the direct effect of LO and EO on SMEs performance and the effect of EO as a mediator on LO and SMEs performance relationship. They identified and selected 700 small firms in the manufacturing sector and survey their owners, CEOs or presidents. however, only received 138 responses; a response rate of 19.71%, however, only 105 responses were found useable. In respect to EO, the results highlight that there is a significant direct and positive effect of EO on SMEs growth, and EO fully mediate the relationship between LO and SMEs growth. In general, learning is considered a significant component to identify new opportunities, however, the role of EO is even more important as those opportunities can be exploited with the existence of EO.

Andersén and Samuelsson (2016) investigated the effects of EO and management accounting practices (MAPs) on the profitability of SMEs and to what extent this relationship differ in growing and non-growing SMEs. By using the 'InfoTorg Företag' database they identified and contacted 939 Swedish manufacturing SMEs to collect data. A total of 176 responses received out of which 23 were found non-usable resulting in a total of 153 usable responses (16%). They found that both EO and MAPs have an independent positive effect on profitability in non-growing SMEs, however, no additional effect was found when EO and MAPs implemented combinedly. For growing SMEs, they found that high usage of MAPs in decision making is the condition for EO to affect profitability. This indicates that growing SMEs required resources combination to enhance their performance.

McGee and Peterson (2019) assessed the lagged effects of EO and entrepreneurial self-efficacy (ESE) on firm performance. The sample was drawn from new firms (less than two years in business) located in metropolitan areas in Southwestern US. They collected data in three waves. The first wave of surveys was sent to 1,404 firms in 2006 yielding 311 usable responses, a response rate of 20%. The second wave was sent to 311 firms in 2009 and received 189 responses and only 89 (out of 189) responses received in the third wave in 2011. The data on firm age and size, EO and ESE were obtained in wave 1 and on performance in wave 2 and wave 3. They found that the effect of both EO and ESE on firm performance is positive but differ. EO was found to have a positive effect on mature firms only. While, ESE of founders/managers influences the performance of very young which dissolve over time. The findings related to the effect of ESE on performance are found inconsistent with contemporary literature however, McGee and Peterson (2019, p. 732) argued that "the sparse empirical work is far from conclusive", which indicate future longitudinal research using the a similar research design. They further argued that only a limited number of studies examined the long-term performance implications of EO, however, this research covers the lengthiest time span to examine the impact of EO on new firm performance.

Calabrò et al. (2020) examined the relationship between EO and family firms (FF) performance and the moderating effects of two top management team (TMT) faultlines i.e identity-based faultlines (IBFs) and knowledge-based faultlines (KBFs) on EO and

FF performance. To test the relationships, they collected primary data on all variables and also secondary data for performance measures. To collect data, they identified a sample of 781 German medium to large-sized firms from 'Amadeus' database and contacted CEOs/key informant. They received 144 (18.4%) usable responses, which reduced to 111 as no secondary information of 33 firms was found. They found that EO and FF performance have a positive relationship. Furthermore, strong identity-based faultlines (IBFs) found to have a negatively moderating effect on and strong knowledge-based faultlines (KBFs) found to have a positive moderating effect on EO and FF performance relationship. These findings emphasise on the need to go beyond family membership as the most salient social identity attribute. Further, FFs needs to be properly managed through the competence and knowledge of TMTs to reap its potential for supporting the strategic role of internal influencers.

Galbreath et al. (2020) examined the relationship between EO and firm performance and the moderating effect of competitive strategy i.e. low-cost strategy and differentiation strategy. A total of 1,334 Italian for-profit firms identified from the Aida-Bureau van Dijk database expressed interest in participation. The survey was sent to high-level managers of these firms, however, only 280 responded and 229 were found usable. The analysis of sample firms indicates that an EO is positively associated with firm performance. It was also found that competitive strategy moderate the EO-performance relationship. A low-cost strategy was found to have a negative effect, whilst a differentiation strategy was found to have a positive effect EO-performance relationship.

2.7 Learning Orientation (LO)

Organisational learning (OL) is defined by Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006, p. 135) as "the development or acquisition of new knowledge or skills in response to internal or external stimuli that lead to a more or less permanent change in collective behaviour and that enhances organisational efficiency and/or effectiveness". Although, the learning takes place in a certain environment which is provided by the organisational culture, however, there are different elements of culture that can influence the direction of organisational learning (Palos and Stancovici, 2016), and organisational values are considered a central element that forms the organisational culture (Grant, 2015). OL

is a meta-construct, which encompasses three elements (Wolff, Pett and Ring, 2015), which are organisational actions, market information-processing behaviours and organisational values and are considered as core facilitators of OL (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). The learning orientation (LO) is reflected in organisational values (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997) and considered an important element in examining firm performance (Wang, 2008; Hult and Ketchen, 2001).

Theoretically, Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997) stated that LO is that specific set of the firms' values that impact the firms' propensity to create and use knowledge. In other words, values affect the levels of satisfaction of a firm with its way of doing things which in turn produce proactive learning. LO is a corporate behaviour (Lonial and Carter, 2015) and the firm's activity to convert the knowledge created and used into a competitive advantage (Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao, 2002). According to Wang (2008), the acquisition of knowledge and values must be examined collectively, because the firm's values are reflected in its understanding of how things should be done, which influences its action.

In the extremely competitive markets where on one hand firms are focusing to globalise their operations and desire high returns, while on the other hand there is a high demand of customers and aggressive rivalry among firms. Learning is deemed as an effective firm's essential capability and a crucial component of a firm's strategy for corporate renewal (Slater and Narver, 1995). As quoted by Starkey (1996) that learning and knowledge are the key strategic resources that are crucial in attaining competitive advantage and LO may be considered as a vital advantage generating capability, as it has four VIRN qualities as proposed by RBV theory (Sanzo et al., 2011).

Learning and knowledge are two separate things. Learning is a process that leads to the generation of potentially useful knowledge for organisations and knowledge (that is known) is temporary which needs to be up to date (Harrison and Leitch, 2005). Numbers of researchers such as Slater and Narver (1995); Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997); Baker and Sinkula (1999) and Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006) have categorised learning into two types; (a) adaptive learning – also known as single-loop learning or lower-order learning – and (b) generative learning – also known as double-loop learning, higher-order learning or frame-breaking learning. Firms embrace

adaptive learning to refine existing knowledge, routines and to understand the basic concept of cause and effect relationships between the environment and the firm. While, generative learning demands individuals in the firm to question their behaviour and assumptions (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). Adaptive learning does not require a vision; however, generative learning must be backed by a strong vision of accomplishing something (Senge, 2010). Although organisational learning can be seen in organisational routines (Kim, 1993), however, maintaining and elaborating routines are both important for firms and thus, they must avoid learning which is excessively routinised (Slater and Narver, 1995). Therefore, by going beyond adaption, generative learning may lead an organisation to refine its long-held routines and practices (Spicer and Sadler-Smith, 2006) by questioning its deep-rooted norms (Slater and Narver, 1995).

Although adaptive learning facilitates the development of a range of routines that enhance the firm's highly efficient performance, however, the lack of higher-order (generative) learning cause inflexibility, a reliance on existing routines and delay the process of responding to new problems (Spicer and Sadler-Smith, 2006). Therefore, it is mostly generative learning that leads to competitive advantage (Slater and Narver, 1995; Baker and Sinkula, 1999).

According to Wang (2008, p. 637), the conceptualisation of LO demonstrates two key focuses; first, LO highlights concrete market information processing systems, which contain information generation, distribution, interpretation and memory (the process of storing information), as a tool that generate learning (Sinkula, 1994). Second, LO emphasises on the condition of having three key elements for firms, a "shared mental model, a shared organisational vision, and an open-minded approach to problem-solving", considering the firm as a cognitive enterprise (Senge, 1990).

Nevertheless, entrepreneurial firms and their culture can promote organisational learning, however, it can obstruct learning too, specifically the abilities of entrepreneurs. Furthermore, entrepreneurs are often motivated to pursue their vision and are unskilled to foster a shared vision. Consequently, the firms dominated by one or two key personalities which lead to the problems (Senge, 1990).

2.7.1 Dimensions of Learning Orientation

Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997) conceptualised LO as three firm values which are usually linked to the tendency of a firm's learning. The three values include; "commitment to learning, open-mindedness and shared vision" (p. 309). Numbers of researchers supported the same views such as Wang (2008); Lonial and Carter (2015) and Baker and Sinkula (1999) This study also used the LO as a composite of three key values as described by Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997).

a) **Commitment to learn**

To be a learning-oriented firm, the existence of fundamental value is compulsory that lead to the development of learning-oriented culture and climate. As claimed by Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997) that fundamental value of a firm is a key to LO, as it influences the likelihood of the firm's ability to promote a learning culture. 'Commitment to learning' is the extent to which organisations are committed to place their value on learning (Sackmann, 1991) by valuing the need to comprehend the outcome of their actions which are vital to identify and rectify the error in their methods of doing things (or theory in use) (Baker and Sinkula, 1999). If little the value is placed by a firm, the little the likelihood of learning occurrence (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997). Several researchers including Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997); Baker and Sinkula (1999) and Wang (2008) quoted Senge (1990) as a contributor to the concept of commitment to learning as his work on learning principles is firmly related to the commitment of learning. As argued by Wang (2008, p. 638) that Senge's (1990) work of 'learning principles' is a "call for organisations to place axiomatic value on learning activities". Moreover, Tobin's (1993, p. 55) concept of 'thinking literacy' is also related to commitment to learning in which the emphasis is on the ability of a firm to "think and reason" to be a learning organisation. In other words, commitment to learning is the extent to which a firm sees its value that is committed on the learning activity as axiomatic to the organisation and if the ability to 'think and reason' is firms' axiomatic value (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). In general, the firms are learning-orientated when they hold a central value regarding learning, and they have a commitment to learning when they are willing to place that central value on learning activities.

b) Open-mindedness

As discussed earlier that the process of storing information (memory) is one of the key elements of an information processing system that leads to organisational learning. As past experiences form a mental model (memories) of how things work, within a firm (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997) and the mental model lost its experiential truth with the change in time (Baker and Sinkula, 1999), which may encourage ineffective learning. The ability to learn is the ability to face uncertainty and adopt change (Tobin, 1993) and thus, requiring firms to modernise their capabilities and business processes. Although new processes or capabilities can be effective as compared to old ones, however, the firms are reluctant or incapable to discard the heavily invested capabilities (Slater and Narver, 1995). As mentioned by Schein (1992, p. 6) that “unlearning is emotionally difficult because the old way of doing things, has, after all, worked for a while and has become embedded”, however, such culture and behaviour become dysfunctional and have to be unlearned. Therefore, as argued by Calantonea, Cavusgil and Zhao (2002) that the existence of knowledge obsolescence is high in most of the business sectors, which make unlearning the old ways of doing things equally important as renewing and updating the knowledge base. Unlearning often replace routines and considered an important condition to successfully adopt changes (Tsang and Zahra, 2008).

Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997) stated that ‘open-mindedness’ is that component of LO that is associated with the concept of unlearning, as it enables the firms to question their deep-rooted assumptions, beliefs and routines. Baker and Sinkula (1999) argued that the core element of change in organisations is unlearning while open-mindedness is that important organisational value that initiates the process of unlearning.

c) Shared Vision

Vision sharing is a distinctive value of a learning-oriented firm because the other two components of LO, impacts the strength of learning, whereas shared vision impact the direction of the learning (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). If a firm has a higher level of common goals at different levels of a firm, there will be a higher level of shared vision, which promote a sense of direction (Baker and Sinkula, 1999). As argued by

Wang (2008) shared vision not only determines the direction of learning but it has a strong relationship with firm performance as compared to the commitment to learning and open-mindedness.

Moreover, firms with no common direction and goals fail to exploit the great ideas (Calantonea, Cavusgila and Zhao, 2002), which further enhance the importance of clear direction within an organisation. Employees working at different departments of a firm may interpret the same information in different ways (Brown and Eisenhardt 1995), therefore, a focus for learning is required and a shared vision is considered critical underpinning proactive learning as it provides direction (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). Nevertheless, the importance of commitment to learning and open-mindedness are crucial for a firm to be learning-oriented, as the existences of both motivate individuals to learn in a firm (Wang, 2008), however, the motivation to learn is not enough to be a learning-oriented firm unless one does not know what to learn. As argued by Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, (1997) that the lack of shared vision enhance ambiguity in a firm because individuals are less likely to know the key activities of the organisation, which, makes it hard for individuals to know what to learn, regardless of their motivation to learn and thus, it inhibits the higher-order learning (Baker and Sinkula, 2002).

2.7.2 Relationship between LO and Firm Performance

The literature research highlights that there is a positive relationship between LO and firm performance. Wang (2008) found that LO directly impacts firm performance by mediating EO and firm performance relationship. He argued that LO must mediate EO and performance relationship to maximise the impact of EO. In the context of SMEs learning Dada and Fogg (2016) argued that LO is an outcome of EO and exists as a dependent variable, thus, the positive EO and performance relationship is the result of LO. Lonial and Carter (2015) propose that LO can enhance SMEs performance, however, LO along with other organisational orientations (EO and MO) works as an indicator for the positional advantage which has a significant and positive relationship with performance, which as a result, enables SMEs to achieve superior performance

Underpinning the resources-based view, it is mostly generative learning that enables a firm to generate or identify VIRN ideas quicker and more effectively, which lead a

firm to superior performance (Alvarez and Busenitz, 2001). The firms with an ability to learn from the environment are mainly the firms that outperform their rivals in adopting changing business environment and in enhancing the quality of product and service (Lonial and Carter, 2015). As claimed by Wang (2008) that learning-orientated firms are more adaptive to organisational change by producing new products or services that fulfil the potential needs of the consumer, as a result, it improves the firm's performance (Baker and Sinkula, 2009). However, firm size is an important element in the LO and firm performance relationship, as small firms commit less to learn as compared to large firms which weaken the effect of LO on their performance (Lonial and Carter, 2015).

A study conducted by Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006) is the only study found in the literature that is conducted specifically on LO and firm performance relationship, and mostly the studies in this context, as in the high rated entrepreneurship journals, are conducted alongside other organisational orientations such as MO and EO or their components, for example, Lonial and Carter (2015); Wang (2008); Baker and Sinkula (2002); Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002) and Baker and Sinkula (1999). A comprehensive literature review of past studies is as follows:

Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006) investigated the development and validation of a measure to assess the firm's LO within small firms and what effect LO has on firm performance. To test the relationship between LO and performance the owner-managers of 450 small manufacturing firms were sent a postal questionnaire survey, however, 91 responses received, a response rate of 20.2%. They found that the LO of the firms and their current financial and non-financial performance are positively related, however, the result is not conclusive because the relationship between LO and subsequent performance is partially supported. Therefore, Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006) suggested further research to examine the strength of the relationship.

Baker and Sinkula (1999) studied the relationship of LO and MO with firm performance with an assertion that firms with both, strong LO and strong MO, have a higher possibility of creating sustainable competitive advantage. They used three measures of organisational performance as the dependent variable, which were; "change in market share, new product success and overall performance". They collected the data through a direct mail survey using an instrument consists of a majority of previously

utilised items. The sample of 2000 marketing and non-marketing executive, 50% each at vice-precedents or higher rank was drawn from the commercially available list and half of the sample consist of the firm with sales over \$500 million. Altogether, 411 response received, a response rate of 21% of which 60% from marketers and 40% from non-marketers. A total of 47% of responses came from firms with sales over \$500 million.

They found that LO affects firm performance directly and indirectly. The direct main effect of LO is found significant and positive with all three measures of organisational performance i.e. “change in market share, new product success and overall firm performance”. Furthermore, Baker and Sinkula (1999) found that LO moderates the relationship between MO and change in market share and new product success, but not between MO and overall firm performance. They argued that in the absence of either strong MO or strong LO, a firm may sustain its performance, however, it may not lead to a competitive advantage. Therefore, a combination of strong MO and strong LO lead to a long term competitive advantage, which ultimately enhances organisational performance.

The study conducted by Baker and Sinkula (2002) is an extension of Baker and Sinkula (1999) in which Baker and Sinkula (2002) attempted to contribute to the literature by presenting an enhanced theoretical explanation of how MO and LO affect product innovation capabilities. They found three types of firms that differ in their effect of LO and MO on innovation. Type 1 firms are with weak MO and low LO, have little or no deliberate consideration of the external environment and learn through modelling i.e. it involves the transfer of prevailing theory in use. They described the theory in use as “knowing how things are done, not necessarily why they are done the way they are done” (p. 9) the type 1 firms are limited to manager-driven incremental innovation.

Type 2 firms are the ones with strong MO but weak LO. They are reactive to the external environment and learn primarily through adaptive learning i.e. it involves the learning in the context of prevailing theory in use. These types of firms are usually limited to market-driven incremental innovation. Type 3 firms have strong MO and strong LO and they are proactive in the external environment. They learn from generative learning i.e. the learning involving the replacement of theory in use. Baker

and Sinkula (2002) argued that these types of firms pursue radical innovation and suggested only type 3 firms can sustain a competitive advantage.

Similarly, a framework has been developed by Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002) to investigate the relationship between LO, firm innovativeness and firm performance. To test the framework, they collected data from a sample of 400 R&D vice presidents of large US firms from a range of manufacturing and services industries, through a survey questionnaire in two waves. A total of 187 usable responses were received, a useful response rate of 46.75%.

They found that LO is critical for innovation and firm performance as it has a positive, direct as well as an indirect (through innovation) effect on firm performance. They also tested the moderating effects of organisation age and found that firm age moderately affects the relationship between LO and firm innovation, but not between LO and firm performance relationship. Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002) argued that the direct relationship of LO and firm performance, as found, is not surprising as the importance of this relationship can be seen in the literature, for instance, Baker and Sinkula (1999).

Moreover, Wang (2008) also found that there is a positive LO and firm performance relationship. Wang's (2008) primary focus of the research was to investigate the EO and firm performance relationship, as discussed above (see section 2.8.2). He found LO as a mediating factor on EO and performance relationship. This result implies that LO is directly related to firm performance and must be there to enhance the EO and performance relationship.

Kumar et al. (2020) investigated the simultaneous effects of LO, supply chain integration and operations strategy (i.e. quality, flexibility, cost and delivery strategies) on the innovation performance of UK manufacturing firm. To collect the data the sample firms were identified using the FAME companies' database. Altogether, a survey questionnaire was sent to 1254 firms via email, however, only 266 responded (21.2%), out of which 243 were found usable. The results of the analysis indicate that LO has a positive direct effect on innovation performance, however, not strongly significant. Kumar et al. (2020) argued that the key reason for this result is that the LO affects innovation performance through several other mechanisms too that can explain its indirect effect. LO was found to have a positive indirect effect on innovation

performance via supply chain integration and operations strategy which directly influence innovation performance. However, only quality and flexibility strategies were found to have a significant effect on innovation performance, while cost and delivery strategies were not found to have a significant effect. This result implies that the combined effect of several capabilities emerged to have a better influence on performance.

2.8 Market Orientation (MO)

The concept of marketing is a paradox in the field of management (Day, 1994) and so the concept of marketing orientation (MO), as it is argued by several researchers that despite considerable attention, there is no general agreement on the definition of MO (Kohli and Jaworski, 1990; Narver and Slater, 1990 and Matsuno et al., 2005). Kohli and Jaworski (1990) claimed that the concept of marketing is the basis for marketing discipline, which emphasizes on effectively fulfilling the needs and wants of customers as compared to the rivals to achieve sustained profitability (Slater and Narver, 1998 and Kirca, Jayachandran and Bearden, 2005). Although, the concept of MO conceptualised in numbers of ways, however, Baker and Sinkula (1999) stated that the key operative emphasis is on the market information processing activities related to the competitors and customers and market information processing specifically consists of the acquisition of information, distribution of information and being able to respond to this information behaviourally. However, according to Sinkula's (1994) description of market information processing, it does not include responsiveness but includes the interpretation of the information and storage of information along with the acquisition of information and its distribution. Jaworski and Kohli (1996) stated that MO and market information processing are overlapped and distinct themselves by stating that MO also includes responsiveness, i.e. to make a decision and take actions by using the information obtained. They further argued that interpretation and storage of information are implicit when it is in the process from acquisition to dissemination. According to Slater and Narver (1998), MO is more than just marketing orientation because marketing is just one function of a firm, therefore, to be market-oriented, firms must holistically embrace the values implicit therein and must emphasize on creating superior values for the customer. Slater and Narver (1998, p. 1003) define market-oriented firms as the ones that "committed to understanding both the expressed and

latent needs of their customers and the capabilities and plans of their competitors through the processes of acquiring and evaluating market information in a systematic and anticipatory manner". In other words, market-oriented firms enhance market information processing activities, which help them to acquire, distribute and interpret the information before rivals.

In the literature, there are two key contending conceptualisations of MO (Mavondo, Chimhanzi and Stewart, 2005), (a) from a behavioural process perspective which is conceptualised by Kohli and Jaworski's (1990), and (b) as an organisational culture, which is conceptualised by Narver and Slater (1990) (Matsuno, Mentzerb and Rentzb, 2005). According to Renko, Carsrud, and Brännback (2009) MO was initially described as an organisational culture in which priority is given to customers in strategy development, however, since then both of the terms; cultural and behaviour has been associated with MO. Although, both the models are opposing each other (Mavondo, Chimhanzi and Stewart, 2005), however, there are some similarities too. As Jaworski and Kohli (1996) highlighted that there are four key elements which both of the conceptualisations consider important (a) customer, (b) external environment, (c) being responsive to customers and (d) focusing on broader perspective than just on customers (i.e. competitors). Varadarajan and Jayachandran (1999) claimed that MO is a set of both; behaviour (tangible activities) and culture.

2.8.1 Dimensions of Market Orientation

2.8.1.1 Kohli and Jaworski (1990) Conceptualisation

The term market orientation (MO) has been described as the application of the marketing concept in the conceptualisation of Kohli and Jaworski (1990). In other words, MO is referred to as the structure of a firm that emphasises on the implementation of the concept of marketing (Loinal and Cartet, 2015). Kohli and Jaworski's (1990) define MO as an "organisation-wide generation of market intelligence pertaining to current and future customer needs, dissemination of the intelligence across departments and organisation-wide responsiveness to it" (p. 6). Three components of MO emerged from this definition i.e. generation, dissemination and responsiveness to market intelligence. Matsuno, Mentzerb and Rentzb (2005) stated that Kohli and Jaworski's (1990) operationalisation of MO emphasises on the firm's activities that deal with the intelligence concerning customer needs and the

market environment that affects firms. Furthermore, market-oriented firms emphasize on learning about customers and elements that hinder the ability of the firms to influence and satisfy the customers, thus the key focus of these firms is on the customer. As, the market-oriented firms are skilful in acquiring, distributing, and responding to the marketplace information systematically (Jaworski and Kohli, 1993), they are adaptable to a changing environment, which facilitates successful incremental innovation (Baker and Sinkula, 2002).

The three key components that emerged from Kohli and Jaworski's (1990) definition are described below:

a) Market Intelligence Generation

Market intelligence is more than knowing about the needs and wants of the customers as it also includes the analysis of external factors that may impact such needs and wants (Kohli and Jaworski's, 1990). Jaworski and Kohli (1996) highlighted this market insight as a strategic orientation to markets because it encompasses the external environment that shapes markets and thus, the term market orientation (MO) is more fitting than the term customer orientation as used by Narver and Slater (1990). Consequently, effective market intelligence requires firms to develop an understanding of the current and future needs of the customers and the external environment (including competitors).

b) Market Intelligence dissemination

Market intelligence generated, is of no use until it is disseminated across the firm. Intelligence dissemination is a key activity of the marketing department of a firm (Schmidt et al., 2016) and a core component of MO (Jaworski and Kohli 1993). It is argued by Jaworski and Kohli (1990) that numerous managers emphasize on communicating, disseminating and even selling the market intelligence across all the related departments as well as individuals in a firm and encourage their virtual participation to adapt to market needs.

c) Responsiveness

Nonetheless, the dissemination of generated market intelligence is important, however, a firm achieves very little unless it takes actions to respond to that

intelligence (Kohli and Jaworski's, 1990). Day (1994) argued that the well-papered firms in responding to market needs and in predicting environmental changes are the firms that are likely to have a sustained competitive advantage and superior firm performance. Being responsiveness includes developing and marketing those products or services which meet the recent and potential needs of the selected target market by all the departments of a firm rather than just the marketing department (Kohli and Jaworski's, 1990).

2.8.1.2 Narver and Slater (1990) Conceptualisation

Narver and Slater (1990) conceptualised MO as “the organisational culture that most effectively and efficiently creates the necessary behaviours for the creation of superior value for buyers and, thus, continuous superior performance for the business” (p. 21). In other words, to be market-oriented firms need to develop the values for their customers that are superior and sustainable that produces the necessary behaviour leading the firm to attain a sustainable competitive advantage. Renko, Carsrud, and Brännback (2009) argued that in business planning the firms with market-oriented culture encompasses those values and beliefs that give priority to customers.

Hult and Ketchen, (2001) posited that the key capability to be market-oriented around customers and competitors is the culture. While, Day (1994, p. 38) stated two distinct capabilities of marketing-oriented firms which are “market-sensing” and “customer-linking”. Kirca et al. (2005) argued that these two capabilities enable firms to achieve enhanced performance

As Narver and Slater (1990, p. 21) deduced from the literature that MO has three behavioural components which are; “**customer orientation, competitor orientation and inter-functional coordination**”. Each component is further described as follow:

a) Customer orientation

Customer orientation is a key component of MO which enables firms to better understand their potential customers to produces exceptional value for the customers (Narver and Slater, 1990). As posited by Porter (1985) that to achieve above-average profit, the firm must create sustainable superior value for customers, which encourage firms to develop a customer-oriented culture that enables them to know and satisfy

the needs of the customers (Appiah-Adu and Singh, 1998). Highly customer-oriented firms are more likely to achieve a competitive advantage in terms of market differentiation and innovation. (Zhou, Brown and Dev, 2009).

b) Competitor orientation

Narver and Slater (1990) argued that competitor orientation is the process of generating market intelligence regarding the existing and potential rivals in the market of interest and disseminates the intelligence across the firm to satisfy the current and future needs of targeted customers. Competitor-oriented firms observe their current and potential competitors intently (Zhou, Brown and Dev, 2009), in an attempt to understand their strengths and weaknesses and capabilities and strategies (Narver and Slater, 1990), and in particular, they match the competitors' marketing initiatives as their emphasis is to "beat the competition" (Day and Wensley, 1988, p. 1). Sørensen and Denmark (2009) stated that the firms that are more competitor oriented are the firms that achieve superior market share.

c) Inter-functional coordination

The process of the "coordinated utilisation of company resources in creating superior value for target customers" is known as inter-functional coordination and this coordination of firm's resources is tied with both customer orientation as well as competitor orientation intently (Narver and Slater, 1990, p. 22). Although, individuals in a seller firm can enhance the generation of superior value for buyers (Porter 1980), however, there is a need to integrate firms' human capital and other resources effectively to generate value for buyers constantly and firm-wise holistically (Narver and Slater, 1990).

Product innovation is categorised by Lukas and Ferrel (2000) into three key types: (a) line extensions, i.e. the products that are known to the firm but new to the market, (b) me-too products, i.e. the products that are new to the firm but known to market or the imitated products of the competitors' and (c) new-to-the-world products, i.e. the products that are neither familiar to the firm nor the market. Each of the component of MO in Narver and Slater (1990) conceptualisation is associated with one of these types of product innovation. For example, the products that are new to the world are associated with customer orientation, the production of the me-too products are

associated with competitor orientations and line extensions products are associated with inter-functional coordination.

This study implements a behavioural view of MO as conceptualised by Kohli and Jaworski (1990), due to several reasons. Firstly, the MO construct reflects the behaviour of a firm that is focused on the generation of market intelligence, dissemination of that market intelligence and responding to change based on the generated market intelligence (Loinal and Carter, 2015). These three features also cover the behavioural characteristics inferred by Narver and Slater (1990). Secondly, this conceptualisation is well supported in the present literature for SMEs as well as large firms (see Kara, Spillan, and DeShields, 2005 and Martin, Martin, and Minnillo, 2009). Finally, the MO definition of Kohli and Jaworski's (1990) has a clear focus on market information and behaviour (Renko, Carsrud, and Brännback 2009).

2.8.2 Relationship between MO and firm Performance

Similar to the concept of MO, the researchers have different views on the MO and firm performance relationship. Kirca, Jayachandran and Bearden (2005) distinguished the researchers into three categories (a) those who support the positive MO and firm performance relationship, (b) those who reported a negative MO and firm performance relationship and (c). those who consider that MO and firm performance relationship as a non-significant relationship.

Numbers of researchers argued that MO and overall firm performance is positive and significant apart from the market share (Jaworski and Kohli, 1993; Baker and Sinkula, 1999). It is stated by Jaworski and Kohli (1993) that the market share is not proved to be an accurate indicator of performance and as the effect of MO on market share may take a long period, it is hard to capture the effect in a cross-sectional study. Kirca, Jayachandran and Bearden (2005) highlighted that there is an indirect effect of MO on performance through, customer loyalty, innovativeness and quality. While, Mavondo, Chimhanzi, and Stewart (2005) argued that MO enhances three types of innovations i.e. product, process and administrative.

Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009) stated that the firms with superior MO achieve a 'know-what advantage' which allow the firms to choose a specific combination of

productive resources according to the conditions of the market and enhance their performance. According to Narver and Slater (1990), MO of firms is mostly considered as a tool to obtain a sustainable competitive advantage, however, Hult and Ketchen (2001) argued that MO independently cannot be a unique resource that provides a firm with a positional advantage. Nonetheless, there is a direct effect of MO on firms' return on assets (ROA) but to achieve superior firm performance, MO must work together with the firm's other marketing capabilities as complementary assets (Morgan, Vorhies and Mason, 2009).

According to Pelham and Wilson (1996), a small firm with a strong MO can achieve a competitive advantage and it is the variable that directly positively impact small firm performance. As argued by Loinal and Carter (2015) that strong evidence proves positive MO and firm performance relationship, most importantly in SMEs as it is an important indicator of positional advantage. In contrast to Loinal and Carter (2015) Varadarajan and Jayachandran (1999) argued that there is a limited amount of empirical evidence proving the positive MO and firm performance relationship.

Verhees and Meulenber (2004) stated that MO in large companies is inherently different from SMEs and that may be the reason for the inconsistent result of the MO and firm performance relationship. This differentiation of MO in large firms, as opposed to SMEs, may exist because of several reasons such as (a) SMEs have limited access to finance, which may restrict them to generate the required levels of market intelligence by conducting market research and having decision support systems and (b) the dissemination and responding of marketing intelligence to some extent easier in SMEs as there are limited numbers of employees (Loinal and Carter 2015). A comprehensive literature review of past studies is as follows:

Narver and Slater (1990) established the measure of MO and examined the effect of MO on business profitability. They took the MO construct as unidimensional with three components. By using a sample of 140 strategic business units (SBU) of two types i.e. commodity firms and non-commodity firms, with 440 top management team members identified and surveyed. Out of 440 surveys, there were 371 usable responses, a response rate of 84% with no missing data. It was found by Narver and Slater (1990) that there is a considerable positive effect of MO on the profitability of both types of firms. However, for commodity firms, the relationship between MO and profitability is

U-Shaped where firms with low and high MO show the highest profit and firms with midrange MO show the lowest profit. Furthermore, both types of businesses can pursue either or both differentiation and low-cost strategies.

Jaworski and Kohli (1993) empirically tested several hypotheses regarding antecedent and consequences of MO, by collecting data from two samples. In Sample 1, a total of 549 companies, 49 from marketing science institute (MSI) and 500 from Bradstreet Million Dollar Directory (D&B) were contacted, 115 (13 from MSI and 479 from D&B) companies agreed to participate and gave the name of senior executives of 256 SBUs (27 from MSI and 229 from D&B). The data were collected from two key informants (marketing executives and nonmarketing executives) in a 3-wave mail questionnaire and the executives of 222 SBUs responded. To cross-validate the finding from sample 1, the data were collected from sample 2 consists of 487 individuals. The data were collected following the same 3-wave mail questionnaire and received 230 usable individual responses in sample 2, a response rate of 47.2%.

First, it was found that several factors including top management emphasize, risk aversion, interdepartmental conflict and connectedness, centralisation and reward system drive MO by positively affecting a minimum of two out of three components of MO. Second, the findings indicate significant MO and overall business performance relationship when measured using judgemental measures, however, MO is not related to performance when it is taken as market share (i.e. objective measure). Jaworski and Kohli (1993) quoted two key reasons for this result, (a) market share might be an inappropriate measure of firm performance and (b) MO takes a longer period to affect market share. Third, the result did not support the moderating effects of three environmental characteristics i.e. "market turbulence, competitive intensity and technological turbulence" between the relationship of MO and performance.

Pelham and Wilson (1996) investigated the impact of MO on small-firms performance compared to other influences such as the small firm's market structure, firm structure and strategy, in an integrated model. They conducted a longitudinal study by using the longitudinal database developed by the Centre of Entrepreneurship at Eastern Michigan University, which consisted of 370 firms with an average turnover of \$2.9 million and average numbers of employees per firm were 21.5. Presidents of 71% (263 firms) of the firms agreed to participate in the panel over the telephone, however,

only 68 firms fulfil the need for a complete response to all measures of survey questionnaire for both the current and previous year, a response rate of 25.85%. The firms that responded include, manufacturing (29%), wholesaler (32%), services (26%) and construction (13%) firms.

They found that a small firm's market structure, firm structure and strategy all have a weak causal relationship among each other along with the weak influence on small-firm performance, however, it was found that there is a strong and consistence effect of MO on small-firm performance. MO is significantly and positively, influences three of the four key measures of small-business performance ("relative product quality, new product success, growth/share and profitability"). In terms of the impact of MO on growth/share, the result is consistent with Jaworsk and Kohli (1993) as the result does not show a significant and direct effect of MO on growth/share. However, the small sample size (68 usable responses) limit the confidence in the results, given the number of parameters estimated in some models. Future studies using a larger sample would provide more confidence in these results.

Baker and Sinkula (1999) tested MO, LO and firm performance relationship. They used three measures of organisational performance as the dependent variable, which were; "change in market share, new product success and overall performance". They collected the data through a direct mail survey using an instrument consists of the majority of previously utilised items. The sample of 2000 marketing and non-marketing executive, 50% each at vice-precedents or higher rank was drawn from the commercially available list and half of the sample consist of the firms with sales over \$500 million. Altogether, 411 response received, a response rate of 21% of which 60% from marketers and 40% from non-marketers. A total of 47% of responses came from firms with sales over \$500 million.

In terms of MO, they found that MO, directly and indirectly, relates to organisational performance. The main effect of MO was found consistent which replicate the finding of Jaworski and Kohli (1993) as the results show that MO positively relates to overall performance and new product success but not to market share. Furthermore, in the examination of the moderation of LO on MO and organisational performance relationship, they found that LO did not moderate MO and overall performance (one measure of organisational performance) relationship, however, they found that the

stronger the LO the stronger MO and change in market share relationship and the stronger the LO the weaker MO and new product success relationship. In other words, when firms lack strong LO, MO may lead to enhances performance, however, it may not become the source of competitive advantage that will build market share.

Kirca, Jayachandran and Bearden (2005) argued that numbers of attempts have been made to consolidate research findings in the MO literature either with a qualitative approach focused only to examine MO scale or through meta-analysis which provides a quantitative summary of specifically MO and firm performance relationship based on small samples. Kirca, Jayachandran and Bearden (2005) conducted the meta-analysis, which provides a quantitative summary examining comprehensive models and utilising a significantly higher amount of effect sizes. They selected 114 studies that were conduct on a total of 130 independent samples resulting in a total of 430 effects. The result shows that in manufacturing firms which they described as firms with “low power-distance and with uncertainty-avoidance cultures” MO and performance relationship was stronger, specifically, in the studies that use subjective measures of performance. Furthermore, in manufacturing firms, the stronger effects of MO was found for both cost-based and revenue-based performance measures as compared to service firms. In other words, the MO and firm performance relationships are positive, as consistent with Jaworski and Kohli (1993) and Narver and Slater (1990), however, the relationship is stronger in manufacturing firms than services firms and the implementation of MO generates profit more than the cost of implement it.

Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009), drawing on resource-based theory and dynamic capabilities theory, examined if occupying MO and the marketing capabilities, that enables firms to deploy the resources into the marketplace, enhance firm performance. They collected data from a cross-industry sample of 748 U.S. firms through a mail survey of top marketing executive of the firms operating in consumer and business markets. Out of 748 surveys, only 230 usable responses (31% response rate) were received. They have also collected secondary data regarding the return on assets (ROA) of 108 respondent firms.

They examined each hypothesis separately for subjective performance measures and objective performance measure. In the direct effect, MO was only found significant with objective performance measure (ROA) and not with subjective measures.

However, the result supports the direct marketing capabilities and performance relationship measured using both subjective and objective measures. In the interaction effect, the interaction effect of MO and marketing capabilities on firm ROA (objective) and subjectively perceived performance was positive. Furthermore, as a control variable, available financial resources were found positively associated with ROA, while competitive intensity and organisation size both were not found significant in either the subjective or the objective performance models. Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009) argued that for the comprehensive understanding of the value of MO in a firm it needs other complementary capabilities, therefore, it is recommended to conduct future research to identify those complementary organisational capabilities.

Abbu and Gopalakrishna (2019) conducted a study to investigate synergistic effects of MO implementation and internalisation on firm performance, by adding MO internalisation as a mediator between MO implementation and firm performance relationship and LO as a moderator between MO implementation and MO internalisation. The key informants of 500 marketing service provider firms were contacted by email to collect data. The firms were identified through the Direct Marketing Association (DMA) directory, trade associations, and professional groups associated with specified industries. A total of 151 responses were received with 143 usable responses a response rate of 28.6%. They found that the MO implementation directly as well as indirectly via MO internalization (mediator) effects on both financial performance and customer service performance. however, LO was not found to moderate or mediate the MO implementation and performance relationship. This indicates that firms that exploit high levels of capabilities collectively (i.e. MO implementation and internalization) contribute to both financial performance and customer service performance.

Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2021) examined the independent relationship between four dimensions of the dynamic capabilities (DC) construct such as sensing, learning, integrating, and coordinating and firm performance and moderating effects of MO on these relationships. To collect data, they identified 91,880 Spanish private (non-listed) SMEs (10 to 249 employees) from the SABI database and sent surveys to 4,410 randomly. In total 603 responses

received yielding a response rate of 13.67% but only 509 responses (11.54%) were found usable.

They found that two of the four dimensions of DC i.e. learning capability and integrating capability had a significant positive effect on SME performance. However, two dimensions i.e. sensing and coordinating capabilities were not found to have a significant positive effect on performance. Furthermore, MO was found to moderate the sensing capability and SME performance positively and learning capability and SME performance relationship negatively. No moderation of MO was found on the relationship between integrating capability and firm performance and between coordinating capability and SME performance relationship. Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2021) posited that these results are in line with previous studies and indicate that resources must be leveraged accurately to achieve a competitive advantage and superior performance.

2.9 Relationship between Organisational orientations and Firm Performance (Combined Approach)

The comprehensive literature review as conducted above shows an independent positive EO-performance, LO-performance and MO-performance relationships. Although, Hult and Ketchan (2001) are agreed with the notion, however, emphasised that one specific orientation should not be seen in isolation, rather they suggest that MO, entrepreneurship, innovativeness and organisational learning (four capabilities) altogether enable firms to attain a positional advantage which, in turn, enhance performance. Lonial and Carter (2015) argued that each of the orientations can have a positive relationship with firm performance, however, the potential of each of the orientations should not be seen in isolation and thus support the views of Hult and Ketchan (2001).

Hult and Ketchan (2001) underpinning RBV, examined the effect of positional advantage on long term performance and whether MO matters. They focused specifically on large multinational corporations with a sales volume of over \$100 million and operate in more than 50 countries. A random sample of 1000 firms drawn from Dun and Bradstreet information services. They collected the data through a survey,

mailed to senior executives of one SBU of each corporation to assess the four capabilities. There were 54 discarded surveys and from a remaining total of 944 sample firms, 181 (19.1%) usable responses were received.

The findings highlight that MO can be directly and positively related to firm performance; however, the relationship is not linear rather it is more complex. They found that positional advantage can be achieved by convergence of MO along with other capabilities including entrepreneurship, innovativeness, and organisational learning. In other words, MO enhances firm performance independently, however, its effect is even stronger when firms obtain other important capabilities. These findings support the RBV's argument that a unique set of resources lead to superior performance (Barney, 1991; Wernerfelt, 1984).

Likewise, Lonial and Carter (2015) using the same approach and to some extent similar assumptions conducted a study underpinning the RBV and took EO, MO and LO as the capabilities, however, the emphasis of their study was on SMEs. They investigated the relationship of EO, LO and MO and firm performance by using positional advantage as a latent construct. They identified a sample of 400 SMEs out of 755 firms from the list of Small Business Administration. The data was gathered in 2007 through a self-administrated mail survey. A total of 164 usable responses (41%) were received. The median of numbers of employees of responding firms was 40 and responses received from a range of different industry sectors including metalworking (52 responses), services (28 responses), computer software (20 responses), distribution (20 responses), chemical (16 responses) and medical (16 responses) and financial services (12 responses).

Lonial and Carter (2015) findings are consistent with Hult and Ketchan (2001) as they found that the organisational orientations and firm performance relationships are not direct rather complex. The finding shows that EO, LO and MO are indicators of positional advantage and collectively enhance firm positional advantage, which in turn, enhance firm performance. Lonial and Carter, (2015) argued that EO, MO and LO all have a positive independent effect on firm performance, however, focusing on a single orientation a firm's performance may suffer and thus, they should not be observed independently. This consistent with RBV indicates that when EO, MO and LO

deployed jointly they work as a unique set of capabilities for SMEs and provide a deeper and complete assessment of their effect on performance.

Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018) investigated the relationships between LO, MO and EO in the context of family business. They proposed that a positive relationship between LO and EO and MO and EO is stronger for family firms than for nonfamily firm. They identified 91,880 Spanish private (non-listed) SMEs (10 to 249 employees) from the SABI database and sent surveys to 4,410 randomly. In total 603 responses received yielding a response rate of 13.67% but only 509 responses (11.54%) were found usable.

They found that LO and MO work as antecedents of EO i.e directly positively related to EO, and these relationships are partially moderated by family firm status. It was found that high LO enables family firms to transform knowledge into entrepreneurial behaviour however family firms with low LO are less efficient in transforming this learning into entrepreneurship. In terms of the MO-EO link, the family firm character was not found to moderate. In other words, family and non-family firms in transforming MO into entrepreneurial intentions and behaviours are the same. Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018) stated that underpinning RBV the link between each construct i.e. LO, MO, and EO and performance is more complex than a simple one, which in turn confirm the need to analyse different strategic orientations jointly than separately.

Acosta, Crespo and Agudo (2018) examined the direct and interdependent influence of the International MO, Network Capability (NC), and International (EO) on the International Performance of SMEs. To analyse these relationships, they collected data from SMEs identified from the National Institute of Statistics and Geography of Mexico. A total of 8887 firms identified and using convenient sampling procedure 161 usable responses were collected owners/managers personally using electronic devices.

The results show that international EO and NC have a direct positive influence on international performance, however, international MO negatively linked with international performance. The international EO found to have positive effects on both international MO and NC. In other words, international EO indirectly affect international

performance through NC and has a strong direct effect on international MO. Thus, the findings show that the combination of specific strategic variables leads to superior results for export SMEs

Cake et al. (2020) also used the RBV approach and examined the relationship among organisational orientations (i.e. MO, LO and EO) and their effect on the development of dynamic radical innovation marketing launch capabilities (MC) and their subsequent effect on a successful launch of radical innovation. The sample was drawn from Qualtrics and Amazon M-Turk database panels and LinkedIn. The online survey was developed and administrated through Qualtrics to senior marketing and technical managers, the key informant on the process of the firm's radical new product development and/or launch. A total of 552 managers started the survey, however, only 193 completed it (35%) of which 176 were usable. The respondent managers were from medium to large-sized US firms.

The results indicate that LO has a positive direct effect on EO, MO and MC and an indirect effect on the successful launch of radical innovation via EO and MC. MO was found to have a positive direct effect on MC leading to an indirect effect on the successful launch of radical innovation alongside LO. The findings show a positive direct effect of EO on MO and the successful launch of radical innovation. Cake et al. (2020) argued this result suggests that firms must have strong MO and EO need a learning-oriented culture to help discover new opportunities and to deploy dynamic organisational and marketing resources and capabilities that may enhance successful radical innovation launch. This, consistent with RBV assumption emphasizes that firms to achieve successful radical innovation development and launch required a combination of three key capabilities including MO, EO and LO to respond to radical innovation opportunities in a vibrant and unstable environment.

Gupta et al. (2020) investigated the mediating effect of two key types of learning, downstream acquisitive learning and generative learning between EO and performance relationship. They identified 8,000 privately held high tech SMEs based in the US through the CorpTech directory. The CEOs of a total of 1,200 randomly selected firms were contacted, however, only 198 showed interest in completing the survey for a response rate of 16.5%. The result indicates a positive link of EO with downstream generative learning and acquisitive learning in which the EO-generative

learning link found stronger than the EO-acquisitive learning link. Furthermore, both types of learnings were found to have a positive association with a firm performance where the generative learning-performance link was found stronger than the acquisitive learning-performance link. Both types of learnings were also found to partially mediate the EO-performance link, where downstream generative learning is found to be a stronger mediator than acquisitive learning.

Gupta et al. (2020) stated that in the articulation of EO and performance relationship the emphasize on intermediate processes such as downstream generative and acquisitive learning can be beneficial for EO research. Thus, it is suggested to expend future research to encompass other learning activities in the EO nomological net.

Morgan and Anokhin (2020) stated that EO and MO do positively impact performance individually and jointly, however, research suggests that additional contextual factors need to be determined. Therefore, they investigated the moderating effect of several factors such as firm size, offering services, environmental turbulence and high-tech industry on the relationship between joint EO and MO and new product development (NPD) performance. The sample frame was drawn from SMEs of US Chamber of Commerce directories and sent email surveys to 1,705 senior managers and functional managers. A total of 269 responses received in two waves, however, 179 responses were found usable. The analysis indicates that EO and MO have a positive direct effect on NPD performance, however, their interaction effect was found negative. The firm size (i.e. larger firms) was found to have a positive moderating effect on the joint effect of EO and MO on NPD performance. Offering services as compared to goods strengthen the EO–MO effects on NPD performance. Similarly, environmental turbulence and being a high-tech firm as opposed to low-tech also enhance the relationship between joint EO-MO and NPD performance. The key reasons for these findings might be the larger firms' higher access to resources. Also, firms that operate in violating environments may mitigate risk by closely examining external market intelligence and being high-tech they are more innovative and thus, may enhance future product and service developments that disrupt the marketplace.

2.10 Financial Resources

Financial resources are mostly referred to as financial capital such as cash, debts or equity that help firms to maintain their financial transactions. Although, the availability of funds are the lifeblood of any organisation and for SMEs in particular. However, to have access to funds strongly depends on the financial literacy of a firm, i.e. having financial decision-making ability and knowledge of how to get access to funds. According to Perry and Morris (2005), a misinformed firm with a lack of financial decisions ability may lead them to loan defaults, as a result, the interest rates may rise and may damage the private and government investment. Hence, financial literacy can be considered as an important part of financial resources. Therefore, this study categorises financial resources into two parts (a) financial capital and (b) financial literacy.

Carbó-Valverde et al. (2016) stated that SMEs are generally characterised as firms that have a lack of knowledge in the field of finance and management and have poor financial training which impacts their access to external finance. This ultimately reduces the chances of survival, growth and innovation of SMEs (Hussain, Salia and Karim, 2018).

2.10.1 Financial Capital

Financial capital in firms is referred to the availability of cash i.e. working capital (internal capital) and mix of debt and equity from external resources (Van Praag, 2003; Coleman, 2007) which is also known as capital structure (Fatoki, 2011, Kira and He, 2012), and effects firm performance (Kyereboah-Coleman, 2007). Banks are one of the key sources for SMEs external finance, as unlike large organisations SMEs are unable to raise capital through issuing stocks and bonds (Coleman, 2000). Therefore, SMEs' performance mostly depends on the ability to generate internal finance as well as secure external finance. Van Praag (2003) in their study of "Business Survival and Success of Young Small Business Owners" found that the debt capital which is granted by the bank to selected entrepreneurs are not any more successful than those who start a business with their personal capital (internal source).

Wiklund (2005) argued that several researchers mentioned financial capital as a major factor that influences the performance of SMEs. As claimed by Coleman (2000) that capital is the key element that enables small business to grow, innovate and enhance employment in the economy. Coleman (2007) argued that numbers of studies show that a lack of access to funds can be a key factor that causes small business failure.

According to Stevenson and Jarillo, (1990, quoted in Wiklund, 2005), it is the access to financial capital, which is important, and not the possession of financial resources. Morgan, Vorhies and Schlegelmilch (2006) stated that access to financial resources is the ability of a firm to access to cash and capital, which is critical for the growth of SMEs (Abor and Biekpe, 2006). Also, Storey (2016) suggested that there is a need to improve the access to funds to optimise the potential of SMEs and minimise the risk of failure. However, unlike large firms, SMEs are financially more constrained and have limited access to formal financial capital (Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, 2015 and Beck and Demirguc-Kunt 2006).

In this study, financial capital is referred to the cash available to a firm (i.e. working capital) and long-term funds such as debt capital and equity capital. As the financial capital is limited when there is limited access to financial resources, therefore, the term financial capital, access to financial capital, access to funds and availability of financial capital will be used interchangeably.

2.10.2 Financial Literacy

West (2012) contended that financial literacy is a critical factor of individual well-being, which has received growing attention in the developed as well as developing economies. Although, financial literacy generally derived from studies conducted on individual-related concerns (see for example Lusardi, Mitchell and Curto et al., 2010) however, Mandell (2008) argued that those studies can potentially be related to organisations. Financial decisions, specifically the decisions of investment, strategic planning and borrowing depends on the level of firms' financial literacy (Lusardi and Mitchell 2007a and Lusardi and Tufano 2008). Kurihara (2013) postulated the lack of financial literacy may have a negative impact on individuals and the economy of a country.

Financial literacy has no universally accepted definition as the term financial literacy differs depending on one's skills, needs and experiences (OECD, 2005; Worthington, 2006). According to Kim (2001), Financial literacy refers to the people's fundamental knowledge required to live in modern society, while, financial knowledge is the knowledge of key financial terms and concepts required for day to day tasks in society (Bowen, 2002). The use of the knowledge learned to demonstrate that people are financially literate and the more literate they are the more financially sophisticated and competent they become (Moore, 2003). Thus, having financial knowledge means that firms know about their financial options and have the ability to make the right financial decisions.

Financial literacy is defined by Lusardi and Mitchell (2007b, p. 36) as "people being informed in all aspects of their savings, investment and decumulation, which measured in the context of everyday financial choices". Whilst, Stone et al. (2008, p. 12) described it as "basic financial knowledge about how to successfully manage debt". Hung, Parker and Yoong (2009) argued that financial literacy is not just having financial knowledge, but managers must know how to use that fundamental knowledge along with a range of skill sets to attain required aims (Wise, 2013). Similarly, the financial management system is important to optimise the use of scarce resources effectively and efficiently (Hussain, Salia and Karim, 2018). It is evidenced that poor financial management skills of SMEs increase levels of asymmetric information when applying for external finance, which not only leads to 'financial literacy gap' (Adamoka, Danso and Damoah 2016) but also limits SMEs' ability to access the required financial capital, and thus leads firms to financial agony and failure of a business (Smith, 2011). Financial literacy helps in preparing timely, useable financial information, which enables lenders to make lending decisions by analysing the resilience of SMEs (Hussain, Salia and Karim, 2018).

Theoretically, financial literacy has been described by several researchers as a decision-making skill, which makes the term useful for the business context. For instance, according to Noctor, Stoney and Stradling (1992, p. 4) "financial literacy is the ability to make informed judgments and to make effective decisions regarding the use and management of money". Piprek et al. (2004, p. 4) define financial literacy as "the ability to make informed decisions and take appropriate actions on matters

affecting one's financial wealth and well-being". Similarly, financial literacy is described by Fox et al. (2005) fundamental element of effective consumer decision-making. While, it has been described by Gouws and Shuttleworth (2009, p. 145) as "the process of obtaining financial knowledge to understand and use financial information for organisational decision-making related to planning, control and profit maximisation. Brown et al. (2006, p. 179) supported the definition of Gouws and Shuttleworth (2009) and stated that financial literacy enables business people to evaluate the information needed to make decisions that have financial difficulties or consequences".

Additionally, evaluation of financial decisions is important for firms, therefore, they must have financial information, because firms that do not appropriately evaluate the results of their financial decisions may lead to poor performance (Horngren. Datar and Rajan, 2012). Van Praag (2003) stated that poor financial literacy is the source of poor decisions and poor management which ultimately increase the rate of failure in SMEs. Therefore, the effective use of financial information is crucial for efficient business operations (Shields, 2010).

Another term that is used in the literature for financial literacy is financial education. Hussain and Matlay (2007) posited that financial education decrease information asymmetry, enhance the flows of capital and decrease the costs of monitoring and thus, allows entrepreneurs to enhance their firm's financial performance (Eniola and Entebang, 2015 and Lusardi and Mitchell, 2014). Hastings et al. (2013) stated that the financial literacy skills of SMEs are a vital resource that improves employment and economic development

Building on the above discussion, financial literacy in a firm may be categorised into three key dimensions which are: (a) knowledge of future financial needs, (b) awareness of investment perspective and (c) ability to make financial decisions by knowing the use of financial resources and their consequences. Therefore, it can be derived from the above review that financial literacy may be an important concept in the research related to the effects of organisational orientations on SMEs performance. In this research, financial literacy is taken as an indicator of financial resources construct and used to highlight the SMEs financial knowledge, financial investments and their ability of firms to make the financial decision by analysing the consequences.

2.10.3 Relationship between Financial Resources and Firm Performance

Cooper, Gimeno-Gascon and Woo (1994) argued that financial capital is one of the most visible resources; it protects against random shocks and let firms to implement more capital-intensive and less imitable strategies. As argued by Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) that numbers of researchers found that a considerable amount of financial resources are essential to implement entrepreneurial strategies. Ngeek (2016) stated that access to financial capital is a key resource of a firm, which plays a critical role to achieve key business objectives including a firm's growth and performance. Abor and Biekpe (2006) highlighted that availability of inadequate capital has a negative effect on the ability of SMEs to create new products and services and thus, impact firm performance. International business literature highlights that SMEs have managerial and financial resources constraint which affects their entry into the foreign market (Rua, França and Ortiz, 2018)

Binks and Ennew (1996) argued that limited access to external finance would likely be a significant threat to SMEs growth. Their research addresses the extent to which credit constraint negatively affects the growth firms, i.e. the firms that are young, more profitable and have easy access to their bank manager. They obtained data from a survey conduct by the "Forum of Private Business" (FPB) among its members. FPB distributed 16,000 questionnaires and received 6,101 usable responses with a response rate of 37.5%, from SMEs.

They found that firms that experienced financial difficulties also considered their firms as more credit constrained in comparison with the firms which did not experience any financial difficulties. Although, the impact of financial difficulties had no significant relation with actual growth rates, however, It is found significant with expected growth rates. Furthermore, the results show that the firms that have a plan for future growth expect stronger credit constraint as they are younger, have a poor track record and poor bank relationship. This stronger constrained can be minimised by improving bank relationships and eliminating information asymmetric.

Similarly, Bell (1997) conducted a comparative study to investigate the behaviour of small computer software export firms located in Finland, Ireland and Norway. They

identified 500 firm, 170 from Finland, 175 from Ireland and 155 from Norway, by using Kompass (a global business to business directories). In total 187 firms surveyed with equal proportion by mail questionnaires, with the majority of the firm employs less than 50 employees. In total 98 (52.4%) usable responses were received of which 34 from Finland (53.1%), 38 from Ireland (57.6%) and 26 from Norway (45.6%). Furthermore, they interviewed 24 managing directors of a representative subsample of firms. The key finding of Bell (1997) proposed that the main problems of export firms are related to finance which often increases, and increased international exposure diminishes the factors related to marketing, which implies that limited financial resources restrict SMEs to grow.

Likewise, Wiklund (1999) investigated the sustainability of EO and the firm performance relationship, in which he included financial capital availability as a control variable. They collected data in three years, by using a large sample of small firms from Sweden from three different industrial sectors i.e. retail, manufacturing and service.

Nevertheless, Wiklund (1999) found a positive EO and firm performance relationship, however, “financial capital availability” has been found as the largest influencing factor on the firm performance, which even surpasses the influence of EO on firm performance. Therefore, as indicated by the results, the firms with sufficient access to financial capital performance better than the firms with the lack of availability of financial capital. It is claimed that in small firms, financial capital is a major resources shortage rather than poor management skill.

Beck and Demirguc-Kunt (2006) summarise recent empirical research on the access of SMEs to finance as a growth constraint. They concluded that SMEs are a key contributor to economic growth, however, they may not contribute to economic growth as these firms face greater growth obstacle and one of the fundamental growth hurdles is their poor access to finance. In other words, the availability of finance may enhance SMEs growth, which ultimately contributes to economic growth.

Furthermore, Coleman (2007) assessed the human capital, financial capital and small firm performance relationship. Coleman (2007) used the existing data which is collected by the Federal Reserve in 1998 for the “Survey of Small Business Finances”

(SSBF), in which a total of 3,561 U.S. SMEs surveyed. The 1998 survey was used as it was the most recent publicly available survey. Coleman (2007) used the data from only 2,795 firms (605 women-owned and 2,190 men-owned) from the service and retail industries.

The study, in terms of financial capital, found that financial capital positively affects the profitability and also the growth of men-owned small firms, thus it is considered more important for men-owned firms than any other variable. However, it was found that financial capital only affected the 'profitability' of women-owned firms and not found to affect their 'growth'. Coleman (2002) found that women are significantly more hesitant in applying for debts as compared to men, and thus, women avoid seeking debt capital as they perceive a higher denial rate, which may restrict them to grow their firms. Although, financial capital does affect the profitability of women-owned small firms, however, variable other than financial capital (i.e. human capital) is found more important. Further, the absence of the influence of financial capital (and human capital) on the growth of small firms owned by women suggests that the determinant factor that influences these firms growth included in this analysis, therefore, there is a need to include other factors in the future research that may have an effect on the growth of women-owned firms. These findings highlight that there is a significant difference between small women-owned and men-owned firms when studied the effect of financial capital on profitability and growth

Fatoki (2011) investigated the relationship between human, social, financial capital and performance of SMEs in South Africa. To collect the data Fatoki (2011) distributed 322 self-administrated questionnaires out of 694 identified firms and received 122 usable responses, yielding a response rate of 36.8%. The data was collected on both subjective and objective measures of performance. The findings show that all variables i.e. human capital, social capital and financial capital have a positive relationship with SMEs performance. He argued that financial capital is required by SMEs to obtain a physical resource that in turn, enhance SMEs ability to exploit other opportunities.

Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013) examined the relationship between several different variables including financial resources and small firms specifically from the retail sector and operate independently. They also hypnotised the negative

moderating effect of environmental hostility and the positive moderating effect of entrepreneurial orientation. To collect the data, they identified and sent the surveys to the owners/managers of 2,013 small (less than 20 employees) independent Tasmanian (Australian) retail firms. three hundred and twenty-two surveys were received undelivered and out of 1,691 remaining only 401 (23.71%) responses received but 384 were found usable response.

Financial resources were found to be the most important small retail firm resource, which affects their performance direct and positive. It was found that the retailers with access to financial capital mostly show superior performance as compared to the firms that have poor access and thus access to financial capital is critical for the success of small firms. Furthermore, the moderating effects of both EO and environmental hostility on access to finance (and human and organisational resources) were not found significant. This in turn rejects the hypotheses assuming negative moderation of environmental hostility and the positive moderation of EO on financial resources and small firm performance relationship.

Adomako and Danso (2014) investigated the effects of financial capital availability and resource flexibility on the relationship between financial literacy and entrepreneurial firms' performance in the developing market. A total of 969 independent, Ghanaian manufacturing firms with five years in operations and employ 5 to 500 employees were contacted by telephone. Out of 969 firms, 298 agreed to participate in the surveys for a response rate of 30.8%. The results indicate a positive direct relationship between financial literacy and firm performance. Furthermore, financial resource availability and resources flexibility moderates the relationship between financial literacy and performance. In other words, financial literacy enhances firm, specifically, with resources flexibility and access to finance.

Another research conducted in Ghana by Adomako, Danso and Damoahc (2016) on the moderating effects of financial literacy on access to finance and firm growth relationship. They contacted 969 firms listed in the Ghana company register database by telephone. A questionnaire administrated personally to a total of 598 firms that were agreed to participate, however, only 201 usable responses received (33.6%). The results show that the access to finance and firm growth relationship is positively

moderated by financial literacy i.e. the relationship is stronger with high financial literacy

Fowowe (2017) conducted a research on access to finance and firm performance in Africa. They used the newly available firm-level data from the Enterprise Surveys conducted by World Bank on 130,000 firms from 125 countries in 2008-2012. To analyse the access to finance and firm performance relationship in Africa, Fowowe (2017) used data of 10,888 firms across 30 African countries on both subjective and objective measures of access to finance. The results of subjective measures highlight that a lack of access to finance negatively linked to firm growth. Similarly, the results of objective measures indicate faster growth for firms that are not credit-constrained as compared to the firms which are credit constrained. This indicates that firms with growth plan must overcome credit constraints and obtain more external finance.

Hussain, Salia and Karim (2018) investigated financial literacy, access to finance and growth relationships of SMEs located in the UK, to assess the role of financial literacy to mitigate information asymmetry and need for collateral, and improves capital structure and access to funds. A total of 112 firms were contacted through letter and phone calls respectively to collect qualitative data, however, only 17 (15%) agreed to participate. Further 26 firms were recruited with the recommendation of 17 respondent firms. out of the total of 43 firms' interview, 6 responses were excluded from analysis due to incompleteness.

The findings indicate that financial literacy diminishes information asymmetry and collateral deficit when evaluating loan applications, decreases monitoring cost and optimize firms' capital structure. Hussain, Salia and Karim (2018) argued that financial literacy is a necessity that moderate information asymmetry, which in turn, enhance access to finance and positively impacts SMEs growth

The literature highlights that both access to finance and financial literacy contribute to SMEs performance, however, financial literacy is fundamentally important as it enhances firms' ability to access to finance.

2.10.4 Financial Resources as a Moderator

2.10.4.1 Financial Resources as a Moderator in EO-Performance Relationship

Prior studies, conducted on the EO and firm performance relationship, consistently indicate two key points (a) EO and firm performance are positively related and (b) the EO and performance relationship is not main-effect-only but complex (see, for example, Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003 and Lumpkin and Dess, 1996). Lumpkin and Dess (1996) stated that EO and firm performance relationship may be moderated by several internal and external factors.

Wiklund (1999) examined the sustainability of the EO and firm performance relationship to see whether this relationship is continuous over time, or it just temporarily affect firm performance. Wiklund (1999) controls financial capital alongside environmental dynamism, industry, firm size and age. The data collected from small Swedish firms over three years through telephone interviews and mail questionnaires from a sample of 808 firms. A total of 132 usable responses were received in four waves, a response rate of 16.34%. Nevertheless, Wiklund (1999) found that an EO has a positive effect on firm performance and that the relationship increases throughout the study's time frame, however, the effect of financial capital availability on performance surpasses the effect of EO on performance. The finding shows that the firm with sufficient access to finance can perform intended activities which ultimately impact their performance positively. Whilst, the firms with limited capital are restricted to perform desired activities and thus perform worse.

Similarly, Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) investigated EO and firm performance relationship in a configuration (three-way) approach. A total of 808 managers from small Swedish firms contacted for the process of collecting data. They received 413 responses, a 51% response rate of the original sample. The results show a positive and significant effects of both EO and financial capital on small firm performance, i.e. higher the EO and financial capital the higher the firms' performance will be. However, no moderating effects of financial capital on EO and small business performance relationship was found, in a way that performance increases faster with EO when they have higher access to finance. The finding in the configuration approach of EO, access to finance and environmental dynamism show that a firm's performance is highest

when they have higher EO, a stable environment and low access to financial capital. Nonetheless, this investigation strengthens the prior empirical findings of positive EO and firm performance relationship. Despite the lack of moderating effect of financial capital, the importance of financial resources cannot be ignored as Wiklund and Shepherd (2005, p. 77) stated that “EO is a resource-consuming strategic orientation” and financial resources are that specific resources which can be converted into any other resource easily.

Furthermore, Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013) underpinning resources advantage theory, investigated the several different firm resources (i.e. financial, physical, human, organisational, informational, and relational resources) and firm performance relationship to see whether EO and environmental hostility moderate firm performance. A total of 2,013 owner/managers of small independent retailers, selected from Tasmanian yellow pages were surveyed. A total of 401 (23.7%) responses were received, out of which 384 surveys were usable. In the main-effect-only, the result shows that firm resources and firm performance are positively related (financial and human capital). Further, it was found that financial capital is the most important resources for small firms as firms with access to financial capital reported higher performance. however, no moderating effect of EO and environmental hostility was found in the relationship of firm resources and small business performance.

Khan et al. (2020) investigated the effects of EO on SMEs performance and to ewhat extent access to finance moderate this relationship. A total of 356 Pakistani SMEs, out of 380, responded to the structured survey, yielding a response rate of 93.68%, however, only 326 response were found usable. The findings indicate a significant positive effect of EO on SME’s financial and non-financial performance. Furthermore, it was found that access to finance only moderate EO and financial performance relationship and not non-financial performance. The interaction effect of EO and access to finance was found stronger than their independent effect on the financial performance of the firms. This indicates that resources and/or capabilities implemented mutually can have a higher influence on performance.

Li and Qian (2019) investigated the relationship between financial literacy and entrepreneurship (i.e. entrepreneurial participation and entrepreneurial performance) and tested the moderating effects of industrial regulation. To analyse these

relationships Li and Qian (2019, p. 587) obtained the data of a sample of 3,575 households from “China Family Panel Studies 2014, a nationally representative survey conducted by the Institute of Social Science Survey of Peking University”. It was found that financial literacy has positive and significant effects on both entrepreneurial participation and entrepreneurial performance. Additionally, an industrial regulation was found to moderate the effects of financial literacy on entrepreneurial participation and performance positively in the way that the tighter regulation strengthens the influence of financial literacy on entrepreneurial participation and performance. The result enhances the importance of financial literacy as it supports entrepreneurial participation at the entry stage and improves entrepreneurial performance at the business operation stage.

2.10.4.2 Financial Resources as a Moderator in LO-Performance Relationship

Prior studies confirmed that there is a direct and also indirect LO and firm performance relationship. Although, limited empirical studies exist that show the moderation of financial resources on the effect of LO on SMEs performance, however, it does not prove that the financial resources do not affect LO and SMEs performance relationship. The literature implies that a high level of availability of financial resources can facilitate firms to access essential resources (Cooper, Gimeno-Gascon and Woo, 1994). Lack of financial resources (specifically external finance) obstructs SMEs to adopt LO that in turn affect their superior business performance (Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson, 2019). Therefore, as firms need financial resources to obtain tangible and intangible resources (capabilities) such as EO, LO and MO, this study assumes that the financial resources moderates the LO-performance relationship.

LO is that specific set of firm’s values, that affect a firm’s tendency to generate new knowledge, which has the potential to reshape the behaviour, and convert the generated knowledge into a competitive advantage (Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao, 2002 and Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). Similarly, obtaining financial knowledge would also be considered a part of firms learning, as financial knowledge enables the owner/managers of a firm to involve in numerous financial practices (Adomako and Danso, 2014). In other words, financial literacy enhances

owner/managers ability to make key financial decisions, which in turn, positively impact firm performance.

Adomako and Danso (2014) drawing on RBV theory examined the moderating role of financial capital availability and resource flexibility on financial literacy (i.e. learning) and firm performance relationship. They argued that having appropriate financial knowledge itself may not enhance firm performance as availability of financial capital is the key part of operating any firm. They further claimed that financial resources are likely to enhance financial literacy and firm performance relationship. In other words, financial capital moderates LO and firm performance relationship positively, as it was found in the study that financial literacy is positively associated with performance, particularly when there is easy access to finance.

To test hypotheses, Adomako and Danso (2014) collected the data from entrepreneurial firms located in Ghana. They identified and approached 969 firms listed in the "Ghana company register database". A total of 298 (30.8%) firms agreed to participate and contacted by telephone to confirm the participation. The data was collected through a survey questionnaire. Out of a total of 298, only 198 useable responses were received.

They found that financial literacy enhances firm performance, however, resources flexibility and easy access to finance are resources, in particular, that are valuable for enhancing the relationship between financial literacy and firm performance. It implies that learning does enhance firm performance directly, however, the availability of financial capital, strengthen the LO and firm performance relationship.

Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson (2019) tested the moderating effects of access to external finance on the LO and SMEs performance relationship. The owner/managers of a total of 519 Nigerian manufacturing SMEs were surveyed, out of which 305 usable response were received and analysed. The results show positive but insignificant direct effect of LO and SMEs performance, however, access to external finance strengthen the LO and firm performance relationship. The effect of LO on performance was not only increased but also significant in the presence of access to finance. This indicates that access to external finance will enhance SMEs abilities to embrace a learning culture that leads to superior performance.

2.10.4.3 Financial Resource as a Moderator in MO-Performance Relationship

Past empirical studies attested that MO and financial resources both have a positive independent relationship with firm performance. However, there are limited numbers of studies that are focused on the role of financial resources as a moderator on the relationship between MO and firm performance. Although, several researchers highlighted the important role of financial resources on EO and firm performance relationship (see e.g. Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005), however, implementing a marketing strategy or to be market-oriented also required financial resources.

Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) argued that EO and MO both use firms' financial resources. Furthermore, building on literature, they suggested that with high access to financial resources the positive impact of strong EO and strong MO should increase on export performance. In this regard, they have developed and tested a model that shows the simultaneous impact of both EO and MO on the performance of export SMEs and whether the financial capital and market environment turbulence influence this relationship. The data collection was based on the sample frame of Ghanaian export independent SMEs with the international focus. A total of 332 active exporters identified and agreed to participate. However, a total of 164 useable responses were obtained through on-site questionnaires. representing 49.9% of the response rate.

The result indicates that simultaneously focusing on stronger EO and MO enhance export performance, however, their impact is found even stronger when the firms have greater availability of financial capital and operate in a more turbulent environment. This implies that financial capital effects on MO and SMEs performance relationship and hence, the importance of financial capital on MO-performance relationship cannot be ignored. Albeit, the literature supports the main-effect-only relationship of MO and financial capital with firm performance, however, the empirical literature is limited to support the assumption that financial capital moderate MO and firm performance relationship. Thus, limited literature in this regard encourages to test the moderating effects of financial resources (financial capital and financial literacy) on MO and firm performance relationship.

Although, the review of the literature argues that organisational orientations (EO, LO and MO) and financial resources both enhance firm performance. Whilst, SMEs limited access to financial resources may limit firms to be organisational-oriented firms and ultimately restrict them to grow and enhance their performance. As a result, the effect of organisational orientations, specifically on SMEs performance, may change with the availability of financial resources. However, literature is limited and mostly focused on single or two orientations to address this issue and hence, less is known about the influence of financial resources on organisational orientations and SMEs performance relationships. Also, the majority of the studies are focused on access to financial capital (one indicator of financial resources in this study) and mostly conducted in developing countries. Therefore, this study investigates the role of financial resources as a moderator on the relationship between organisational orientations (EO, LO and MO) and firm performance. This study proposes that the more access to financial resources SMEs have, the stronger the organisational orientations and SMEs performance relationships will be.

Table 2.4 - Summary of the Empirical Literature Review

(a) Relationship Between EO and Firm Performance			
Researcher	Method	Findings	Comment
Lumpkin and Dess (1996)	Meta-analysis	The relationship is complex and there are internal and external factors of firm that may moderate the relationship	We suggest the testing of alternative models (independent effects, moderating effects, mediating effects, interaction effects)
Zahra and Covin (1995)	Qualitative (primary and secondary) longitudinal data	Corporate entrepreneurship has a positive impact on firm financial performance which increases over time., particularly on the firms that operate in a hostile environment,	Variables other than environmental hostility will moderate the effectiveness of Corporate entrepreneurship.
Wiklund (1999)	Mixed-Method: Qualitative (telephone interviews) and Quantitative (mail questionnaire) longitudinal data	There is a positive and statistically significant relationship between EO and firm performance which grow over time	Although, further evidence for the positive effects of EO on firm performance has been added to the growing body of research, however, this may spur others to further explore the value of firms' entrepreneurial strategic orientation.
Wiklund and Shepherd (2003)	Quantitative data through surveys	There is a direct positive relationship between EO and firm performance and EO also moderate the relationship between knowledge-based resources (Market Knowledge and Technological Knowledge) and firm performance.	The relationship between EO and performance is likely more complex than a simple main-effect-only.
Wiklund and Shepherd (2005)	Quantitative data through telephone interviews and mail questionnaire	In the main-effect-only model and contingency model, EO and access to finance have a positive effect on small firm performance, however, the effect of environmental dynamism is not found significant. In the configurational model the effect of EO even stronger when there is a dynamic environment and firms have considerable access to finance.	The configurational model (three-way approach) is more relevant than main-effect-only model and contingency models (two-way approach), for studying the relationship between EO and performance.
Wang (2008)	Quantitative data through surveys	LO mediate the relationship between EO and firm performance and firm strategy moderated the relationship between EO and LO, and LO and firm performance	Entrepreneurial firms must foster organisational learning to maximize the effect of EO on performance.
Rauch et al. (2009)	Meta-analysis	EO has a positive and moderately large effect on firm performance	There are internal and environmental moderators that should be assessed in future research.
Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015)	Quantitative data through surveys	EO alongside having a significant direct positive relationship on SMEs growth, also mediate the relationship between LO and SMEs growth	Given the divergent relationships found by the research; there is an opportunity for future research to test the premise that feed-forward and feedback loops potentially give rise to a reciprocal relationship between LO and EO.
Andersén and Samuelsson (2016)	Quantitative data through surveys	EO and management accounting practices (MAPs) have an independent positive effect on profitability in non-growing SMEs, however, no additional effect was found when EO and MAPs are combined. For growing SMEs, they found that high usage of MAPs in decision making is the condition for EO to effect profitability.	Combination of EO and MAPs as a proxy for resource exploitation is an important contribution to the RBV. Whereas EO can be used to consider how resources are exploited in order to discover and seize opportunities, MAPs reflect how efficiently resources are exploited
McGee and Peterson (2019)	Three wave quantitative data through surveys	The found that the effect of both EO and ESE on firm performance is positive but differ. EO was found to have a positive effect matures firms only. While. ESE of founders/managers influence the performance of very young which dissolve over time.	Only limited number of studies examined the long-term performance implications of EO, however, this research cover the lengthiest time span to examine the impact of EO on new firm performance.
Calabrò et al. (2020)	Survey-based quantitative data	EO and family firms performance have positive relationship which is negatively moderated by strong identity-based faultlines (IBFs) and positively moderated by strong knowledge-based faultlines (KBFs)	Research has shown that entrepreneurial orientation (EO) is positively associated with performance, but several context-specific features and contingencies affect this relationship.
Galbreath et al. (2020)	Quantitative survey-based primary data and secondary data..	EO is positively associated with firm performance. Competitive strategy moderate EO-performance relationship in which low-cost strategy was found to have a negative effect, whilst differentiation strategy was found to have a positive effect EO-performance relationship.	Previous research generally finds that an EO is positively associated with firm performance in the USA, with increasingly positive findings found in international contexts. This study finds consistent results in Italian for-profit firms, expanding these international findings. However, contingent views have gained momentum as scholars argue that the relationship is likely to be complex and not as simple as evidence might suggest. This study advances the contingency perspective by exploring competitive strateg
(b) Relationship Between LO and Firm Performance			
Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006)	Quantitative data through surveys	There is a positive relationship between learning orientation and current financial and non-financial firm performance, however, the result is not conclusive as the relationship between performance and LO is partially supported.	As the relationship between LO and subsequent performance is only partially supported which raise the question of the longer-term relationships between LO and performance. Thus, further research is required to explore the strength of these relationships.
Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002)	Quantitative data through surveys	LO directly as well as indirectly (through innovation) affect firm performance and firm age moderately affect the relationship between LO and firm innovation but has no effect on the relationship between LO and firm performance.	As the world economies become increasingly interdependent, an urgent issue is to test the applicability of the learning and innovation constructs countries other than the U.S.

Baker and Sinkula (1999)	Quantitative data through surveys	There is a significant positive direct effect between LO and organisation performance and LO also moderate the relationship of MO and Firm performance	Both strong MO and strong LO lead to long term competitive advantage, i.e. the simultaneous effect is stronger than independent.
Wang (2008)	Quantitative data through surveys	There is a direct relationship between LO and firm performance and LO mediate the relationship between EO firm performance	LO is directly related to firm performance and must be there to enhance the EO-performance relationship.
Kumar et al. (2020)	Quantitative data through surveys	LO has a positive direct effect on innovation performance, however, not strongly significant. LO was found to have a positive indirect effect on innovation performance via supply chain integration and operations strategy which directly influence innovation performance	The key reason of this result is that the LO affects innovation performance through several other mechanisms too that can explain its indirect effect
(c) Relationship Between MO and Firm Performance			
Narver and Slater (1990)	Quantitative data through surveys	MO has a substantial positive effect on the profitability of both commodity and non-commodity businesses.	It would be useful to test the relationship of MO to additional performance measure that may affect the long-term profitability.
Jaworski and Kohli (1993)	Quantitative data through surveys	MO significantly related to business performance but not to market share	It is important to note that business performance is a multidimensional construct and may be characterised in numbers of ways.
Pelham and Wilson (1996)	Quantitative longitudinal data through surveys	MO has strong and consistence effect on small-firm performance. However, no significant and direct effect of MO was found no growth/share.	The small sample size (68 usable responses) limited confidence in the results given the number of parameters estimated in some models, future studies using larger sample would provide more confidence in these results.
Baker and Sinkula (1999)	Quantitative data through surveys	In the main effect, the results show that MO positively relates to overall performance and new product success but not to market share and the interaction effect it id found that Stronger LO strength the relationship between MO and market change and weaken the relationship between MO and new product success.	Both strong MO and strong LO lead to long term competitive advantage, i.e. the simultaneous effect is stronger than independent.
Kirca et al, 2005	Meta-analysis	There is a positive relationship between MO and firm performance, however, the MO-performance correlation is found stronger for both cost-based and revenue-based performance measures in manufacturing firms than in service firm,	Complex relationships are fertile topics for further research in which the profiles of best practices to implement market orientation both in service and manufacturing firms and in different cultural contexts should be identified.
Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009)	Quantitative data through surveys	The study found that the MO has a direct effect on firms' return on assets (ROA) but not with subjectively perceived performance measures and that marketing capabilities directly impact both ROA and subjectively perceived firm performance. furthermore, MO and marketing capabilities have an interaction effect with performance	Market-based knowledge assets such as MO require complementary organisational capabilities if their value to the firm is to be fully realized, therefore, it is recommended to conduct future research to identify those complementary organisational capabilities
Abbu and Gopalakrishna (2019)	Quantitative data through email surveys	MO implementation directly as well as indirectly via MO internalization (mediator) effects on both financial performance and customer service performance	Firms that practice high levels of market orientation implementation and internalization (combined capabilities) perform better in both financial performance and customer service performance.
Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2021)	Quantitative data through surveys	Two of the four dimensions of DC i.e. learning capability and integrating capability had a significant positive effect on SME performance. however, two dimensions i.e. sensing and coordinating capabilities do not. MO was found to moderate the sensing and SME performance relationship positively, learning and SME performance relationship negatively. However, does not moderate integrating capability and SME performance and coordinating and SME performacne.	The results are in line with previous studies and indicate that resources must be leveraged accurately to achieve a competitive advantage and superior performance.
(d) Relationship Between Organisational Orientation and Firm Performance (Combined Approach)			
Hult and Ketchan (2001)	Quantitative data through surveys	The results indicate that positional advantages, obtained from the confluence of market orientation, entrepreneurship, innovativeness, and organizational learning, has a positive effect on large multinational corporations' performance.	MO can have a positive relationship with firm performance; however, the relationship is not linear, rather it is more complex. Therefore, future studies need to address the potential intricacies of the relationships among MO, entrepreneurship, innovativeness, and organizational learning and in different market conditions, using diverse firm types, and with varying degrees of resource endowments
Lonial and Carter (2015)	Quantitative data through surveys	The results indicate that MO, EO and LO jointly give rise to positional advantage, which, in turn, is positively related to the performance of the firm.	The conceptual paths connecting three organizational orientations and firm performance are more complex than a direct linkage, as by focusing on single orientation the performance of a firm may suffer.
Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018)	Quantitative data through surveys	They found that LO and MO work as antecedents of EO. However, the family business context found to moderate the LO-EO link positively but not the MO-EO link	Our findings support the idea that the process by which LO, MO, and EO operate is more complex than a simple link between each construct and performance confirming the need to analyse different strategic orientations together

Acosta et al. (2018)	Quantitative data through surveys	The results show that international EO and network Capability have direct positive influence on international performance, however, international MO has a negative influence on international performance. The international EO found to have positive effects on both international MO and NC	The combination of specific strategic variables, such as International Entrepreneurial Orientation and Network Capability leads to superior results for export SMEs
Cake et al. (2020)	Quantitative data through online surveys	LO has a positive direct effect on EO, MO and MC and indirect effect on successful launch of radical innovation via EO and MC. MO was found to have a positive direct effect on MC leading to indirect effect on successful launch of radical innovation alongside LO. EO has a direct and positive effect on MO and successful launch of radical innovation	Firms to achieve successful radical innovation development and launch required a combination of three key capabilities including MO, EO and LO to respond to radical innovation opportunities in vibrant and unstable environment
Gupta et al. (2020)	Quantitative data through surveys	EO boosts generative and acquisitive learning through customer relationships, and both generative and acquisitive learning have significant positive impact on firm performance.	EO research can benefit from greater consideration of intermediate processes such as downstream generative and acquisitive learning when articulating and examining the EO-performance relation. Future efforts directed at expanding our predictions to encompass other learning activities in the EO nomological net.
Morgan and Anokhin (2020)	Quantitative data through email surveys	EO and MO have a positive direct effect and negative interaction on NPD performance. The larger firms, firms that offer services, operate in violating environment and high-tech industries were found to have a positive moderating effect on the relationship between joint EO-MO and NPD performance.	Despite historically positive evidence of the benefits of both individual and joint efforts of EO and MO, recent research suggests that additional contextual factors need to be determined.
(e) Relationship Between Financial Resources and Firm Performance			
Binks and Ennew (1996)	Secondary data	The impact of financial difficulties is not found significant with actual growth rates; however, it is found significant with expected growth rates	The growth firms perceive tighter credit constraint as they are younger and have a lack of a track record and a less-developed relationship with the bank, however, where a better relationship is employed to reduce information asymmetries, it is possible that conditions for growth firms may be more favourable.
Bell (1997)	Quantitative data through surveys	Finance-related problems influence exporters with the greatest difficulties and that these problems often intensify, and marketing-related factors tend to diminish with increased international exposure, which implies that limited financial resources restrict SMEs to grow.	Improvements in training and better financial infrastructure may mitigate the problem of SMEs' limited access to finance.
Wiklund (1999)	Mixed-Method: Qualitative (telephone interviews) and Quantitative (mail questionnaire) longitudinal data	It is found that "financial capital availability", which was included as a control variable, has the largest influence on the firm performance, which even surpass the influence of EO on firm performance.	Financial capital availability" has an even stronger impact on firm performance than EO, therefore, the firms with sufficient access to financial capital performance better than the firms with lack of availability of financial capital.
Beck and Demircug-Kunt (2006)	Summary of Empirical research	The availability of finance would enhance SMEs growth, which in turn contribute to economic growth.	Access to finance is an important growth constraint for SMEs and financial and legal institutions play an important role in relaxing this constraint and that innovative financing instruments can help facilitate SMEs' access to finance even in the absence of well-developed institutions
Coleman (2007)	Secondary data from the 1998 Survey of Small Business Finances (SSBF)	Financial Capital affect the profitability of both men as well as women-owned firms. However, it only affects the growth of men-owned firms and not the growth of women-owned firms.	The absence of effect of financial capital (and human capital) on women-owned small firms growth suggest that growth in women-owned firms was determined by variables not included in this analysis, which present an opportunity for further research into the factors that contribute to growth in women-owned firms
Fatoki (2011)	Quantitative data through surveys	Financial capital along with social capital and human capital have a strong positive relationship with SMEs performance	SMEs need financial capital to obtain physical resources that in turn, enhance SMEs ability to exploit other opportunities
Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013)	Quantitative data through surveys	The Financial resource was found to be the most important resource for small retailers, which has a direct positive effect on small firm performance	Entrepreneurial orientation and environmental hostility play a role, though not as moderators of the effect of resources on performance.
Adomakoa, and Danso (2014)	Quantitative data through surveys	Financial literacy improves firm performance and particularly so when resources are flexible, and entrepreneurs can access finance with ease.	Repeating the analysis by relying on data from others developing parts of the world could be fruitful.
Adomakoa, Danso and Damoah (2016)	Quantitative data through surveys	Financial literacy positively enhances (moderate) the relationship between access to finance and firm growth.	Future studies might examine the access to finance, financial literacy and firm growth market in mature economies, where firms typically have more resources to determine how the findings discussed in the current study are different.
Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016)	Quantitative data through on-site surveys	Simultaneous focus on stronger EO and MO enhance export performance. The greater availability of financial capital and turbulent environment positively moderated the effects of simultaneous EO and MO on export performance	Greater access to export finances can facilitate the successful implementation of EO and MO activities concurrently in more hostile export market environments.
Fowowe (2017)	Secondary data from the Entrprise survey of World bank 2006-2012.	The lack of access to finance negatively linked to firm growth.	Firms with growth plan must overcome credit constraints and obtain more external finance

Hussain, Salia and Karim (2018)	Secondary data from the Entprise survey of World bank 2006-2012.	Financial literacy is an interconnecting resource that mitigates information asymmetry and collateral deficit when evaluating loan applications, reduces monitoring cost and optimize firms' capital structure.	Financial literacy is a necessity that moderate information asymmetry, which in turn, enhance access to finance and positively impacts SMEs growth
Li and Qian (2019)	Secondary data from China Family Panel Studies 2014 Survey	Financial literacy has positive and significantly effects on both entrepreneurial participation and entrepreneurial performance. Additionally, tighter industrial regulation was found to strengthen the effects of financial literacy on entrepreneurial participation and performance.	The result enhance the importance of financial literacy as it support entrepreneurial participation at the entry stage and improve entrepreneurial performance at the business operation stage.
Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson (2019)	Quantitative data through surveys	LO has a positive but insignificant direct effect on SMEs performance, however, access to external finance strengthen the LO and firm performance relationship.	Access to external finance will enhance SMEs abilities to embrace a learning culture that leads to superior performance.
Khan et al. (2020)	Quantitative data through surveys	EO has a significant positive effect on SME's financial and non-financial performance. The moderating effect of access to finance was found significant only on the relationship between EO and financial performance but not between EO and non-financial performance.	The interaction effect of EO and access to finance was found stronger than their independent effect on the financial performance of the firms. This indicate that resources and/or capabilities implemented mutually can have higher influence on performance.

Source:- Extracted from Literature Review

Figure 2.3 – Theoretical Framework of the Study

Source:- Developed from Literature Review

2.11 Hypotheses Building

2.11.1 Hypothesis 1 (H1) - Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P)

The first hypothesis addresses the level of the effect of EO on SMEs performance. Prior studies fairly consistently indicated that the EO as a firm-level characteristic can have a positive relationship with SMEs performance (see section 2.8).

In the investigation of sustainability of EO and firm performance relation Zahra and Covin (1995) conducted their research on medium to large size firms. They found that EO and firm performance are directly positively related, and the relationship grows with time. Wiklund (1999) conducted research in a similar context on small size firms. the result of Wiklund (1999) study proposed positive EO and small firm performance relationship, which improves over time, consistent with Zahra and Covin (1995).

Limpkin and Dess (1996) argued that the relationship is complex and there are other factors (internal and external) that moderate the EO-performance relationship. However, Wiklund and Shepherd (2003; 2005) found in their longitudinal studies on SMEs that, nonetheless, EO and firm performance relationship is complex, however, there is a direct and positive effect of EO on firm performance.

Although Wang (2008) found that LO mediates EO and performance relationship and argued that LO must be there to maximise the effect of EO on firm performance. However, Rauch et al. (2009) in their meta-analysis found a direct and moderately large positive effect of EO on firm performance. Thus, the results indicate EO is an important element for better firm performance and suggest that there is a need to examine other moderators in future research.

Furthermore, Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015) also found direct and positive effect of EO on SMEs growth and Andersén and Samuelsson (2016) found independent positive effect EO on profitability in non-growing SMEs when applied alongside management accounting practices (MAPs). Also, positive direct effects of EO was found on mature firms by McGee and Peterson (2019), on family firm performance by Calabrò et al. (2020), on firm performance by Galbreath et al. (2020), on new product development performance by Morgan and Anokhin (2020) and on MO and successful launch of

radical innovation by Cake et al. (2020). Acosta, Crespo and Agudo (2018) found that international EO has a direct as well as indirect (via network capabilities) positive effect of on international performance.

Using Miller's (1983) conceptualisation, EO comprises of three dimensions, Innovativeness, propensity to take risk and proactiveness. Concerning the effect of an individual component of EO, it is stated by Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) that each component universally positively impacts firm performance. According to Rauch et al (2011), all three components are equally important to explain performance.

Therefore, based on the discussion above, as derived from the empirical EO literature, the first hypothesis of this study is that **“EO has a direct and positive effect on firm performance”**.

2.11.2 Hypothesis 2 (H2) – Learning orientation (LO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).

Hypothesis two is related to the effect of LO on SMEs performance. The discussion in section 2.9 provides a general assertion in this context. This study examined several studies that were conducted on the effect of LO on firm performance along with other orientations and variables, however, there were limited studies found that were conducted independently on the effect of LO on firm performance.

In the study of Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002), they investigate the effect of LO on firm innovativeness and firm performance. They found that LO is critical for innovation and firm performance. Furthermore, LO not only directly relates to firm performance, but it also indirectly influences performance through innovation. While Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006) conducted a study on small manufacturing firms and found a positive LO and current firm performance. However, this result was partially supported and thus, not conclusive. Therefore, Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006) recommended further research to examine the strength of the effect of LO on performance.

Moreover, Baker and Sinkula (1999) found that the effect of LO on firm performance is direct as well as indirect. They found that the direct main-effect-only effect of LO

was significantly and positively linked to organisational performance. They argued that firms with a learning orientation may be successful in establishing a mechanism that enhances growth. Similarly, it was found by Wang (2008) that the effect of LO is positive and direct on SMEs performance. He argued that learning-oriented firms are more adaptive to changing business conditions by creating new products that fulfil the consumers' potential needs, as a result, it enhances the performance of the firms (Baker and Sinkula, 2009).

Kumar et al. (2020) found that although LO has a positive direct effect on innovation performance, however, it was not strongly significant. They stated that the key reason of this result is LO's indirect effect on innovation. LO was found to have a positive indirect effect on innovation performance via supply chain integration and operations strategy (i.e. quality and flexibility strategies) which directly influence innovation performance. Cake et al. (2020) found that LO has a positive direct effect on EO, MO and marketing capability (MC) and indirect effect on successful launch of radical innovation via EO and MC. Although Kumar et al. (2020) and cake et al. (2020) did not find direct effect of LO on innovation performance, however, Lonial and Carter (2015) argued that firms that learn from environment mostly outperform their rivals in adopting changing business environment and in enhancing the quality of product and service.

Similarly, Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018) found that LO (alongside MO) work as antecedents of EO i.e. directly positively related to EO. In other word high LO enable family firms to transforming knowledge into entrepreneurial behaviour. While Gupta et al. (2020) found that EO enhance performance through generative and acquisitive learning i.e. both types of learning have direct positive link with firm performance. Lonial and Carter (2015) discussed that firms that learn from environment mostly outperform their rivals in adopting changing business environment and in enhancing the quality of product and service.

Therefore, as per the above discussion, this study hypothesised that **“LO has a direct and positive effect on firm performance”**.

2.11.3 Hypothesis 3 (H3) – Market orientation (MO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).

The third hypothesis is based on the MO and SMEs performance relationship. As discussed in section 2.10, MO has predominantly been associated positively to SMEs performance. It provides firms 'know-what' advantage which enables firms to choose productive resources combination and thus, enhances firm performance. According to Porter (1985) a firm must create sustainable superior value for customers to achieve above-average profit. MO has been found by Narver and Slater (1990) as a key determinant of profitability. They argued that 'customer orientations', a key component of MO, brings superior value for the customers as customer-oriented firms better understand their customers.

Similarly, Jaworski and Kohli (1993) found that there is a significant MO and overall business performance relationship apart from the market share. Baker and Sinkula's (1999) finding of the main effect of MO was consistent with the results of Jaworski and Kohli (1993).

Likewise, Kirca et. al. (2005) in their meta-analysis also found that there is a positive MO and firm performance relationship. Jaworski and Kohli (1993) argued that nonetheless MO enhances sales performance, but the cost of its implementation might reduce profits. While, Kirca et.al (2005) discussed that firms may need other resources to implement MO, however, amount of profits generated by implementing MO is more than the costs of its implementation. Pelham and Wilson (1996) found that the effect of MO on small-firm performance is strong and consistent. They argued that strong MO can lead small businesses to achieve a competitive advantage. Loinal and Carter (2015) supported these findings and stated that MO and firm performance relationship is positive, specifically for SMEs.

The findings of Pelham and Wilson (1996) and Kirca et.al (2005) were also consistent with the finding of Jaworski and Kohli (1993) in terms of market share. Jaworski and Kohli (1993) highlighted two key reasons for this result: (a) the market share might not be an appropriate performance measure and (b) MO takes a longer period to effectively market share.

Abbu and Gopalakrishna (2019) also found direct as well as indirect effect (via MO internalisation) of MO implementation on both financial performance and customer service performance. Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2021) found that MO enhance the relationship between sensing capability and SME performance positively. Morgan and Anokhin (2020) also found direct positive relationship between MO and new product development performance.

In general, the assumption here is that the market-oriented firms can satisfy customer needs and thus, enhance performance. Therefore, the third hypothesis is that **“MO has a direct and positive effect on firm performance”**.

2.11.4 Hypothesis 4 (H4) – Financial Resources (FR) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).

The fourth, hypothesis address the relationship between financial resources (financial capital and financial literacy) and SMEs performance. As it can be derived from the discussion above (see section 2.12) that financial resources are essential for the success of SMEs. As argued by Bell (1997) that limited financial resources restrict SMEs to grow as financial related problems found to be the greatest difficulties for export SMEs. Wiklund (1999) argued that the firms with sufficient access to financial capital performance better than the firms with lack of availability of financial capital because it was found to have a positive effect on SMEs performance. Coleman (2000) posited that financial capital is the key element that enables a small business to grow, innovate and enhance employment in the economy.

Likewise, Beck and Demircuc-Kunt (2006) summarize the prior empirical research and quoted that limited access to finance is one of the fundamental growth obstacles. Thus, the availability of financial capital would enhance SMEs growth. Coleman (2007) found that financial capital positively affects the profitability of both men-owned and women-owned small firms. Fatoki (2011) found that financial capital along with social capital and human capital have a strong positive relationship with SMEs performance. He stated that funds are required by SMEs to acquire physical resources that in turn, enhance SMEs ability to exploit other opportunities.

Also, Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013) found that the most important resource for small firms is financial capital. They argued that small retail firms with access to financial capital are also highly likely to report higher performance. Furthermore, access to capital is found as one of those small set of resources that is positively linked to small firm performance and thus, appears to be critical to the success of small retailers. As found by Fowowe (2017) that lack of access to finance negatively linked to firm growth, and thus, firms with grow plan must overcome credit constraints and obtain more external finance

Adomako and Danso (2014) found financial literacy as a resource that enhances performance, specifically, when entrepreneurs have access to finance and resources are flexible. Whilst, Adomako, Danso and Damoahc (2016) found that financial literacy enhances access to finance and firm growth relationship. Albeit, both access to financial capital and financial literacy contribute to SMEs performance, however, financial literacy is fundamentally important as it enhances firms' ability to access to finance.

Similarly, Hussain, Salia and Karim (2018) found that financial literacy diminishes information asymmetry and collateral insufficiency, reduces cost of monitoring and enhance firms' capital structure, which in turn, enhance access to finance and positively impacts on SMEs growth.

Therefore, the study hypothesised that **“Financial resources (FR) have a direct and positive effect on firm performance”**.

2.11.5 Hypothesis 5 (H5) - The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between EO and Firm Performance (P).

Hypothesis 5 emphasised on the role of financial resources as a moderator on EO and SMEs performance relationship. Lumpkin and Dess (1996) stated that EO and firm performance relationship is moderated by several internal and external factors. Financial resources are indeed key resources required by the firms to be organisational oriented. Wiklund (1999) found that financial resources have a positive effect on performance which surpass the effect of EO on SMEs performance. The

results also highlight those firms with sufficient access to capital to perform much better than the firms which have limited access to capital. Furthermore, financial capital protects firms in uncertainty and facilitates change (Wiklund, 1999)

Although, Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) did not find the moderating effect of financial capital on the EO and SMEs performance relationship and Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013) did not find the moderating effect of EO on the access to financial capital and SMEs performance relationship, however, Wiklund and Shepherd (2005, p. 77) argued that the “EO is a resource-consuming strategic orientation” and thus, raise firms’ requirement of resources to facilitate EO. Firms with abundant of resources (financial resources in particular) may have more capacity to employ entrepreneurial activities as compared to the firms with “sparse resources” (Covin and Slevin, 1991, p. 15) as financial capital is the most generic resource that can be converted into any resource (Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer, 2013). Hence, access to finance is fundamental, for SMEs, as such firms are mostly innovating and growth-oriented and required higher financial resources. Also, Khan et al. (2020) found a positive and significant effect of EO on performance and the moderating effects of access to finance on EO and financial performance,

Therefore, depending on the above arguments, this study assumed that the financial resources construct may be a moderator in the EO and SMEs performance relationship, and so the fifth hypothesis of this study is that **“the moderating effect of Financial Resources strengthens the positive relationship between EO and firm performance”**.

2.11.6 Hypothesis 6 (H6) - The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between LO and Firm Performance (P).

This hypothesis emphasises on the assumption that there is a moderating effect of financial resources on LO and SMEs performance relationship. LO is a firm value that generates new knowledge and converts it into a competitive advantage. Therefore, in this study, obtaining financial knowledge or financial literacy is viewed as a part of a firm’s learning and considered important for the success of a firm.

Adomako and Danso (2014) found that financial literacy and firm performance are positively related, as consistent with other LO literature. They emphasised that easy access to financial resources improve financial literacy (learning) and SMEs performance relationship. In other words, nonetheless, learning directly influence performance, but the availability of financial resources strengthens the relationship between LO and firm performance.

Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson (2019) found that LO has a positive but insignificant effect on SMEs performance however, access to external finance strengthen the LO and firm performance relationship. The effect of LO on performance was not only increased but it was also significant in the presence of access to finance.

Consequently, this study assumed that **“the moderating effect of financial resources strengthen the positive relationship between LO and SMEs performance”**.

2.11.7 Hypothesis 7 (H7) - The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between MO and Firm Performance (P).

Finally, Hypothesis 7 presumes that financial resources moderate the MO and SMEs performance relationship, however, the literature is inadequate to support this assumption. Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) argued that MO and EO both utilise the financial resources of the firms. Although, they found that firms with a simultaneous focus on MO and EO enhance export performance, however, when these firms also have high availability of financial resources then their effect on SMEs performance is increased.

Furthermore, MO is a process of generation and dissemination of market intelligence and being responsive to that intelligence (Kohil and Jaworski, 1990), which implies that MO can be a resource-consuming organisational orientation. Whereas, financial resources are those universal resources which can be transformed into other types of resources easily (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005), thus, they facilitate firms to have access to other essential resources. Therefore, it can be assumed that financial resources moderates the MO and SMEs performance relationship. Moreover, the

limited literature to support this assumption further encourages the testing of this relationship.

Therefore, depending on the above discussion it is hypothesised that; **“The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between MO and firm performance (P)”**.

Figure 2.4 - Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source:- Developed from Literature Review

3 Chapter Three - Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

Chapter two – Literature Review – critically review relevant literature, identified key factors that influence SMEs performance and built a conceptual framework. This chapter presents the methodology of this research. Firstly, the chapter discusses the key philosophical foundations of the research and critically analysis three key research philosophies including positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism leading to why positivism philosophy is adopted in this research. The chapter then presents the research approach (deductive/inductive), highlights the four phases of the research process and outlines the research design. Then, the chapter presents the measurement of variables, leading to the development of the questionnaire instrument, pre-testing and pilot testing of the instrument. Next, the population and sample of this study are discussed, and the justifications of the sampling technique applied are presented. The chapter then posits the real-time experience of identifying and gaining access to SMEs, the actual process of data collection, response overview and ethical consideration. Furthermore, the chapter elucidates the techniques of measuring the validity and reliability of the survey instrument, followed by an overview of the statistical procedure. Finally, the chapter ends with a chapter summary.

3.2 Philosophical Foundation of the Research

Several terms used in the literature to represent the philosophical foundation of the Research, such as research philosophy (Crotty, 1998), research paradigm (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016), philosophical worldview (Creswell and Creswell, 2018) and generally it is known as a research methodology (Neuman, 2014). Creswell and Creswell (2018) used the term philosophical worldview and defined it as “a basic set of beliefs that guide action”. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) stated that the chosen research philosophy represent significant assumptions of the researcher’s view of the world. Although, there are different definitions of the research philosophy, however, all the definitions share the central meaning by assuming that the research philosophy represents researchers’ interpretation of phenomena and their thinking about the development of knowledge.

Although research philosophy remains hidden, however, Creswell and Creswell (2018) suggest that researchers should make the philosophical worldview of their study explicit, as it will justify why the researcher uses a specific data collection method. As argued by Mukhopadhyay and Gupta (2014) that the identification of paradigm together with the research subject, impact the choice of research method.

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) examined three major philosophical thinking: (a) ontology, (b) epistemology and (c) axiology and argued that each influences the thinking about the research process, underlying research strategy, and research methods based on the researchers' assumptions.

3.2.1 Ontology

Ontology is that philosophical thinking that is focused on the nature of reality or the existence of reality (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016; Neuman, 2014). According to Antwi and Hamza (2015) ontology identifies the form and nature of reality and what can be known about reality. The key concerns of the ontology are whether the existence of social reality is objective, i.e. it is external to social actors, or whether it is subjective (constructive), i.e. it is created by social actors' views and subsequent actions (Bryman, 2016). Therefore, ontology has two categories (a) objectivism and (b) subjectivism.

3.2.1.1 Objectivism

Objectivism is that aspect of the ontological position that implies that social reality has independent existence (i.e. external) to social actors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016) and it is beyond social actors' reach or influence (Bryman, 2016). Neuman (2014) refers to objectivism as realism and posited that the realists see an independent world exist out there for them to discover.

3.2.1.2 Subjectivism

Subjectivism is often associated with constructionism which is that ontological position that implies that social actors (including researcher) create social phenomena from their perceptions and consequent actions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). As argued by Wahyuni (2012) subjectivists believe that social actors develop reality and

individual contributions to social phenomena. According to Bryman (2016), social phenomena is not just created by social interaction, but it is revising constantly. The subjectivism here is not realist rather it is nominalist as the world out there to discover is not independent as it is influenced by the beliefs of social actors (Neuman, 2014). Thus, subjectivist believe that social reality is what social actors associate with it (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

3.2.2 Epistemology

Epistemology is related to what constitutes acceptable knowledge in a field of study and concerns with the notion that if the method of studying natural science be implemented to study social science? (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Epistemology is the study of criteria that enables the researchers to distinguish what creates scientific knowledge from what does not create (Johnson and Duberley, 2000). Antwi and Hamza (2015) stated that it is the nature of the relationship between the knower (researcher) and what is known. By adopting a realist position new knowledge can be created deductively and a researcher can learn about reality by carefully observing the reality. Whilst, with nominalist the new knowledge, is produced inductively by observing, interpreting, and reflecting on (a) social actors' views and conducts in specific contexts and (b) the researcher's personal experiences and interpretations (Neuman, 2014).

3.2.3 Axiology

Axiology is another philosophical thinking which is concerned with the function of values and ethics within the research process (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). As described by Ponterotto (2005) that axiology is a philosophical view that is concerned with the role of the researcher's values in the scientific process. Lee and Lings (2008) stated that axiology is at the heart of the research aim, as it addresses the questions related to what is valued.

The role of the researcher's values is fundamentally important for the credibility of the research results, as a researcher demonstrates his/her values at all the phases of the research process. The researcher's values reflect his/her selection of the topic, research philosophy and data collection methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill,

2016). However, positivists consider values a separate entity as compare to interpretivists where values cannot be separated from the research process (Lee and Lings, 2008). According to post-positivists, values are important but believe that they can control the level of the impact of values on research results. While pragmatists hold a strong belief that values are crucial for conducting research and drawing conclusion. Therefore, they see no reason to be specifically concerned about the influence of values and study what they think is important (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998).

In general, this branch of philosophy explains the key aim of a researcher, i.e. whether the researcher tries to explain or predict the world, or whether he/she trying to understand the world. Thus, axiology is what a researcher value in his/her research and it is important as values direct the human actions that may impact the research.

3.3 Research Paradigms

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) discussed five major research paradigms in business and management research, which are: “positivism, critical realism, interpretivism, postmodernism, and pragmatism” (p. 135). However, this study will only discuss the three mostly adopted paradigms, i.e. positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism.

3.3.1 Positivism

The supporters of positivism (positivists) proclaim that there is an existence of an objective, a “mind-independent reality”, that can be examined by a value-free and unbiased researcher (Tsang, 2017, p. 4). The philosophical stance of positivism is related to natural science and being value-free is one of the components of positivism (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2016). Remenyi et al. (1998, p. 32) quoted that “working with observable social reality and that the end product of such research can be law-like generalisations similar to those produced by the physical and natural scientists”. Positivism explains and predicts the phenomena of the social world with an emphasis on regularities and causal relationships between variables (Kuada, 2012). The key reality underpinning positivism is that the different researchers would produce similar results of a real problem when they will examine a large sample using

an identical research process and statistical tests (Wahyuni, 2012). According to Collis and Hussey (2014) positivism has its roots in realism which is another research philosophy.

Della Porta and Keating (2008) stated that positivism assumes that the researchers have an independent existence in the research and thus, they remain unbiased and does not affect the research subject. It is believed in positivism that independent causes lead to observed effects and that the observed phenomena should be possible to generalise in the quantitative sense (Remenyi et al., 1998). According to Collis and Hussey (2014), the fundamental belief of positivism is that reality is independent, and the research aim is to ascertain theories empirically which can be verified scientifically.

According to Crotty (1998), the meaning of the term positivism has changed and grown over time and the attenuated form of positivism is now known as post-positivism. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), post-positivism represents the after-positivism philosophy and it challenges the positivist assumption that there is absolute truth knowledge, particularly, in the studies of human behaviour and action in social science (Wahyuni, 2012).

The key assumption of being independent of the subject of research in positivism is often criticised as it separates the researcher from what is being researched and thus, ignores the importance of human interaction in collecting data (Hennink, Hutter and Bailey, 2011).

3.3.2 Interpretivism

Interpretivism is another key research philosophy, an alternative approach (Bryman and Bell, 2015) and far extreme of positivism/post-positivism (Wahyuni, 2012), which emerges as a reaction of positivism (Hennink, Hutter and Bailey, 2011). As argued by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) that interpretivists are against the views of positivists as they claim that the social world is extremely complex to be studied as definite laws like physical science.

Interpretivism emphasises the need to understand the situation from people's point of views and the meanings people construct from their experiences (Kuada, 2012). An

interpretivist researcher needs to comprehend the differences between people as social actors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016), who construct the reality (Wahyuni, 2012). As posited by Crotty (1998) that interpretivists (constructionists) claim that truth is constructed by human beings as they engage with the world they are interpreting.

Interpretivists attempt to understand phenomena by collecting information by interviewing people or participant observation and interpreting the information to make meanings that people assign to them (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Thus, it relays on the subjective relationship between the researcher and the subject (Antwi and Hamza, 2015). As also argued by Wahyuni (2012) that interpretivists prefer to interact with participants of the study to know the social world through experiences and participants subjective meanings. The interpretivists researchers focus on exploring the complex social reality to gain interpretive understanding rather than measuring social reality as in positivism (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Therefore, the preference is given to qualitative data underpinning interpretivism as it provides a rich description of the social world.

According to Hennink, Hutter and Bailey (2011) the interpretivism paradigm acknowledge that the perceptions and experiences of people as social actors about the social reality are subjective, which may change and thus, the reality can have multiple perspectives, as oppose to positivism which proposed a single truth about reality. The key challenge for researchers in interpretivism is entering into the social world of people's and understanding how as research subject they view the world (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Nonetheless, both positivism and interpretivism paradigms seem fully opposite, however, the difference between the two is not as diverse as it seems. Because, there are some quantitative research approaches that include interpretive elements and some qualitative research approaches that have positivist influence (Hennink, Hutter and Bailey, 2011).

3.3.3 Pragmatism

Although positivism and interpretivism are two broad research philosophies, however, pragmatism cannot be ignored. If the choice of one or the other position is considered unrealistic then the researcher may adopt the position of the pragmatist (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), the researchers in pragmatism do not focus on methods, rather, they focus on research problems and questions and can use any approach to solve a problem. Therefore, if the choice of positivism and interpretivism is ambiguous from research questions, the researchers can work with both of the paradigms, as to answer a specific research question one paradigm might be 'better' than the other (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Pragmatism focuses on more than one method, hence, a mixture of philosophical thinking is acceptable to know the reality (Wahyuni, 2012), therefore, researchers under pragmatism are free to choose the research methods, techniques and approaches and may adopt quantitative and qualitative approaches simultaneously to better understand the social reality (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Wahyuni, 2012). As argued by Tsang (2017, p. 8) that "instead of engaging in the debate concerning methodological dualism of qualitative versus quantitative methods, pragmatism chooses a middle position mixed research method". Therefore, if the researcher is allowed to use both quantitative and qualitative it is unavoidable to embrace both subjective and objective point of views (Tashakkori and Teddlie (1998). Moreover, pragmatists support the use of abduction, a form of inference other than deduction and induction, to generate and justify hypotheses (Tsang, 2016).

In general, pragmatists researchers avoid the concepts of truth and reality and rather study what they think is important to study and what interests them and valuable for them (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998). Thus, pragmatism opens the doors to use mixed methods in which different philosophies, different assumptions and different methods of collecting and analysing data can be adopted (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

3.3.4 Philosophy of this study

The three broad ways of thinking 'ontology, epistemology and axiology' as described above are the key determinant behind the research philosophy of a study. Researchers' beliefs about the world reflect their ontological commitment which often affects their epistemological direction. Both ontology and epistemology positions then affect the methods the researchers implement for the research process (Tsang 2017). Therefore, the major ways of thinking are derived from the assumptions that a researcher make about how he/she views the world, which leads to the choice of the research design (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Moreover, the research problems and questions play an important role to modify the researcher's thinking and thus, also considered important for the selection of particular research philosophy and method (Thomas, 2004).

According to Tashakkori and Teddlie (1998) during the past three decades two major paradigms 'positivism and interpretivism' have been under debate on the superiority of one on the other in social and behavioural science. However, Tsang (2017) stated that positivism philosophy is most common in management research. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) claimed that more than one philosophical paradigm is used in business and management research.

Building on the understanding of the philosophical foundations and research aims and questions, this study adopted the positivism research paradigm. This paradigm directs the choice of a data collection method in this study. As this study is focused on to identify and investigate the effects of the key resources on SMEs' performance using scientific models, positivism research philosophy is found appropriate for this study as it tends to apply the methods and principles of the natural sciences.

Moreover, as the researcher's focus is to test the theories, the researcher used a deductive approach (see section 3.4 for justification) in which the hypotheses are first developed and then tested using a specific research strategy (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Consequently, this study used positivism research philosophy which relies on the testing of hypotheses by using a self-administrated survey-based quantitative data collection method as it satisfies the objective reality. Whereas,

interpretivism is considered to be inappropriate for this research as it is not inclined to enhance the understanding of the researcher to describe the world.

The basic demand of positivism is that the research is objective, i.e., reality and researcher are independent elements; therefore, the data is collected using objective methods rather than subjective interpretation. Furthermore, the study is value-free underpinning positivism, which based on the law like methodology to obtain unbiased findings, thus, it leads to the 'law-like value-free generalisation'.

3.4 Research Approach

The two research approaches are deductive and inductive and the choice of research approach depends on the researcher's understanding of the underlying theory at the initiation of the research which leads to the right research design (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

The deduction is a reasoning process that refers to going from general to specific (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015). According to Gray (2016), the deductive approach moves towards hypotheses testing. The researcher underpinning the deductive approach, deduce hypotheses based on what is already known about the field (Bryman, 2016), which Neuman (2014) refers to as 'abstract concepts', which logically connects the ideas in theory to concrete evidence. The concepts must be translated into researchable entities and the researcher needs to specify the data collection method on the concepts which are the building blocks of hypotheses (Bryman, 2016). These hypotheses and theories are then empirically tested through observation or experimentation (Gray, 2016).

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) deductive approach is mostly quantitative and the researcher stays independent of what is being observed. In other words, the researcher develops hypothesis/es and design a strategy to test the hypothesis/es by following a step by step process in this approach. As claimed by Bryman (2016), deductive approach is logically a stepwise and apparently a very linear approach.

Whilst, the inductive approach is a reasoning process in which the research moves from specific to general (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015). The researcher underpinning this approach builds the theory by starting from empirical observations and concrete evidence toward increasingly abstract ideas (Neuman, 2014). Although, the process of induction is moved in the opposite direction as compared to the deduction in which the theory is developed from the findings (Bryman, 2016). However, existing theories and ideas are not ignored in the inductive approach when approaching the problem. It is implicit that the selection of the research topic is dependent on the value and concepts, which may be helpful to formulate the overall research purpose (Gray, 2016).

The deductive approach is criticised by inductive researchers as it facilitates the creation of a cause-effect link between the variables without knowing how humans view their social world. While, in the inductive approach, the data is mostly collected through qualitative methods where human interactions are required, and participants' interpretation is considered. Therefore, a small research sample would be more appropriate as compared to the large sample in the deductive approach (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Although the notion that the deduction is often positivism and induction is interpretivism is contended by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016), however, in this research, the research adopted the deductive approach underpinning positivism.

3.5 Research Process

This research is categorised into four phases as shown in figure 3.1.

Phase 1: The Research started with the identification of the research problems, providing rationale and significance of the study, which directed the researcher to establish the key aim and objectives of the research. Then, the study conducted a critical literature review of key areas of research such as firm performance, EO, LO, MO and financial resources underpinning the theoretical foundation i.e. Resource-Based View (RBV). The literature review helped to clarify research objectives and leads to the development of a conceptual framework and hypotheses

Phase 2: This phase is based on the research methodology. This phase discussed and justified the philosophical foundation of this research, which directed the research to the selection of the right research design such as research strategies, data collection method, and time horizon. Furthermore, this phase included the measurement and operationalisation of variables.

Phase 3: Phase three involved the development of a questionnaire instrument, pre-testing and pilot test. The initial instrument is first pre-tested to further refine the questionnaire, and the pilot test is then conducted for further improvement considering respondents' feedback and to test the validity and reliability of the instrument. Moreover, the sampling frame is identified and selected using the 'Fame', an online database of companies, and a suitable method of gaining access to respondents is selected in this stage. The data collection process is also started in this phase.

Phase 4: This phase encompassed of data analysis process through statistical methods. Structural equation modelling (SEM) was chosen as the main multivariate research technique for data analysis. The research process ended with the interpretation of the results from the analyses and writing up the findings.

Figure 3.1 - Research Process

3.6 Research Design

Research design is the logical plan for getting from the initial research question to be answered, to the conclusion (Yin, 2009). A specific methodology is adopted to answer research questions, which is influenced by the research philosophy. As discussed above that the research philosophy does not just highlight the research paradigm but also contains key assumptions that guide how the research should be conducted. Thus, once the research paradigm is identified, the researcher can design the research by choosing the strategy and data collection methods that reflect the philosophical assumptions of the paradigm (Collis and Hussey, 2014). This stage of selecting the appropriate research design is the most crucial part of the research as this convert the research questions into a research project (Robson and McCartan, 2016)

Furthermore, it is necessary to have a clear purpose of research before collecting the data and the purpose of this study is descriptive and explanatory. The study is descriptive as it is conducted to ascertain the characteristics of a group in a given situation (Sekaran, 2016) and it is explanatory as it is focused on the phenomena which investigate the relationship between two or more variables (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016, p. 134)

3.6.1 Research Strategies

There are several research strategies available to choose from, depending on the research purpose. Some of the key research strategies as noted by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) includes survey, experiment, case study, ethnography, action research, grounded theory and archival research and can be used for explanatory, descriptive and exploratory research (Yin, 2009).

Considering the aim, objectives and research questions as well as the researcher's philosophical assumptions and research approach; this study adopted the survey strategy, which is a widely used non-experimental research method that relay on questionnaires (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015). The survey strategy is often linked with the deductive approach (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2016) and it is

most common in business research (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). A self-administered survey instrument was used to collect data in which a list of carefully structured and previously tested questions was selected to elicit reliable responses from a chosen sample (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

The key concern of adopting a survey strategy is to generalise the finding to a wider population (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This is a cost-effective strategy to generate findings that are representative of the whole population. Although, the availability of data analysis software would not be timesaving, however, once the data collection process through survey strategy is completed the research is independent (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

3.6.2 Data Collection Method

There are two broad data collection methods; the quantitative data collection method, which is adopted in this study, and the qualitative data collections method. As posits by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) that in business and management research these two methods are widely used to differentiate the data collection methods as well as data analysis procedure. Although, quantitative data collection method can be discriminated from qualitative in several ways, however, one way to distinguish between the two is that the quantitative study use numeric data and qualitative study use non-numeric data (Christensen, Johnson, and Turner, 2015).

Although, quantitative research is also differentiated because of the use of the measurement, which according to Bryman and Bell (2015) is not used in qualitative research, however, Neuman (2014) stated that researchers measures in both types of studies but the measurement is more important in quantitative research because it occurs before data collection as a key step in the research process. Special terminology and set of techniques are used in quantitative measurement to precisely collect data and present findings in numbers. On the other hand, in qualitative studies, measurement does not occur in the form of numbers and is part of the research data collection process.

Moreover, the ontological orientation of the quantitative method is objectivism which keeps the researcher independent of the research subject. This allows the researcher

to investigate the subject of the research without influencing or getting influenced by the research. Therefore, quantitative research is less biased and increase the validity of the research. As compared to qualitative research, which is ontologically subjective and adopts an interpretive position, which involves the researcher's participation and thus the research is subject to researchers' bias. As argued by Guba and Lincoln (1994) researchers' influence threat the validity of the research and it is extensively believed that "only quantitative data are ultimately valid, or of high quality" (p. 106).

3.6.3 Time Horizon

Based on time horizon, research is divided into two forms: (a) cross-sectional research and (b) longitudinal research. In cross-sectional research, the data is gathered once in a specific period to answer the research question. In longitudinal research, the researcher may want to study people or phenomena at more than one point in time to answer a research question (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Cross-sectional studies may be conducted to show the relationship of factors in different organisations, while the key to longitudinal studies is to see if there has been any change with the change in time (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). One notable point is that the results of two of these approaches are not always the same because cross-sectional studies investigate several diverse groups of individuals or different age cohorts, however, only one group of individuals or age cohorts are studied over time in longitudinal studies (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015). Moreover, cross-sectional study is economical, timesaving and requires fewer efforts as compared to a longitudinal study (Robson and McCartan 2016).

Consequently, this study is inclined to collect that data in one shot. Additionally, as the research is adopting a survey strategy to collect data, the cross-sectional approach is the most common practice of data collection in survey research (Robson and McCartan 2016). As argued by Bryman and Bell (2015) survey research is cross-sectional and data is mostly collected underlying cross-sectional design by questionnaires or structured interviews on numbers of cases.

3.7 Measurement of Variables

Once a construct is developed, it is important to clearly define it before actual measurement and assessment. According to Neuman (2014), there are two major processes in measurement: (a) conceptualisation which “refers to taking an abstract construct and refining it by giving it a conceptual or theoretical definition” (p. 205) and (b) operationalisation which is “the process of moving from a construct’s conceptual definition to specific activities or measures that allow a researcher to observe it empirically” (p. 207). Sreejesh, Mohapatra, and Anusree (2014) asserted that this definition of conceptualisation helps the researchers to appropriately frame and address the research question because once the constructs are conceptually defined, their operational definition can be developed easily. The operational definition is essential to measure abstract concepts, mostly that are subjective (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016)

To test the hypotheses, the development of correct measurement scales to measure the constructs is a fundamental element of the research. “A scale is a set of numbers or symbols developed in a manner to facilitate the assigning of these numbers or symbols to the units under research, following certain rules” (Sreejesh, Mohapatra and Anusree, 2014, p. 110). Sekaran and Bougie (2016) noted four key types of scales such as nominal, ordinal, interval, and ratio scale.

The most simple and non-quantitative scale of measurement is the nominal scale which uses numbers or letters to identify different objects and separates the data into categories that are “mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive” (Sreejesh, Mohapatra and Anusree, 2014). For instance, the variable of gender are categorised into, male and female, and assigned code numbers, say 1 for male and 2 for female (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In the ordinal scale, the variables are categorised in the form of rank-order. Although this scale help to determine the rank, however, it only tells the position and does not tell the exact level of highness or lowness of an object in comparison to another (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015).

The interval scale is more dynamic as compared to nominal and ordinal scales as it also measures the degree of the variances in the preferences. Furthermore, the interval scale allows the researcher to perform a certain arithmetical operation such

as means and the standard deviations of the responses on the variable (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The difference between the points on the scale is of the equal interval with no absolute zero points (Sreejesh, Mohapatra and Anusree, 2014). Finally, the ratio scale is the highest scale of measurement which not only has the characteristics of the other three lower-level scales but also has an absolute zero point (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015).

This study utilised nominal and interval scales. The nominal scale is used where the information about the firm profile such as industry, firm size and age and respondent's profile such as gender, age, experience and education level is collected. The interval scale is used to collect data on the key variable of interest. A Likert Scale is chosen as a suitable measurement scale for this study. It is formally an ordinal scale but generally treated as a type of interval scale as it allows researchers to calculate averages and standard deviations and more advanced statistical techniques (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

Likert scale is described by Christensen, Johnson and Turner (2015, p. 252) as “the most frequently used multi-item approach to scaling,... in which participant rates multiple items designed to measure one construct, using a 4, 5, 6, or 7-point rating”. Although, there is a range of different possible responses a respondent can choose from on a Likert scale, however, a 5-point scale is the most common (Bryman, 2016). Nonetheless, the 7-point scale often considered appropriate than a 5-point scale to obtain more reliability responses (Joshi et al., 2015) and to reduce attenuation problems caused by range restriction (Oh and Rhee, 2008). Moreover, there are more varieties of options on a 7-point scale and thus, the likelihood of meeting the objective is high. Consequently, the 7-point Likert scale items were used in this study as given below:

Table 3.1 - 7-Point Likert Scale

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neither	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

Most of the scales of measurement utilised in this study were already developed, utilised and verified in previous studies. The measurement scales of firm performance

and EO were adopted from Lonial and Carter (2015), LO was adopted from Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997), MO was adopted from Baker and Sinkula (2005). Measurement scales of financial capital, one of the indicators of financial resources were adopted from Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) and financial literacy was developed by the researcher through an in-depth literature review as no existing measures were found to measure the financial literacy of firms. The key reason for utilising existing scales was to increase the validity and reliability of the data collected (Hair et al. 2014). As argued by Cake et al. (2020) utilisation of existing measures ensure content validity. The development of a new scale is practically a lengthy and complex process and may require separate research. As argued by Morgado et al. (2017, p. 1) that several authors have a consensus that the process of scale development includes “complex and systematic procedures that require theoretical and methodological rigor”.

Furthermore, adopting established scales is a common practice and this methodology is in line with the majority of previous studies (see, Baker and Sinkula, 2009; 2005; Cake et al., 2020; Calabrò et al., 2020; Galbreath et al., 2020; Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández, 2018; 2020; Kumar et al., 2020; Lonial and Carter, 2015; McGee and Peterson, 2019; Morgan and Anokhin, 2020; Wang, 2008; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; Wolff, Pett and Ring, 2015). Each of the measurement scales is discussed in detail in the following sections.

3.7.1 Dependent variables

A variable that changes due to change in other variables is called the dependent variable (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). This is a variable of primary interest of research that is investigated as a viable factor to find research answer or solve a problem (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The dependent variable of this study is firm performance. As the nature of the firm performance is multidimensional and it is valuable to integrate different dimensions of firm performance in empirical studies (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005). Firm performance as a construct lack consensus on its measurement in empirical literature as both financial and non-financial measures (Rauch et al., 2009), and subjective and objective types of measures have been used to measure firm performance (Vij & Bedi, 2016). However, numerous authors noted

that subjective measures of firm performance are most common (see Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; 2012, and Santos and Brito, 2012) and justified to be used (Vij and Bedi, 2016). While data on objective measures of performance are either available seldom (Gupta, et al., 2020) or not available publicly and owners/managers of SMEs are reluctant to disclose actual figures (Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, 2015).

Therefore, to sufficiently capture the consequence of independent variables i.e. EO, MO, LO and moderator variable i.e. financial resources on firm performance, five subjective performance measures were adopted in this study. Furthermore, a combination of both financial performance measures (two items) as well as non-financial performance measures (three items) were used. The five performance measures were “**return on investment, sales growth, market share, customer satisfaction, and new product/process innovation**”. These measures were adopted from Lonial and Carter (2015) and the average Cronbach alpha for these measures as found by Lonial and Carter (2015) was 0.70. While, this study using these measures found the Cronbach alpha of 0.85, which is well above the minimum acceptable limit (see table 4.15). As the measurement has relied on subjective assessment, the participants were requested to rate the performance of their firms as compared to the past three years performance of their own firms, rather than comparing performance with their competitor. The respondents were asked to compare their firms’ performance with their own past three years performance because it was found difficult for small businesses to compare their performance with their competitors in the pilot test. The seven-point Likert scale items were adopted as discussed above since it is more flexible for participants (Vij and Bedi, 2016). To measure the performance of the firms following questions were asked:

Table 3.2 - Firm Performance Measures

Financial Performance:	
Q1:	The return on investment of your firm has increased as compared to the past three years.
Q2:	The sales of your firm have increased as compared to the past three years.
Non-Financial Performance:	
Q3:	The market share of your firm has significantly increased as compared to the past three years.
Q4:	The level of customer satisfaction in your company has increased as compared to the past three years.
Q5:	The new product/process innovation rate is higher in your firm as compared to the past three years.

Source:- Lonial and Carter (2015)

3.7.2 Independent Variables

A variable that affects other variables is called the Independent variable (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). The dependent variable exists with the existence of an independent variable and a little change in the independent variable affect the dependent variable either positively or negatively (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). There are three independent variables in this study Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO), Learning Orientation (LO) and Market Orientation (MO).

3.7.2.1 Entrepreneurial Orientations (EO)

EO is taken as a three-dimensional construct that encompasses a firm's innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness, as proposed by Miller (1983) and adopted by several researchers e.g. Covin and Slevin, 1991; Zahra and Covin, 1995; Wiklund, 1999; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003; Wiklund and Shepherd, 2003 and Lonial and Carter, 2015; Anderson et al., 2020). Altogether, six items from the original eight-item scale developed by Covin and Slevin (1989) to measure EO construct, in which two items measured innovativeness, two items measured risk-taking and two items measured proactiveness. Several researchers used this scale such as; Wiklund and Shepherd (2005), Baker and Sinkula (2009) and Lonial and Carter (2015). However, as mentioned earlier a 7-point Likert scale items were used in this study instead of 5-point as utilised by Lonial and Carter (2015). Two items were dropped to keep the questionnaire concise and short. Only the less relevant items were dropped after analysing pilot test results. Thus, the research adopted six 7-point Likert type scale items to measure the three dimensions of EO of Scottish SMEs. Moreover, the wording of the questions was modified as required to enhance the understanding of the respondents. Following questions were asked to measure EO.

Table 3.3 - Entrepreneurial Orientation Measures

Innovativeness:	
Q1:	We are usually first-to-market with new products and services.
Q2:	We (Top management) in the company encourage the development of innovative marketing strategies, knowing well that some will fail.
Risk-Taking:	
Q3:	Our company likes to "Play it safe."
Q4:	We value the orderly and risk-reducing management process much more than leadership initiatives for change.
Proactiveness:	
Q5:	We firmly believe that a change in the market creates positive opportunities for us.
Q6:	Members of our company tend to talk more about opportunities rather than problems

Source:- Lonial and Carter (2015)

3.7.2.2 Learning Orientations (LO)

LO is that specific set of firm's values that impact the firm's propensity to generate and utilise knowledge. Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997) conceptualised LO into three components including the commitment to learning, open-mindedness and shared vision and developed a measurement scale to measure LO. Baker and Sinkula (1999) has retested this scale and found further support for its validity and reliability. Several other researchers such as Baker and Sinkula (1999); Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002); Wang (2008); Wolff, Pett, and Ring (2015); Lonial and Carter (2015); Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018; 2020) and Kumar et al. (2020) also utilised this scale.

This study also adopted this scale to measure LO, however, only 9 items, out of a total of 18 items as in the original, were used. The key reason to use the 9 items is to avoid the questionnaire being lengthy and save respondents time to fill out the survey. Only less relevant questions are dropped after discussing with experts in business research in pre-testing. Furthermore, to ensure that by using a smaller number of items still capture LO, a pilot test was conducted, and the reliability of the items were examined using Cronbach coefficient alpha measures. It was found that Cronbach coefficient alpha for LO at the pilot stage was 0.93 which is well above the minimum acceptable limit (Hair et al., 2014) and thus, highlights that 9 items are reliable to examine LO. Furthermore, scale items for LO were adopted from established measurement scales which further ensures the validity and reliability of the items (measures/questions). The following questions were asked to measure LO:

Table 3.4 - Learning Orientation Measures

Commitment to learning:	
Q1:	Managers agree that our company's ability to learn is the key to our competitive advantage.
Q2:	The sense around here is that employee learning is an investment, not an expense.
Q3:	The collective wisdom in this enterprise is that once we quit learning, we endanger our future.
Shared vision:	
Q4:	There is a well-expressed concept of who we are and where we are going as a company.
Q5:	All employees are committed to the goals of our company.
Q6:	Top leadership believes in sharing its vision for the entire company.
Open-mindedness:	
Q7:	Managers in our company do not want their "view of the world" to be questioned.
Q8:	Managers encourage employees to "think outside of the box."
Q9:	Original ideas are highly valued in this organization

Source:- Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier (1997)

3.7.2.3 Market Orientations (MO)

There are two widely used MO scales one is known as MKTOR, developed by Narver and Slater (1990) and the other is known as MARKOR, developed by Kohli, Jaworski and Kumar (1993). The MKTOR is focused on customer value, while, the focus of MARKOR is on generating, disseminating intelligence and being responsive based on the conceptualisation of Kohil and Jaworski (1990). In this study, as MO is based on the conceptualisation of Kohli and Jaworski (1990), MARKOR scale items were adopted. Although, the MARKOR scale originally contains 32 items which then reduced to 20 items to provide satisfactory representation for all three components of MO (Kohli, Jaworski, and Kumar, 1993). Several authors utilised this scale such as Cake et al. (2020); Abbu and Gopalakrishna (2019); Lonial and Carter (2015); Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009) and Baker and Sinkula (2005;1999)

However, this study only adopted six items of the MARKOR scale to measure MO and not to utilise the entire scale due to practical concerns, especially the complexity and length of the questionnaire (Baker and Sinkula, 2005). These six items were adopted from Baker and Sinkula (2005) in which two items measuring intelligence generation,

two items measuring intelligence dissemination and two items measuring responsiveness. Baker and Sinkula (2005) found that the correlation of these six items with the full scale is 0.84. This in turn justifies the use of these six items to measure MO.

To further ensure the utilisation of fewer items to measure MO, a pilot test was conducted. It was found that Cronbach coefficient alpha for MO at the pilot stage was 0.88 which is well above the minimum acceptable limit (Hair et al., 2014). Additionally, the scale items for MO were adopted from established measurement scales which were utilised by several authors and thus, ensures the validity and reliability of the items. This in turn, further justify the use of six items (questions) to capture MO. Following were the six questions that were asked to measure MO.

Table 3.5 - Market Orientation Measures

Intelligence acquisition:	
Q1:	We are slow to detect changes in our customers' product preferences.
Q2:	We frequently review the likely effect of changes in our business environment on customers.
Intelligence dissemination:	
Q3:	When something important happens to a major customer or market, the whole business unit is informed about it within a short period.
Q4:	When one department finds out something important about competitors, it is slow to alert other departments.
Responsiveness:	
Q5:	For one reason or another, we tend to react slowly to changes in our customers' product or service needs.
Q6:	Several departments get together periodically to plan a response to changes taking place in our business environment.

Source:- Baker and Sinkula (2005)

3.7.3 Moderator Variable

A variable that impact the nature of the independent variable and the dependent variable is called the moderator variable (Rose, Spinks and Canhoto, 2015). It strongly affects and changes the original relationship between the exogenous and endogenous variables (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). For instance, this study assumed two types of

relationships: (a) positive direct relationships between each of the independent variables (i.e. EO, LO, and MO) and dependent variable (i.e. firm performance), and (b) moderating variable (financial resources) strengthen the relationship between each of the independent variables and the dependent variable.

3.7.3.1 Financial Resources

The financial resources construct is divided into two indicators (a) financial capital and (b) financial literacy. The study used five items measuring financial resources in which two items measured financial capital and three items measured financial literacy.

As mentioned earlier that the availability of financial capital depends on the access to funds, therefore, to measure financial capital original measure was used as used by Wiklund and Shepherd (2005). This measure is subjective where the level of satisfaction of SMEs' CEOs/owner/manager's access to financial capital was assessed. In this study, this measure is divided into two items. One is related to access to long term funds, such as debts capital and equity capital, and the other is related to working capital.

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, no existing measures were found that directly capture the financial literacy of the firms. Therefore, the researcher developed three measurement items for the financial literacy dimension of financial resources construct from an in-depth literature review. The literature stated several different terms that refer to financial literacy such as financial knowledge, financial awareness, financial information, financial education, financial decision making and financial management. The questions (items) were positioned to address the ability of firms to make a financial decision by focusing on the firm's financial literacy in respect of their financial needs, financial awareness of their investment perspective and rate of return (consequences). The item were pre-tested, and pilot tested along with the measures of other constructs. The reliability test of the data gathered for this study highlight that Cronbach alpha (i.e. 0.87) for financial resource construct is well above the minimum acceptable limit (Hair et al., 2014; see table 4.15)

Following are the five questions that will be used to measure financial resources:

Table 3.6 - Financial Resources Measures

Financial capital	
Q1:	Our firm is satisfied with access to long term funds for the development of the firm.
Q2:	Our firm is satisfied with access to cash (working capital) for day to day financial needs.
Financial Literacy	
Q3:	Our firm is usually well-informed about its overall financial needs.
Q4:	Our firm is well aware of its investment prospects.
Q5:	Our firm knows the rate of return associated with each investment.

Source:- Wiklund and Shepherd (2005)

3.8 Questionnaire instrument

A questionnaire is a predetermined list of questions administered to respondents for their feedback and also known as an instrument (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Questionnaires are usually designed for the collection of large amounts of quantitative data (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). To design the questionnaire to collect data of this study the researcher first, enhanced his understanding of the data requirement and define the research construct theoretically through an in-depth literature review. The deductive approach is adopted to develop the questions and identify numbers of questions (items) for each construct. The initial instrument was then pretested with experts to establish the content and construct validity followed by a pilot test to ensure reliability and to further develop the questions.

3.8.1 Pre-test and Pilot-test

Before starting the actual data collection process researchers need to test the questionnaire. It is to identify construct defects, the ambiguity of proposed measure and to ensure reliability and validity. The questionnaire was tested in two ways. First, the questionnaire was pre-tested with the specialists including research supervisors and fellow researchers. Their feedback helped to revise the questionnaires. Second, a pilot test was commenced with five businesses. A pilot test is mostly suggested to tackle the concerns related to the wording and language used in the scale items, to evaluate the potential rate of responses and examine the feasibility of the research (Johanson and Brooks, 2010). Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) argue that the

pilot test is one of the ways to maximize the response rate, validity, and reliability of the study. As also stated by Neuman (2014) that it is one of the key methods to improve reliability.

The pre-test and pilot-test were conducted to fulfil the following key purposes.

a) To test if the language of the survey questionnaire is understandable.

Since the key target respondents are CEOs/owners/managers of SMEs who may have different levels of literacy, thus, the participants of the pilot test are asked to point out any word, term or question that is unclear and ambiguous.

b) To assess the time to complete the survey.

The surveys have a bad reputation in terms of response rate and one of the key reasons is that the CEOs/owners/managers have limited time to fill them out. The initial survey contained 53 items including items to measure personal and business profile and required 15 to 20 minutes to complete which was found to be lengthy. Therefore, the questionnaire was reduced to 39 questions (items) in total, which include 8 items to measure personal and business profile.

c) To test the layout of the survey to see if it is clear and appealing for respondents.

d) To examine the ease of respondents to answer the questions.

The pilot test highlighted that the small business owners found it difficult being small in size and being less informed about their competitors. Thus, the questions were changed to compare their firms' performance with their own firms' past three years of performance.

e) To analysis the validity and reliability of the study.

3.9 Population

The population consists of a full list of elements (Cooper and Schindler, 2014) and encompass the “entire group of people, events, or things of interest” that are to investigate (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016, p. 238). This specific group share a particular set of characteristics (Collis and Hussey, 2014). According to Saunders, Lewis, and

Thornhill (2016), a population is a full set of cases, more than just people, from which a sample is taken. According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016), a sample is drawn from the population frame which is the entire list of elements in the population.

If a researcher wants to investigate the relationships between organisational orientations and SMEs performance, and the moderating effect of financial resources on these relationships, within Scotland, then the population, from which a specific group of SMEs taken as a sample, will be all the SMEs located in Scotland. Therefore, the population of this study includes all types and sectors of SMEs in Scotland.

There are two key reasons to choose this population. First, this population has a key role in the economy of Scotland, as it accounts for 99.3 per cent (343,535) of the whole private sector enterprise and contributed an estimated 1.2 million jobs (The Scottish Government, 2018). Second, this population has not been studied in the past decade, specifically, concerning the effect of organisational orientations on SMEs performance and the moderating effect of financial resources. Although, there are government reports on SMEs access to finance, however, no such academic research has been found in the literature. Thus, the investigation of the effect of organisations orientations on Scottish SMEs and the role of financial resources as a moderator will certainly provide some guidelines to policymakers and Scottish SMEs to improve performance.

3.10 Sample

A sample is a subset of the population and comprises some of the elements of the population (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The basic idea of sampling is to conclude the entire population (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). The sample of this study was drawn from Scottish SMEs and thus, the firms that registered outside Scotland and those that do not meet the criteria of being SME according to the definition of the European Commission (2015) were excluded, i.e. the firms with more than 249 employees. The head of the firms (CEO/owner/manager) was targeted as a subject for data collection as they were the most informed individuals in the firm. "A subject is a single member of the sample, just as an element is a single member of the population" (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016, p. 237).

3.10.1 Sample size

The sample size or final sample size is the number of surveys for which data has been collected (Lavrakas, 2008). For example, If an online survey is returned with 500 completed questionnaires, then the sample size is 500.

It is important to determine the required numbers of the sample before the process of collecting data. Albeit, the literature recommends a sample size from 30 to 500, however, Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) stated that the larger sample size reduce the amount of error in generalising to the population. Although the minimum adequate sample size to conduct statistical analysis is 30 (Stutely, 2003), however, Hair et al. (2014) argued that the adequate minimum sample size is 100 responses to estimate the correlations between variables. According to Kline (2016), there is no definite rule about the sample size, however, the average sample size might be 200 cases. Christensen, Johnson and Turner (2015) stated that the size of the sample should be higher if the population is higher and recommended that if the population is 100 or less, then the sample size should include the whole population and if the the population is over 99,999 the minimum sample size should be 384, based on the confidence level of 95%. (Christensen, Johnson and Turner, 2015; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Nonetheless, numerous researchers recommended different numbers of samples, however, they are also agreed that there is not a single sample size that would be exactly representative of the population (see Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016; Sekaran and Bougi, 2016; Bryman and Bell, 2015; Sreejesh, Mohapatra and Anusree, 2014 and Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Bryman and Bell (2015) argued that a key factor involves in the decision of sample size is to what extent one is willing to tolerate sample error, the more it is the larger should be the sample size. Therefore, the minimum potential sample size of this research that the researcher aimed to achieve was 384 responses.

3.10.2 Sampling

There are two broad categories of sampling techniques (a) Probability sample and (b) Non-probability sample (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016; Sekaran and Bougi,

2016; Bryman and Bell, 2015 and Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Both of the sampling techniques are further divided into several types as shown in figure (3.2) below. In probability sampling, the chances of the selection of each element as a sample subject are known (Sekaran and Bougi, 2016). In other words, under this sampling technique, the sample is selected using random selection which gives each element a known chance of being selected (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

While, non-probability sampling is the one in which the chances of elements to be selected as sample subjects are not known (Sekaran and Bougi, 2016). As in this sampling, a sample is not selected by the random selection method, therefore, some elements more likely to be selected as compared to others (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This sampling is good for quick surveys or when the researcher is unable to get access to the whole population (Walliman, 2011). As argued by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) that limited resources or the type of research where there is no population frame, for example, case study research and market surveys, may direct to use non-probability sampling method. Bryman and Bell (2015) stated that this sampling technique is used when the researcher is less concerned about the generalisability

This research utilised probability sampling and there were two key reasons, first, this was quantitative research underpinning the survey method to collect data and second, the researcher was concerned about generalisability. Furthermore, the study adopted a stratified random sampling approach, in which the population was divided into subsets based on supplementary information and then a random sample is drawn from sub-population (Neuman, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). In this study, the population was divided into three categories, micro, small and medium firms depending on the numbers of employees. After drawing sample frame, the simple random sampling approach was then adopted to draw a final sample. This sampling technique was selected as it has minimum levels of bias and offers the most generalisability (Sekaran and Bougi, 2016).

Figure 3.2 - Sampling Techniques

Source:- Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016)

3.10.3 Calculation of actual sample size

The actual sample size is the minimum sample to which the researcher should send a questionnaire for data collection. As mentioned above that the minimum targeted responses (sample size) in this study was 384, based on a 95% confidence level. Therefore, to calculate the actual sample size following formula as given by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) was used:

$$n^a = n \times \frac{100}{re\%}$$

Where:

- n^a = actual (required) sample size
- n = minimum sample size (384 in this study).
- $re\%$ = estimated response rate

According to Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016), an average response rate of 35% is rational for most academic research. Nutly (2008) noted that the overall response rate for paper-based surveys is 56% and online surveys are 33%. As the researcher

in this study willing to conduct an online survey, thus the estimated response rate will be 33%. Thus:

$$n^a = 385 \times \frac{100}{33} = 1164$$

Therefore, the researcher targeted more than 1164 SMEs, which were selected by using a stratified random sampling approach.

3.11 Gaining Access and collection of Data

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016). Highlighted three methods to gain access to potential firms to collect data such as:

- a) **Traditional access:** In this method, the access is made by face-to-face interactions.
- b) **Internet-mediated access:** In this method, the access is made by the use of the computer (e.g. Emails)
- c) **Hybrid access:** In this method, the access is made by using both traditional access and Internet-mediated access.

In this research, the potential firms were accessed using the hybrid access approach to collect data, in which the preference was given to the internet-mediated access approach.

3.11.1 Internet-mediated access approach

This is a quantitative research in which a survey strategy using questionnaires is implemented to collect data, and this is the most widely used data collection technique (Neuman, 2014). This strategy allows administration of the questionnaire to a larger population easily and inexpensively. It has high anonymity and allows respondents to take more time to respond at their convenience (Sekaran and Bougi, 2016). Hence, this strategy increases the generalisability of data and enable respondents to give an honest and accurate answer.

Therefore, the researcher initially used internet-mediated access techniques via email to access firms to collect data. This process was further divided into two steps.

a) Step 1 - Identifications of Firms.

Although there are several online databases of companies available such as “Financial Analysis Made Easy” (FAME), Dun and Bradstreet and Amadeus. However, the potential respondent firms were identified and their contact details (email addresses) were gathered using the FAME database in this study. This database was found to be the most appropriate database to the gather contact details of the companies. FAME is a definitive source of private company information and contains information of 13 million companies registered in the UK and Ireland (FAME, 2019). Hopkins and Richmond (2016) stated that the FAME database has the advantage of allowing the identification of individual companies and the nature of their activities and drawn primarily from Companies House. It can be used to research specific companies, companies with particular profiles, and to undertake analysis (Dada and Fogg, 2016). Therefore, this database allowed the researcher to identify firms that matched the selection criteria of this study including size by numbers of employees and location with contact details of these firms. Previous empirical research shows that several authors used FAME to identify firms to collect data (see, Dada and Fogg, 2016; Eshima and Anderson, 2017; Kumar et al., 2020 and Wang, 2008)

As the research is focused on micro, small and medium-sized enterprises based in Scotland, therefore, companies’ information is collected based on two criteria (a) country of operations (Scotland) and (b) numbers of employees (less than 250). FAME identified 841 micro firms, 1,191 small firms, and 2,189 medium-sized firms based on these two criteria (see table 3.7).

Table 3.7 - Identification of Micro, Small and Medium-sized Firms

Firm Type	Search Criteria	Step result	Search result
	All active companies (not in receivership nor dormant) and	178,327	0
Micro	Country: Prim. trading address, R/O address: Scotland	11,252	11,252
	Number of Employees: Last available year, min=1, max=9	25,172	860
	Total Assets (th EUR): Last available year, min=1, max=2,000,000	227,254	841
	TOTAL		841
Small	Country: Prim. trading address, R/O address: Scotland	11,252	11,252
	Number of Employees: Last available year, min=10, max=49	28,962	1,196
	Total Assets (th EUR): Last available year, min=1,	229,381	1,191
	TOTAL		1,191
Medium	Country: Prim. trading address, R/O address: Scotland	11,252	11,252
	Number of Employees: Last available year, min=50, max=249	40,715	2,199
	Total Assets (th EUR): Last available year, min=1,	229,845	2,189
	TOTAL		2,189

Source:- Output of FAME Companies Database

However, as the plan was to send the surveys through emails, not all the firm identified had their email addresses listed on FAME. Therefore, the identified firms were further reviewed manually to extract the firms that have email addresses. Consequently, there were only 266 micro firms, 793 small firms, and 1531 medium-sized firms in Scotland that have email addresses listed on the FAME database. Thus, the sample frame of this study was (1531+793+266) 2,590 SMEs, based in Scotland.

b) Step 2- Collection of Data

Online survey administration software called 'Google Forms' was used to develop an online survey questionnaire. The online link to the survey was emailed to potential respondent firms targeting key informants including CEOs, Owners and Managers inviting them to fill out the survey. The email self-administrated survey approach is in line with Morgan and Anokhin (2020); Kumar et al. (2020) and Basco, Hernández-Perlines and Rodríguez-García (2020). The content of each email includes a brief description of the survey objectives and includes the researcher's contact details. By clicking the link, the respondents will see an information sheet. The information sheet contained brief and clear information on the essential elements of the study such as the aim of the research, the nature of respondents' participation, the potential benefits and risks, research confidentiality and contact details of the researcher and research supervisor.

The information sheet closed with a consent form which was made compulsory for respondents to complete by agreeing that they have read the information sheet, they are over 18 years of age and their participation is voluntary.

Altogether 1,700 firms were randomly selected with approximately equal margin from all three categories of SMEs. Out of 1,700 emails sent, 494 emails were bounced and thus the researcher got no access to those firms. This reduced the actual sample size of the internet-mediated access approach to 1,206 (1700 minus 494). The bounced emails could not be delivered because of the following reasons: (a) the email address was not identified at the destination domain, (b) the recipient's mailbox is unavailable, (c) the email address might be misspelt or d) the email address might not exist. The actual cause of this cannot be identified as the email addresses were obtained from the FAME directly and the researcher stayed independent. Out of a total of 1,206 successful email surveys, only 78 responses received after three reminders, yielding a response rate of 6.47%.

3.11.2 Traditional Access Approach

The extremely low response rate from the internet-mediated access approach urged the researcher to collect data in a traditional way in which the firms were accessed physically. The researcher identified 500 firms based in Glasgow (mainly), Edinburgh and Aberdeen using yellow pages and google search. A total of 180 firms were randomly selected and visited personally to get the surveys done. A total of 120 surveys were completed on the spot, with the owners/managers of the firms, using the hard copy and an electronic device. The use of an electronic device to collect data personally is in line with Acosta, Crespo and Agudo (2018). The researcher did not intervene in this method of data collection and stayed independent. The remaining 60 firms were given an online link and hard copy of the survey depending on their choice, to complete the surveys at their convenience, however, only 33 responses were received.

Furthermore, the researcher requested an accountancy firm (former employer) to request its clients to fill out surveys. This accountancy firm is located in Glasgow, however, have clients from different cities of Scotland such as Glasgow, Edinburgh, Dumfries, Livingston and Sterling. The director of the accountancy firm requested 120

clients (business owners/managers), however, a total of 91 responses were received. Again, these surveys were filled either electronically or on printed copy. As a result, in the traditional approach, a total of 244 (120+33+91) responses were received out of 300 requests (180+120), which accounts for 81.33%.

3.12 Response Overview

A total of 2,000 firms (1700 plus 300) were targeted to get access for data collection, however, only 1,506 firms were accessed successfully. Out of a total of 1,506 (actual sample size), there were 322 responses received representing a response rate of 21.38% (see table 3.8). The response rate from the traditional approach (81.33%) was satisfactory, but the response rate from the internet-mediated access approach (6.47%) was extremely low. This low response rate was consistent with the general experience of online surveys (Sekaran and Bougi, 2016) and in line with Basco, Hernández-Perlines and Rodríguez-García (2020). They collected data from three different samples using email surveys and their average response rate was 6.98%. The overall response rate in this study is 21.38% which is consistent with several contemporary studies conducted in the relevant field of researcher's interest such as the response rate of Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018; 2020) was 13.67%; Morgan and Anokhin (2020) 15.78%; Gupta et al. (2020) 16.5%; Calabrò et al. (2020) 18.4%; McGee and Peterson (2019) 20%; Asemokha et al. (2019) 14%; Ro et al, (2019) 18.5% and Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015) 19.71%.

Table 3.8 - Responses Overview

Actual Sample Size (N)		
Internet-mediated Access Approach	1206	80.08%
Traditional Access Approach	300	19.92%
Total	1506	100%

Responses Received:		
Internet-mediated Access Approach	78	24.22%
Traditional Access Approach	244	75.78%
Total	322	100%

Overall Response Rate:		
Internet-mediated Access Approach	78	5.18%
Traditional Access Approach	244	16.20%
Total	322	21.38%

3.13 Ethical Consideration of the Thesis

Research ethics are crucial in formulating the research design and the researcher is required to obtain approval from the Research Ethics Committee (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). To collect data ethical approval was obtained from the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) Research Ethics Committee. This ensured that the standard conditions of the ethics committee were met to design the questionnaire instrument.

3.14 Reliability and Validity

Reliability and validity are significantly important in a research project and thus, are considered as the central concerns in the measurement (Neuman, 2014). Reliability categorised into two forms (a) Stability which includes test-retest reliability and parallel-form reliability and (b) consistency which includes inter-item consistency reliability and split-half reliability. Validity encompasses content validity, criterion-related validity and constructs validity (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

3.14.1 Reliability

Reliability is the replication and consistency of a study i.e. repeating an earlier study with the same results means this study is reliable (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill,

2016). There are four common methods of measuring the reliability underpinning two broad categories (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). Which are:

1. Stability

a. Test-retest reliability:

In test-retest reliability, the consistency between responses of an individual is measured at two different points (Hair et al., 2014). If the result is the same then the measures have stability reliability (Neuman, 2014). However, it is difficult as respondents may not be interested to answer the same questionnaire twice (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016)

b. Parallel-form reliability

When the same construct is measured with two comparable sets of measures and is highly correlated then it is parallel-form reliability (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). The problem with this method is that it is often difficult to ensure that these questions are considerably equivalent (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016)

2. Consistency

a. Inter-item consistency reliability

This method tests the consistency of responses across the items of the measures (Kline, 2016). In other words, this statistical test examines whether the scale items measuring the same thing. If the items are highly intercorrelated then they are measuring the same thing (DeVellis, 2017). Sekaran and Bougi (2016) stated that Cronbach's coefficient alpha tests the strength of positive correlation of items to one another and it is the most popular test of internal consistency reliability. Scholars have different views about the value of Cronbach's coefficient alpha. According to Hair et al. (2014), the most accepted minimum limit for Cronbach's coefficient alpha is .70, however, in the exploratory research the value of .60 would be acceptable. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) argue that the value of .70 or above shows that the questions in a scale measure the same thing. However, Sekaran and Bougie (2016) argue that it will only be considered poor if the value is less than .60.

b. Split-half reliability

In this method, the instrument is divided into halves and the two are correlated to estimate the reliability (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016)). This method is a convenient alternative to other forms of common reliability methods and a commonly used method before the invention of Cronbach's coefficient alpha (Frey, 2018). However, it may show different results because there are different ways to divide the items in an instrument (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

This study used Cronbach's coefficient alpha underpinning the inter-item consistency reliability method. Table 3.9 highlights the Cronbach's coefficient alpha of each scale in the pilot test. All the scales are found within an acceptable range (>0.60) and hence, the scales have a good level of reliability.

Table 3.9 - Reliability statistics (Pilot Stage)

Measures	Cronbach's Alpha	Numbers of Items
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.89	6
Market Orientation	0.88	6
Learning Orientation	0.93	9
Financial Resources	0.61	5
Firm Performance	0.94	5

Source:- SPSS Output of Reliability Test

3.14.2 Validity

The validity of the measuring instrument answer a key question that how certain a researcher is, that he/she is measuring the concept as intended. It is the test of the questionnaire that a researcher intended to administrate to see if it can measure the right concept. As quoted by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016, p. 450) that "measurement validity refers to concerns that what you find with your questionnaire represents the reality of what you are measuring". Sekaran and Bougie (2016) divided validity into three categories; content validity, criterion-related validity, and construct validity.

1. Content Validity

Content validity confirms that the questions in the questionnaire are adequate to answer the key research question. It is also called face validity (Hair et al., 2014) which indicates that the measuring questions explicitly express their intended measurement of the concept (Sekaran and Bougie (2016). Content validity can be achieved in two ways, (a) through the careful definition of the underlying construct by reviewing literature and (b) by the judgment of panel of individuals (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

To achieve content validity, in this study most of the measures were adopted from previously available well-validated measurement instruments in the literature (Coke et al., 2020) Furthermore, the final questionnaire was made after pre-test, and pilot test.

2. Criterion-related validity

In this approach, validity is verified by comparing two indicators of the same construct in which a researcher has confidence (Neuman, 2014). Criterion-related validity has two forms **(a) Concurrent Validity** and **(b) Predictive Validity** (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). When an indicator is allied with a pre-existing indicator (previously proven valid) and it produces similar results than that indicator has concurrent validity (Neuman, 2014). **Predictive validity** is referred to as the ability of the questions to make accurate predictions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). In another word, it refers to the likelihood of an indicator to predicts future events that are logically related to a construct (Neuman, 2014). Numbers of measures taken to ensure the criterion-related validity, such as:

- The questions that are suitable and applicable to the potential respondents are used.
- Negatively worded items were employed.
- The use of a short and concise questionnaire.
- The questionnaire used closed-ended questions.
- Seven-point Likert scales items were used rather than five points.

3. Construct Validity

When a set of questions are measuring the construct that those questions are proposed to measure then they have construct validity. When different sets of questions (items) are used to measure the same construct, their correlation refers to **convergent validity** and when different items are used to measure theoretically different constructs, their uncorrelation refers to **discriminant validity** (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Correlational analysis, factor analysis, and the multitrait-multimethod matrix are some of the methods to test the construct validity (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In this study, the factor analysis approach is adopted to examine the construct validity in the following chapter.

3.15 Statistical Procedure

The four stage Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique was utilised to analyse the data including: data screening, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the analysis of structural path model through SEM. The software “IBM SPSS Statistics 25 and IBM SPSS Amos 25” were used for the process of the data analysis.

SEM is not titled as a single statistical technique, but it is a family of statistical techniques and also known as “covariance structure analysis, covariance structure modeling, or analysis of covariance structures” (Kline, 2016, p. 9). Hair et al. (2014) posited that SEM is a multivariate statistical analysis technique and represent a linear association between variables. According to Byrne (2016), it is a confirmatory approach (i.e. hypothesis-testing) to analysis the structural theory

Weston and Gore (2006) described SEM as a hybrid technique which is the combination of factor analysis and path analysis. As a factor analysis, it provides a parsimonious summary of the interrelationships among variables and as path analysis, it tests hypothesised relationships among constructs. In other words, it refers to whether a hypothesised theoretical model is consistent with the data collected to reflect the theory (Lei and Wu, 2007). In general, SEM is a set of complex statistical models of linear relationships among latent (unobserved) variables and measured (observed) variables (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016).

SEM is chosen over other multivariate analysis techniques for several reasons, such as multiple regression analysis. First, this study is examining multiple relationships of independent variables, moderator variable, and dependent variable. Therefore, SEM is considered the most suitable method for analysing these kinds of complex multiple relationships. Although the multivariate regression analysis can also analyse similar types of relationships, however, by looking at a single relationship at a time. Whereas, SEM can analysis multiple relationships among sets of variables concurrently (Hair et al., 2014).

Second, the data collected in this research is cross-sectional data and SEM can be applied to both longitudinal and cross-sectional data (Lei and Wu, 2007). Third, It has been growing as confirmatory methods of analysis that allow researchers to assess and modify theoretical models in a comprehensive way (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988). As argued by Byrne (2016) SEM is a confirmatory data analysis approach while most other multivariate techniques adopt an exploratory approach and are essentially descriptive by nature making hypothesis testing difficult.

Forth, SEM can analyse both observed as well as unobserved (latent) variables, however, other methods are limited to the analysis of observed variables only (Byrne, 2016). Lei and Wu (2007) posited that SEM is an extended form of general linear modeling and has the advantage of analysing the relationships among latent (unobserved) constructs with several indicators where each has many measures (Lei and Wu, 2007). Finally, SEM also considers measurement error in account. The traditional multivariate models are unable to either assess or correct measurement error (Byrne, 2016). Kline (2016) argued that statistical techniques like multiple regression assume that all predictors are measured without error, while, SEM provides an explicit representation of measurement error. Ignoring error by adopting traditional multivariate techniques may produce inaccurate results and hence, SEM is adopted.

Although, SEM has many advantages over other multivariate analysis techniques, however, the complexity of SEM comes with some potential problems. First, the most fundamental assumption in multivariate analysis is normality (Hair et al., 2014) as most statistics used in SEM assume that the multivariate distribution is normally distributed (Weston and Gore, 2006). Nonetheless, there are several methods to test if the data is normally distributed or not, such as tests of skewness and kurtosis (Kline, 2016),

and there are some estimation method in SEM that can be used in the case of non-normal data.

Second, SEM depends on a large sample size as certain types of estimates in SEM, such as standard errors for effects of latent variables, may be inaccurate when the sample size is not large (Kline, 2016). A sample size of 200 cases would be sufficient (Weston and Gore, 2006), however, this will not be large enough when analysing a complex model with non-normal distribution (Kline, 2016). The issue of normality and sample size of this study are discussed and justified in the following chapter.

3.16 Chapter Summary

The key aim of this chapter was to identify and justify the research methodology for this study. This chapter presented the three key categories of philosophical foundations of research; ontology, epistemology, and axiology, which directed the research to choose the right research paradigm. The chapter discussed three research paradigms, positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism. Positivism was chosen for this specific research which relies on theories to test hypotheses underpinning the deductive approach.

Underpinning positivism this study inclined to adopt the survey strategy and quantitative data collection method in a cross-sectional time horizon. This study utilised nominal and interval scales. 7-point Likert scale items were used to collect data on the key variables of the research. The questionnaire contained 39 questions altogether, was administered to SMEs in Scotland using an internet-mediated access approach and traditional access approach. The questionnaire was pre-tested, and pilot tested before data collection. FAME database of companies was used to identify the potential sample of SMEs. Out of 1,506 firms contacted, 322 responses were received, resulting in a response rate of 21.38%.

Furthermore, the chapter highlighted the reliability and validate of this study. The reliability of the scale was tested using Cronbach's Alphas test at the pilot stage and found to be reliable. Similarly, the measures taken to ensure the validity of the study were also discussed in this chapter. Lastly, the chapter considered the various techniques and tools of analysis. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was chosen to

analyse the data in this study. The software 'IBM SPSS Statistics 25 and AMOS 25 was selected to undertake data analysis.

4 Chapter Four – Data Analysis and Findings

4.1 Introduction

Chapter 3 outlined and justified the research methodology of the study, while this chapter covered different stages of data analysis and findings. The chapter started with the process of data screening which discussed the existence and handling of missing data, outliers and the normality of the data. The chapter then highlighted the final response rate and outlined the non-response bias of the study. Next, the chapter presented the descriptive analysis underpinning the demographic profile of the participants and firms' profile. Chapter four then outlined the exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in which four questionnaire items were found redundant and deleted to achieve the right numbers of, valid and reliable, common latent factors, followed by the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) which approves the structure of the factors obtained by conducting EFA, by achieving an overall model fit, and construct validity and reliability. The chapter then presented the structural path model alongside the findings and their significance and then test hypotheses. The chapter ends with a chapter summary.

4.2 Data Screening

Data screening is the process of getting the data ready for analysis. Once the data is collected, there are few steps required before entering the data into computer software for analysis. These steps include; data coding, initial data screening, handling missing data, outliers, normality and multicollinearity.

4.2.1 Data Coding

Data coding is assigning numbers to the participants' responses (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016), which make the entry of the data fast and with minimum errors (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). In this study, the researcher used numbers and conceptual labels to empirical objects for coding. Appendix 2 presents the coding sheet.

4.2.2 Initial Data Screening

Once the data was coded, it was then entered into the IBM SPSS Statistics Version 25. The data coded and entered were edited and refined to identify any errors or mistakes in the data during data entering. The reverse-coded questions in surveys were also recoded at this stage. For initial data screening, some simple tests were conducted which provided a statistical overview of the data along with Cronbach's coefficient alpha test to the internal consistency of the scale items (See table 4.1). In support of uni-dimensionality, the coefficient alphas for all the variables (constructs) i.e. entrepreneurial orientation ($\alpha = 0.935$) market orientation ($\alpha = 0.810$) learning Orientation ($\alpha = 0.867$), financial resources ($\alpha = 0.866$) and firm performance ($\alpha = 0.697$) were found well within the acceptable range.

Table 4.1 - Descriptive and Reliability Statistics

Construct	Items	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
Personal Profile	Gender	322	2	1	3	1.31	0.548	
	Age	322	5	1	6	3.94	1.054	
	Education	322	6	1	7	3.66	1.074	
	Position	319	4	1	5	1.78	0.875	
Business Profile	Employees	322	2	1	3	1.48	0.67	
	Turnover	322	3	1	4	1.37	0.672	
	Firm-age	321	4	1	5	2.8	1.404	
	Industry	319	7	1	8	2.58	1.898	
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	321	6	1	7	4.040	0.738	0.935
	EO2	321	6	1	7	4.022	0.743	
	EO3	321	6	1	7	4.006	0.742	
	EO4	321	6	1	7	4.034	0.734	
	EO5	321	5	1	6	4.087	0.745	
	EO6	321	5	1	6	4.075	0.755	
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1	321	6	1	7	3.807	0.825	0.810
	LO2	321	6	1	7	3.931	0.759	
	LO3	321	6	1	7	3.903	0.766	
	LO4	321	6	1	7	3.801	0.820	
	LO5	321	6	1	7	3.785	0.783	
	LO6	321	6	1	7	4.153	0.745	
	LO7	321	5	2	7	3.956	0.832	
	LO8	321	6	1	7	3.841	0.768	
	LO9	321	6	1	7	2.950	1.005	
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1	321	6	1	7	4.212	0.719	0.867
	MO2	321	6	1	7	4.000	0.859	
	MO3	321	6	1	7	2.950	0.960	
	MO4	320	6	1	7	3.474	0.968	
	MO5	321	6	1	7	3.595	0.996	
	MO6	321	6	1	7	3.558	1.017	
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1	321	6	1	7	3.162	0.928	0.866
	FR2	321	5	2	7	3.277	1.049	
	FR3	321	4	3	7	3.305	0.972	
	FR4	321	5	2	7	3.324	0.959	
	FR5	321	6	1	7	3.882	0.732	
Firm Performance (P)	P1	321	6	1	7	4.050	0.669	0.697
	P2	321	6	1	7	3.903	0.762	
	P3	321	6	1	7	3.984	0.760	
	P4	321	6	1	7	2.259	0.925	
	P5	320	6	1	7	3.488	1.601	
Valid N (listwise)		317						

Source: SPSS Output of Descriptive Statistics and Cronbach's Alpha

4.2.3 Missing Data

There are two sources of missing data; (a) researcher and (b) respondents, and it occurred while collecting the data or entry data or when a respondent does not answer a specific question (Hair et al., 2014). Kline (2016) categorised missing data into (a) missing completely at random (MCAR), (b) missing at random (MAR) and (c) not missing at random (NMAR). While, Weston and Gore (2006, p. 737) stated that “unfortunately, there is no procedure for determining whether data are missing randomly”.

The missing data can either be deleted or a technique that can be applied to remedy the missing date. This depends on the numbers of concerns. First, whether the missing data is ignorable or not ignorable. Ignorable data occurs as part of the research design

and cannot be remodified. Not ignorable data occurred due to known or unknown processes. The known process includes procedural factors such as an error in data entering, coding or directly related to respondent, in which a respondent may have some limitations to answer or may fail to answer for some reasons such as morbidity or limited knowledge. The unknown process is directly related to the respondent, in which the respondent may refuse to answer a question due to its sensitivity or they may not have enough knowledge (Hair et al., 2014). Second, it is the extent of missing data. Kline (2016) suggests that when there is a large sample of less than 5% of missing data on a particular variable is not too problematic. According to Hair et al. (2014) when missing data are under 10 per cent it can be remedied by applying any of the imputation methods. However, Byrne (2015) stated that missing data can lead to inefficient analyses and seriously bias conclusions, therefore, deleting cases with missing data would be an appropriate approach.

In this study, the initial analysis of data highlighted that there were 5 cases with missing data. It is found that the type of missing data is determined as 'not ignorable' and thus, it is assumed that data is MCAR. As missing data may lead to inefficient analyses and seriously bias conclusions (Byrne, 2015), the researcher adopted a complete case approach (also known as listwise deletion) in which the researcher excluded all those cases that had missing data (Kline, 2016). This reduces the total usable response to 317.

4.2.4 Outlier

Outliers are the values of a data set that are unique as compared to the rest of the data, which may have a substantial effect on the results of a study. As defined by Kline (2016, p. 72) "outliers are scores that are very different from the rest". The value in observation is either too high or too low on a single variable or a pattern of values within numerous variables that mark an observation unique (Hair et al., 2014). In general, outliers are illogical responses (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) and may distort the interpretation of the data or make a statistic misleading (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). As stated by Osborne and Overbay (2004) that outliers can negatively affect the process of statistical analyses by (a) increasing error variance and reducing

the power of statistical analyses, (b) decreasing the normality of the data if they were distributed non-randomly, and (c) biasing or affecting estimates of key interest.

Outliers can be detected from a univariate, bivariate, or multivariate perspective (Hair et al., 2014). Nonetheless, handling outliers can also be an issue as there are different views on how to handle them. Aguinis, Gottfredson, and Joo (2013) argued that different ways of defining, identifying and handling outliers change the research conclusion. Leys et al. (2019) provided three strategies for handling outliers:

- I. **Keeping the outliers:** if rightfully belong to the distribution of interest
- II. **Removing the outliers:** it may corrupt the estimation of the distribution parameters
- III. **Recoding the outliers:** this is to avoid the loss of a large amount of data.

Hair et al. (2014) stated that if there is no evidence that the outliers of any observation are truly abnormal, and they do not represent that observation then they must be retained. While, Kline (2016, p. 74) suggested to delete a case if that case with outlier value/s is determined not to be from the same population, however, “extreme-but-valid scores” can be retained.

This study used univariate outliers approach which visually marks (mild) outliers as a circle ‘O’ and extreme outliers as asterisks ‘*’. The study decided to delete the cases with extreme outliers and keep the remaining case(s) if they meet two conditions as suggested by Kline (2016); (a) they are valid scores i.e. not truly abnormal and unengaged and (b) they are from the same population (i.e. a respond from Scottish SMEs). These strategies are chosen to avoid the loss of a large amount of data (Leys et al., 2019).

Firstly, the univariate outliers for continuous variables such as age, position, education level, firm age, industry, and turnover were examined. The analysis shows that there are numerous cases with (mild) outliers, however, none is found with extreme outliers. These cases with mild outliers were further examined visually to see if they meet the above-mentioned conditions of being retained. Only one case (Case no. 59) is found that was truly abnormal and out of the range of the population of interest. This case shows that the responded is under 18 years of age and he has a

master's degree. This is not just abnormal but also implies that the respondent is not paying attention as in the consent form the respondent agreed that he is over 18 years of age. Therefore, this case was deleted.

Secondly, the univariate outliers of Likert scale items were examined, in which none of the cases was found as extreme, however, there were several mild outlier cases. All the mild outlier cases were reviewed, and it was found that three responses (case no. 8, 140 and 167) were unengaged and hence, deleted. As a result, there were 313 complete cases left.

4.2.5 Normality

The multivariate normality of the data is a key assumption in SEM analyses (Byrne 2015) which is the benchmark for the statistical method (Hair et al., 2014). The nonnormality may influence the results of the statistical tests by wrongly suggesting a good fit or a poor fit model to the data (Weston and Gore, 2016).

The normality of data can be tested as univariate or multivariate normality. The normal result of the multivariate normality test suggests that the assumption for all univariate normality tests are met, however, as there is no direct multivariate normality test, the researchers mostly test univariate normality for each variable (Hair et al., 2014). Weston and Gore (2006) also stated that It is impractical to test the multivariate normality because it assesses unlimited linear combinations, therefore, it is recommended to examine univariate normality. Nonetheless, univariate normality does not guarantee multivariate normality, however, if all the variables are found normality, then multivariate nonnormality would not be considered important (Hair et al., 2014).

Skewness and kurtosis are two ways to determine the presence of univariate normality (Weston and Gore, 2006). The data set is skewed if it is distributed asymmetrically around its mean, it is positively skewed if values are mostly below the mean and negatively skewed if the values are mostly above the mean. On the other hand, the data set is kurtotic if the distribution is heavier or lighter on tails when presented by the histogram graph. If the histogram graph shows heavier tails and a higher peak it

is the distribution of positive kurtosis and if it shows lighter tail and lower peak it is the distribution of negative kurtosis (Kline, 2016).

Hair et al. (2014) posited that skewness and kurtosis can be detected visually in the form of graphs or plots, however, statistical tests of normality are present more accurate results of skewness and kurtosis. For the statistical test of normality 'z-value' of skewness and kurtosis is calculated by dividing the statistical value by standard error. The cut-off values for the normality test are z-value of ± 1.96 , corresponding to a .05 error level or ± 2.58 , corresponding to a .01 error level (Hair et al., 2014). Whilst, Kline (2016) argued that an absolute z-value of greater than 3 (i.e. above +3 and below -3) is extreme for skewness index and an absolute z-value of greater than 8 is extreme for kurtosis index. Byrne (2016) argued that the proof of kurtosis is of key interest as kurtosis critically impact the tests of variances and covariances and covariances structure is the base of SEM.

Furthermore, normality can be tested using the Shapiro-Wilks test and Kolmogorov-Smirnov test available in all statistical programs (Hair et al., 2014). According to these tests, a variable is not distributed normally if "Sig." or "P-value" is less than 0.05 (<0.05) (SPSS Tutorials, 2019).

This study used Likert scale items to measure the key variables and hence the variables generated discrete data (not continuous). therefore, a Likert scale cannot generate normally distributed data. However, Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) argued that practically Likert type scale with seven or more categories can be treated as continuous, hence as this study used a 7-point Likert type scale items, the data collected in this study can be considered as continuous.

In this study, the distribution of data is inspected by calculating the z-value of kurtosis. Using the Kline (2016) criteria of kurtosis index only three kurtotic variables were found beyond the critical value of ± 8 . As Byrne (2016) posited that evidence of kurtosis is always of concern, therefore, it can be concluded that the data is moderately normally distributed. As Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) is conducted before analysis of the measurement model and structural path model, It is found justified to proceed with this data. In EFA sample adequacy is one of the key requirement to determine the factorability of the data (Effendi et al., 2019). To test the sample adequacy this study

adopted a Maximum Likelihood (ML) approach underpinning the common factor analysis. The maximum likelihood (ML) approach generates the best results even if the data is non-normally distributed and it is also useful for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to analyse the measurement (Yong and peace, 2013).

Table 4.2 - Tests of Normality

Construct	Items	N	Skewness			Kurtosis		
			Statistic	Std. Error	Z-Value	Statistic	Std. Error	Z-Value
Personal Profile	Gender	313	1.583	0.138	11.488	1.562	0.275	5.687
	Age	313	0.064	0.138	0.463	-0.507	0.275	-1.845
	Education	313	0.426	0.138	3.091	0.242	0.275	0.880
	Position	313	0.615	0.138	4.460	-0.958	0.275	-3.486
Business Profile	Employees	313	1.122	0.138	8.145	0.020	0.275	0.074
	Turnover	313	2.011	0.138	14.597	3.761	0.275	13.690
	Firm-age	313	0.269	0.138	1.955	-1.164	0.275	-4.237
	Industry	313	0.999	0.138	7.248	0.072	0.275	0.263
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	313	-0.712	0.138	-5.169	0.919	0.275	3.345
	EO2	313	-0.701	0.138	-5.085	1.429	0.275	5.202
	EO3	313	-0.630	0.138	-4.575	0.993	0.275	3.615
	EO4	313	-0.622	0.138	-4.511	1.123	0.275	4.087
	EO5	313	-0.586	0.138	-4.250	0.822	0.275	2.992
	EO6	313	-0.904	0.138	-6.557	1.848	0.275	6.727
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1	313	-0.676	0.138	-4.904	1.193	0.275	4.342
	LO2	313	-0.955	0.138	-6.929	1.141	0.275	4.154
	LO3	313	0.058	0.138	0.418	-0.552	0.275	-2.009
	LO4	313	-0.153	0.138	-1.109	-0.506	0.275	-1.843
	LO5	313	-0.497	0.138	-3.609	-0.239	0.275	-0.869
	LO6	313	-0.504	0.138	-3.660	-0.389	0.275	-1.415
	LO7	313	-0.843	0.138	-6.115	1.307	0.275	4.758
	LO8	313	-0.993	0.138	-7.206	2.530	0.275	9.208
	LO9	313	-0.668	0.138	-4.850	1.270	0.275	4.623
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1	313	-0.647	0.138	-4.696	0.767	0.275	2.793
	MO2	313	-0.744	0.138	-5.397	1.175	0.275	4.277
	MO3	313	-0.344	0.138	-2.500	-0.194	0.275	-0.706
	MO4	313	-0.741	0.138	-5.377	0.761	0.275	2.772
	MO5	313	-0.544	0.138	-3.950	0.920	0.275	3.349
	MO6	313	0.085	0.138	0.619	-0.694	0.275	-2.525
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1	313	-0.287	0.138	-2.082	-0.771	0.275	-2.808
	FR2	313	-0.303	0.138	-2.202	-0.675	0.275	-2.456
	FR3	313	-0.197	0.138	-1.427	-0.687	0.275	-2.500
	FR4	313	-0.192	0.138	-1.396	-0.775	0.275	-2.822
	FR5	313	-0.938	0.138	-6.805	1.848	0.275	6.727
Firm Performance (P)	P1	313	-0.653	0.138	-4.738	2.185	0.275	7.953
	P2	313	-0.746	0.138	-5.417	1.707	0.275	6.213
	P3	313	-0.922	0.138	-6.693	2.870	0.275	10.445
	P4	313	0.796	0.138	5.777	0.423	0.275	1.541
	P5	313	0.213	0.138	1.546	-0.572	0.275	-2.082
Valid N (listwise)		313						

Source: SPSS Output of Skewness and Kurtosis

4.3 Collinearity

Collinearity exists when two independent variables are highly correlated in a data, and when one independent variable is extremely correlated with a set of other independent variables, there exists multicollinearity (Hair et al., 2014). The existence of extreme

collinearity highlights that separate variables are measuring the same thing (Kline, 2016). As stated by Byrne (2015, p. 191) that in the situation of multicollinearity “two or more variables are so highly correlated that they both, essentially, represent the same underlying construct”. Commonly used methods of detecting multivariate collinearity with the extreme collinearity value below which a variable is considered problematic, as described by Kline (2016) are shown in table 4.3.

Table 4.3 - Cut Off Values of Extreme Collinearity

Methods	Extreme Collinearity Value
Coefficient of Determination' (R^2)	> 0.90
Tolerance or $1 - R^2$	< 0.10
Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) or $1/(1 - R^2)$	> 10.0

Source:- Kline (2016)

In this study, the computer program SPSS was used to detect the collinearity of the independent variables. This analysis took each independent variable as a dependent variable one by one and regressed against other independent variables (Hair et al., 2014). The result of this test shows the Tolerance values and VIF values. The highest VIF value found is 6.781 for EO4 when EO1 is taken as a dependent variable (see table 4.4). Therefore, the study meets the collinearity assumption as none of the variable is found beyond the extreme collinearity value.

Table 4.4 - Collinearity Statistics

Construct	Constant	Univariate		Multivariate	
		Tolerance	VIF	Tolerance	VIF
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1*			0.529	1.889
	EO2	0.233	4.29		
	EO3	0.174	5.737		
	EO4	0.149	6.718		
	EO5	0.283	3.53		
	EO6	0.331	3.017		
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1	0.415	2.41	0.542	1.846
	LO2	0.272	3.679		
	LO3	0.23	4.343		
	LO4	0.364	2.744		
	LO5	0.325	3.073		
	LO6	0.401	2.493		
	LO7	0.452	2.212		
	LO8	0.432	2.314		
	LO9	0.447	2.235		
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1	0.378	2.645	0.918	1.089
	MO2	0.374	2.671		
	MO3	0.658	1.52		
	MO4	0.234	4.271		
	MO5	0.242	4.129		
	MO6	0.364	2.749		
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1	0.38	2.635	0.907	1.103
	FR2	0.314	3.185		
	FR3	0.361	2.77		
	FR4	0.339	2.953		
	FR5	0.39	2.567		
*Dependent Variable: EO1					

Source: SPSS Output of Collinearity Statistics

4.4 Homoscedasticity and Linearity:

The existence of homoscedasticity was assessed by comparing residuals and standardized predicted scores presented on the scatterplot (see figure, 4.1). The residuals are found to be homoscedastic, as they are equally distributed about zero in the scatterplot (Kline, 2016, p. 81).

Figure 4.1 - Scatterplot

Source:- SPSS Output of Homoscedastic Test

Similarly, the test of linearity is also important, as nonlinearity represents the underestimation of the accuracy of the relationships (Hair et al, 2014). The linearity was assessed graphically by Normal P-P Plot (figure 4.2). It is to identify that there are no serious departures of data from linearity that may affect the correlation. Thus, the assumption of linearity is met.

Figure 4.2 - Normal Probability Plot

Source:- SPSS Output Linearity Test

4.5 Response Rate

A total of 1,506 CEOs/Owners/Managers of SMEs in Scotland were surveyed. Out of a total of 1,506 surveys, only 322 responses were received, yielding a response rate of 21.38%, however, only 313 responses were found usable and 9 responses were found non-usable. Out of 9 non-usable responses, 5 responses had missing data (see section 4.6.3) and thus deleted. The other 4 responses were eliminated from the data analysis as they contained outlier values. The exclusion of 9 (0.6%) non-usable responses reduces the overall response rate to 20.78% (see table 4.5).

Table 4.5 - Overall Response Rate

	Numbers	Perecentrge
Actual Sample size	1506	100%
Total responses	322	21.38%
<u>Nonusable Responses:</u>		
Missing data	5 0.33%	
Outliers	4 0.27%	
Total Non-usable Response	9	0.60%
Total usable Response	313	20.78%

4.6 Non-Response Bias

According to Nishimura, Wagner and Elliott (2015), nonresponse bias occurs when respondents and non-respondents are systematically different and to estimate the non-response bias, the scores (p-values) and mean difference of respondents and non-respondents are compared. In this study, the extrapolation method was applied to estimate the non-response bias. Armstrong and Overton (1977, p. 397) stated that the extrapolation method assumes that respondent who respond late or require “more prodding to answer” is more likely equivalent to non-respondents. The data in this study was initially collected through the internet-medium access approach and then by the traditional access approach. As most of the responses from the internet-medium access approach were received in the first attempt, therefore these responses were considered from respondents. Whilst, the traditional access approach required more prodding to get responses from the respondents, therefore, the responses received through this approach were considered from most likely non-respondents.

To test the statistically significant differences in responses, an independent sample t-test was conducted, which compares the means of all measured items (measures) between two independent groups (i.e. respondents and non-respondents) to determine the statistical differences between the means of these two groups (Calabrò et al., 2020). The result of the t-test analysis is highlighted in table 4.6 which shows that the p-values (sig. 2-tailed values) for all the measures are above the required cut-off value of 0.05, except one item of financial resources, ‘FR5’. Therefore, it can be concluded that significant means differences do not exist between the internet-medium access approach respondents (i.e. respondents) and traditional access

approach respondents (i.e. non-respondents), which in turn, prove the absence of non-response bias.

Table 4.6 - Independent t-test

Construct	Items	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1*	0.988	-0.002
	EO2	0.721	-0.035
	EO3	0.544	-0.063
	EO4	0.633	-0.049
	EO5	0.752	0.032
	EO6	0.985	0.002
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1	0.229	-0.134
	LO2	0.399	-0.086
	LO3	0.878	-0.015
	LO4	0.475	0.075
	LO5	0.775	-0.030
	LO6	0.242	0.112
	LO7	0.660	0.048
	LO8	0.891	-0.014
	LO9	0.052	0.274
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1	0.784	0.025
	MO2	0.228	0.132
	MO3	0.471	0.088
	MO4	0.237	0.150
	MO5	0.303	0.132
	MO6	0.648	0.058
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1	0.962	-0.005
	FR2	0.604	0.067
	FR3	0.330	0.113
	FR4	0.430	0.098
	FR5	0.019	0.200
Firm Performance (P)	P1	0.697	0.031
	P2	0.345	0.088
	P3	0.067	0.152
	P4	0.233	0.144
	P5	0.617	-0.102

Source: SPSS Output of Independent Samples T-Test

4.7 Descriptive Analysis

In the data preparation process, the data is cleansed through the deletion of missing data and outlier responses. Altogether, 9 responses found unusable and thus eliminated, leaving a sample size of 313 usable responses.

Nonetheless, descriptive statistics organise and summarise large amounts of data, which enables the researcher to understand and draw a conclusion from the results of quantitative analysis. This help to obtain research findings and inference about larger

population and generalisation of research findings. Therefore, this section presents the demographic profile of participants and firm profile.

4.7.1 Demographic Profile of Participants

The results of the descriptive statistics of the demographic profile of participants are shown in table 4.7. It shows that most of the respondents (73.16%) were male, whereas, female participants only account for 22.36%. The data also highlights that 14 (4.47%) participants did not prefer to disclose their gender. In terms of age, the respondents with the age between 35 to 44 years dominate the sample with 37.06%, followed by the age groups 25 to 34 years and 45 to 54 years, which account for 25.88% and 22.04% respectively. Both the young entrepreneurs between the age of 18 to 24 years and senior entrepreneurs over 54 years of age were the lowest than all and almost equivalent, representing 7.99% and 7.03% of SMEs respectively. Furthermore, the majority of entrepreneurs, 35.46% (111), have college-level education followed by undergraduates (89), master's degree holders (66) and high school (40). The results show that there were only 6 (1.92%) participants that have some kind of professional qualification and only 1 (0.32%) participant has primary school level education. Similarly, in terms of the position of the participants, it was found that most of the participants (154) were Owners/CEOs/Proprietors which accounts for 49.20%. while eighty-two (26.20%) responses received from directors and 72 (23%) from managers. It was also found that 5 (1.60%) participants have some kind of supervisory role.

Table 4.7 - Demographic Profile of Participants

Participants		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender:	Male	229	73.16	73.16
	Female	70	22.36	95.53
	Prefer not to say	14	4.47	100.00
Age:	18-24	25	7.99	7.99
	25-34	81	25.88	33.87
	35-54	116	37.06	70.93
	45-54	69	22.04	92.97
	54+	22	7.03	100.00
Education:	Primary School	1	0.32	0.32
	High School	40	12.78	13.10
	College	111	35.46	48.56
	Undergraduate degree	89	28.43	77.00
	Master's Degree	66	21.09	98.08
	Professional Qualification	6	1.92	100.00
Position:	Owner/CEO/Proprietor	154	49.20	49.20
	Director	82	26.20	75.40
	Manager	72	23.00	98.40
	Supervisor	5	1.60	100.00

4.7.2 Firm profile

The firm profile encompasses four themes such as numbers of employees, the annual turnover of the firms, the number of years the firms are in operations (firm age) and the type of industry the firms operate in. The first one is fundamental in this study as it helps to differentiate between the types of SMEs. In this study, a firm is considered as SME, if it meets the condition of numbers of employees (less than 250). As highlighted in table 4.8, the annual turnover of 6 participant firms was over €50 million which is above the maximum limit for a firm to be considered as SME according to the EU (2015) definition. However, this study adopted Ward's (2021) definition of SMEs in which an enterprise is considered as an SME if it has less than 250 employees. Therefore, as the numbers of employees of six firms with an annual turnover of above €50 million are less than 250, they were considered as SMEs in this study.

In terms of numbers of employees, the analysis shows that most of the SMEs were micro firms as 198 participant firms (63.26%) have under 10 employees. Whilst, 26.84% (84) participants were small firms that have 10 to 49 employees and 9.90% (31) firms were medium sized that employed 50 to 249 employees. The micro-sized firms also dominate the sample when measured by their annual turnover followed by small firms and medium-sized firms respectively. They accounts for 73.48% (Micro), 19.17% (small) and 5.43% (medium) respectively. It was also found that 6 firms (1.92%) have an annual turnover of over €50 million, however as they have less than 250 employees, therefore, they were considered in the categories of SMEs.

Furthermore, it was found that firms with 6 to 10 years in operations dominate the sample and account for 23.96% (75 firms). Firms under 3 years and 3 to 5 years of operations are slightly left behind and account for 23.32% and 22.68% respectively. Fifty-eight firms were found as experienced firms which are in operations for over 15 years and represent 18.53% of the sample. The firms that are in operations for 11 to 15 years are the lowest, 36 firms and represent only 11.8% of the sample.

In terms of industry, nearly half of the sampled firms (49.52%) were in the retail sector. None of the other sectors is found anywhere close to the retail sector. The second highest sector was the service sector which only accounts for 21.09% of the sample, followed by the hospitality sector which accounts for 16.93%. All other sectors of the sampled firms were less than 5% and collectively account for 12.47%

Table 4.8 - Demographic Profile of Firms

	Participants	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Employees:	Under 10	198	63.26	63.26
	10 to 49	84	26.84	90.10
	50 to 249	31	9.90	100.00
Turnover	Under €2 million	230	73.48	73.48
	€2 million to €10 million	60	19.17	92.65
	€10+ million to €50 million	17	5.43	98.08
	Over €50 million	6	1.92	100.00
Firm-age	Under 3 Years	73	23.32	23.32
	3 to 5 years	71	22.68	46.01
	6 to 10 years	75	23.96	69.97
	11 to 15 years	36	11.50	81.47
	Over 15 years	58	18.53	100.00
Industry	Retail	155	49.52	49.52
	Wholesale	15	4.79	54.31
	Service	66	21.09	75.40
	Distribution	4	1.28	76.68
	Hospitality	53	16.93	93.61
	Manufacturing	8	2.56	96.17
	Fashion	4	1.28	97.44
	E-commerce	8	2.56	100.00

4.8 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Hair et al. (2014) stated that a factor is a set of highly correlated variables and also referred to as the underlying constructs, and the key aim of conducting factor analysis is to examine the underlying structure of the correlations among the factors. This ensures that the items or variables belong to the same construct. Factor analysis is a data reduction technique from a larger to a smaller set of underlying factors (Coakes and Steed, 1999).

EFA is one of the two broad categories of factor analysis, which determines the level of relationships between the observed variables and their underlying factors (Kline, 2016). Hoyle (2012) posits that EFA drags the right number of common factors by analysing the measured variables to ascertain the reasonable indicators of the various latent dimensions, thus, it is conducted to discover and to identify the latent common factor variables (Mulaik, 1987). Furthermore, one of the key purposes to conduct EFA in this research is to ensure the validity and reliability of items before confirmatory factor analysis.

To conduct the EFA there is a condition of sample size that should be met. Hair et al. (2014) provide a general rule to have a sample size of a minimum of five times higher than the items (variables) that are to analyse. This study has 31 variables to analyse and the sample size is 313, which is well above the required level (31×5) i.e. 155. Once the study meets the sample size requirement, there is a need to test the sample adequacy. IBM SPSS provides several different input options to conduct sample adequacy tests and EFA. The detail and justification of the inputs are as follow:

1. **Descriptive:** The descriptive option provides several tests for sample adequacy. This study applied three key tests, “(a) *Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s test* (b) *anti-image matrix correlation* and (c) *reproduced correlations*”. If these steps meet the minimum cut off level then the factorability of the correlation matrix is assumed, and factor analysis can be proceeded (Chan and Idris, 2017).
2. **Factor Extraction:** As factor analysis creates communalities between variables using a variance, where the extraction method is applied to eliminate the common variance in the first factor to the maximum extent (Yong and

Pearce, 2013). SPSS provides the number of different extraction methods underpinning two broad categories (a) common factor analysis and (b) component analysis. Both factor analyses drive essentially identical results if the numbers of the variable are over 30 (Hair et al., 2014). This study adopted a Maximum Likelihood (ML) approach underpinning the common factor analysis. This choice is made as the key purpose is to detect the common factors underpinning latent constructs (Hair et al., 2014). Furthermore, ML generates the best results even if the data is non-normally distributed and it is also useful for confirmatory factor analysis (CFA; Yong and peace, 2013). Moreover, the eigenvalue cut-off depending on Kaiser's criterion of 1.0 is selected for the extraction of common factors.

3. **Factor Rotation:** In EFA the purpose of the rotation is to enhance the interpretability of retained factors (Kline, 2016). A variable may load on more than one factors in the process of EFA therefore, rotation is applied to minimise the loading of each variable on several factors (Rummel, 1970). There are many rotations methods, however, they all produce equivalent results (Kline, 2016). As quoted by Hair et al. (2014, p. 114) "no compelling analytical reason suggests favouring one rotational method over another". The varimax rotations method is adopted in this study. It is the most widely used method of rotation underpinning orthogonal rotation of factors (Kline, 2016). It works on the principle of simplifying the columns of the factor matrix and thus provide a clearer separation of the factors (Hair et al., 2014). Furthermore, the researcher selected to suppress the small coefficient which is below the absolute value of 0.4. This value is selected as it is the minimum significant loadings for the sample size of 200 (Hair et al., 2014), while this study has a useable sample size of 313, well above 200.

The details of SPSS output and cut off for different EFA tests are as follows:

KMO, Bartlett's Test and Anti-Image Matrix Correlation: These tests determine the sample adequacy by identifying if the factorability of the correlation matrix is assumed. If conditions are met the factor analysis can be proceeded (Chan and Idris, 2017).

Reproduced correlation: The reproduced correlation matrix present the summary of the percentage of the non-redundant residuals which determines whether it is a good fit or poor fit model (Yong and Pearce, 2013).

Extracted Communalities: The proportion of common variance present in a variable is known as communality (Field, 2017). In other words, it is the extent to which an item correlates with all other items. Extracted values are considered for this test.

Total Variance Explained: This defines the quantity of significant factors. To interpret the results of the test, only extracted and rotated values are considered (Yong and Pearce, 2013).

Rotated Factor Matrix: This highlights intercorrelations among the variables being tested in the EFA, with factor loading.

Table 4.9 - Cut-off for EFA Tests

Test	Cut-off	Source
KMO	0.5	Kaiser and Rice (1974)
	0.6	Tabachnick & Fidell (2007)
Bartlett's Test	sig<.05	Hair et al. (2014)
Anti-Image Matrix Correlation	>0.50	Hair et al. (2014)
Reproduced Correlations - Non-Redundant Residuals	<50%	Yong & Pearce (2013)
Total Variance Explained	>60%	Streiner (1994)
Average Extracted Communalities	0.6	Field (2017)
Rotated Factor Matrix	minimum ± 0.30 to ± 0.40	Hair et al. (2014)

4.8.1 Sampling Adequacy

Before conducting EFA, the sampling adequacy of the research data must be tested. **KMO, Bartlett's Test and Anti-Image Matrix Correlation** tests are applied to test the sample adequacy. The result shows that the appropriateness of factor analysis was supported by Bartlett's test of sphericity with the significant value (p-value) is less than <0.001 . The KMO is found well above the cut off value of $>.50$, which was 0.908 (see Table 4.10). Likewise, all items have a value of greater than 0.50 on the anti-correlation matrix ranging from .793a to .953a. Similarly, the non-redundant residuals of the reproduced correlation matrix were also found below 50%, which is 6% with an absolute value greater than 0.05. Therefore, the dataset is found suitable for proceeding to the EFA.

Table 4.10 - SPSS output for KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		0.908
Barlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6857.991
	df	456
	Sig.	0.000

4.8.2 EFA Before Modification

EFA was conducted with all 31 variables after successfully meeting the sample adequacy requirement. The total variance explained table (table 4.11) highlights that the study has a cumulative percentage above 50%. Similarly, it shows that there were 6 common factors based on the eigenvalues of 1, however, the study is expecting five factors as there are five key constructs in this study.

Table 4.11 - SPSS Output for Total Variance Explained*

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared			Rotation Sums of Squared		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	10.272	33.135	33.135	9.840	31.741	31.741	5.111	16.486	16.486
2	3.906	12.601	45.736	2.932	9.457	41.197	4.491	14.486	30.971
3	2.968	9.573	55.309	3.327	10.731	51.928	3.807	12.281	43.252
4	2.029	6.544	61.853	1.704	5.497	57.425	2.771	8.937	52.189
5	1.322	4.264	66.117	0.999	3.222	60.647	2.142	6.910	59.099
6	1.112	3.588	69.705	0.597	1.927	62.573	1.077	3.474	62.573

*a Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.

*b Factors that have eigenvalues less than 1 are not shown in the Total Variance Explained table.

Furthermore, it was found that the average extracted communalities of all the variables were above 0.60 (see table 4.12). It was also found that the communalities on one item of market orientation (MO3), two items of learning orientations (LO4 and LO8) and one item of firm performance (P5) were found below the extraction of 0.5.

Moreover, the rotated factor matrix highlights that three of these items (MO3, LO4 and P5) are the candidates of removal as they did not load on any factor with the loading of above 0.4. Similarly, another item of learning orientation LO7 and two items of financial resources, FR1 and FR2, were not loaded on to their main factors (see table 4.12). Therefore, these items were also considered as the candidates for removal.

Table 4.12 - SPSS Output for Communalities and Rotated Factor Matrix*

Rotated Factor Matrix								Communalities
Construct	Items	Factor						Extraction
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	0.720						0.665
	EO2	0.785						0.794
	EO3	0.858						0.838
	EO4	0.875						0.869
	EO5	0.796						0.722
	EO6	0.705						0.628
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1			0.733				0.551
	MO2			0.776				0.657
	MO3							0.186
	MO4			0.816				0.690
	MO5			0.810				0.688
	MO6			0.853				0.738
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1		0.658					0.612
	LO2		0.816					0.791
	LO3		0.865					0.865
	LO4							0.186
	LO5		0.725					0.693
	LO6		0.719					0.623
	LO7	0.624						0.596
	LO8		0.540					0.497
	LO9		0.622					0.589
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1					0.593		0.649
	FR2				0.455	0.704		0.796
	FR3				0.886			0.829
	FR4				0.904			0.840
	FR5				0.792			0.666
Firm Performance (P)	P1					0.570		0.597
	P2					0.638		0.652
	P3					0.756		0.788
	P4					0.527		0.504
	P5							0.146
*a Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.								
*b Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.								
*c Rotation converged in 6 iterations.								

4.8.3 EFA After Modification

As it was found that there were issues of low communalities, higher numbers of factors over the eigenvalue of 1 and issues of factor loadings on the rotated factor matrix. The researcher decided to remove the problematic items one by one to achieve the rotated

factor matrix with items tapping into the same construct. As a result, the researcher removed one item of market orientation (MO3), two items of learning orientation (LO4 and LO7) and one item of firm performance (P5). The removal of these items was felt justified as these items belonged to large latent reflective constructs. The detail of the items deleted is shown in table 4.13.

Table 4.13 - Problematic Items Deleted

Construct	Code	Description of Item Deleted
Market Orientation	MO3	When something important happens to a major customer or market, the whole business unit is informed about it within a short period.
Learning Orientation	LO4	There is a well-expressed concept of who we are and where we are going as a company.
	LO7	Managers in our company do <u>not</u> want their "view of the world" to be questioned. (Reverse coded)
Firm performance	P5	New product/process innovation rate is higher in your firm as compared to the past three years.

The deletion of these four items led to achieving the cumulative rotated sums of squares loading of 65.594%, which is above the cut off of 50%. The total variance explained table also shows that there are five common factors now, as required in this study (see table 4.14).

Table 4.14 - SPSS Output of Total Variance Explained (After Modification) *

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared			Rotation Sums of Squared		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	9.579	35.477	35.477	9.099	33.699	33.699	4.480	16.594	16.594
2	3.731	13.820	49.297	2.918	10.807	44.506	4.430	16.407	33.001
3	2.923	10.827	60.124	3.084	11.422	55.928	3.482	12.896	45.897
4	1.879	6.959	67.083	1.620	6.001	61.929	3.060	11.332	57.229
5	1.271	4.706	71.788	0.990	3.665	65.594	2.259	8.366	65.594

*a Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.

*b Factors that have eigenvalues less than 1 are not shown in the Total Variance Explained table.

Similarly, average extraction communalities found above 0.60 with each item above 0.50 ranging from 0.501 to 0.869. Likewise, the rotated factor matrix highlights that all variables of the same construct are grouped into separate factor. The table now provides a clean factor structure with high loadings (above 0.40) and no major cross-loadings (see table 4.15). This, in turn, prove the convergent and discriminant validity of the model at the EFA stage.

Table 4.15 - Rotated Factor Matrix (After Modification)*

		Rotated Factor Matrix					Communalities	Cronbach's Alphas
Construct	Variables	Factor					Extraction	
		1	2	3	4	5		
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	0.702					0.665	0.945
	EO2	0.779					0.794	
	EO3	0.860					0.838	
	EO4	0.874					0.869	
	EO5	0.780					0.722	
	EO6	0.682					0.628	
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1			0.732			0.551	0.903
	MO2			0.777			0.657	
	MO4			0.819			0.690	
	MO5			0.814			0.688	
	MO6			0.853			0.738	
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1		0.649				0.612	0.908
	LO2		0.818				0.791	
	LO3		0.863				0.865	
	LO5		0.724				0.693	
	LO6		0.721				0.623	
	LO8		0.553				0.501	
	LO9		0.628				0.589	
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1				0.501		0.649	0.878
	FR2				0.560		0.796	
	FR3				0.910		0.829	
	FR4				0.894		0.840	
	FR5				0.804		0.666	
Firm Performance (P)	P1					0.599	0.597	0.851
	P2					0.672	0.652	
	P3					0.726	0.788	
	P4					0.539	0.504	

*a Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.
*b Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.
*c Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Source: SPSS Output of EFA

Based on the result of this EFA, there are now six items of entrepreneurial orientations which are loaded on factor 1, seven items of learning orientation that are loaded on factor 2, five items of market orientation loaded on factor 3, five items of financial resources loaded on factor 4 and four items of firm performance loaded on factor 5.

4.8.3.1 Reliability Test After Modification of EFA

As there were numbers of items deleted in the EFA, the internal consistency of the scale items were tested again to see the impact of the deletion of the items. Table 4.15 shows that the coefficient alpha for entrepreneurial orientation is 0.945, market

orientation is 0.903, learning Orientation is 0.908, financial resources are 0.878 and firm performance is 0.851. Therefore, the study meets the requirement of reliability along with validity.

In general, the results of EFA using maximum likelihood factor extraction approach and varimax factor rotations approach shows that all the factor have unique acceptable loadings after deleting 4 items. As a result, this is evidence of the unidimensionality of the dataset.

4.9 Common Method Variance

The data of this research was collected from the same respondents using the same instrument to collect the data on independent and dependent variables. In a research where the self-reported data on different variables were collected from a single key informant (Renko, Carsrud, and Brännback 2009 and Wang, 2008) and both variables are measured using the same survey instrument (Lonial and Carter, 2015), there is a risk of common method variance. Common method variance can bias the findings of the study (Renko, Carsrud, and Brännback 2009) and thus, observed relationships between constructs can either be inflated or deflated (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

To diminish the impact of method variance on the results of a study, the researcher guaranteed confidentiality and firm anonymity since the researchers assured not to disclose any information and the questionnaire instrument did not ask for the participant firms' names. This procedure is suggested by Podsakoff et al. (2003) and implemented by Lonial and Carter, 2015 and Wang 2008.

Statistically, there are several techniques proposed by Podsakoff et al. (2003), to detect the existence of common method variance, however, this study used Harman's one-factor test, which is an approach that is mostly adopted by the researchers (see: Khan (2020); Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018; 2020); Lonial and Carter (2015); Wang, 2008). To run the test, all the items excluding the problematic items that were deleted in the process of exploratory factor analyses were entered into an exploratory factor analysis. The factor analysis of the dependent and independent variables extracted five common factors, with eigenvalues greater than one, accounting for 65.594% of the total variance. This outcome shows that not a

single factor of this research explain a majority of the variance (see table 4.14) as the highest total variance explained on the first factor was 16.594%. Therefore, it was found that common method variance is not considered to be a major threat in the data of this research.

4.10 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) – Measurement Model

After successfully achieving the unique factor loadings and verifying the unidimensionality, Anderson and Gerbing's (1988) two-step approach for SEM was applied. This approach is recommended by Weston and Gore (2006) and also applied by several researchers including; Lonial and Carter (2015); Wang (2008), in their studies focused on organisational orientations. Underpinning this approach, CFA is conducted first to test the measurement model and then the full structural model is estimated (Weston and Gore, 2006).

CFA is another broad category of factor analysis (Kline, 2016), which also examine if the items load on underlying latent construct as anticipated (Weston and Gore, 2006) and thus confirm the factor structure extracted in the EFA. However, it is different from EFA as it ascertains to the extent the study's theoretical specification of the factors matches reality and hence, it is a tool that helps to accept (confirm) or reject the predetermined theory (Hair et al., 2014). According to Byrne (2016), the confidence in the results of the structural model analysis can only be achieved if the measurement model is functioning sufficiently, therefore, CFA is conducted to test the validity of the measurement model before evaluating the structural model.

Hair et al. (2014, p. 576) claimed that the validity of the measurement model depends on two key aspects (a) "establishing acceptable levels of goodness-of-fit for the measurement model" and (b) "finding specific evidence of construct validity". Therefore, the measurement model was examined to ensure the validity, reliability and fitness of the overall good model, construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and construct reliability (Khan et al., 2020). An overview of these measures are presented in table 4.16 and the model is depicted in figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3 - Measurement Model

Source: AMOS Output of CFA

Table 4.16 - Summary of CFA – Measurement Model

Construct	Items	Factor Loadings	Critical Ratio (t-value)	AVE	MSV	CR	R ²
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	0.811		0.743	0.395	0.945	0.657
	EO2	0.890	19.361				0.791
	EO3	0.916	20.267				0.838
	EO4	0.929	20.753				0.863
	EO5	0.841	17.758				0.707
	EO6	0.775	15.790				0.600
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1	0.714		0.595	0.377	0.911	0.510
	LO2	0.840	14.323				0.706
	LO3	0.880	14.973				0.774
	LO5	0.808	13.779				0.653
	LO6	0.762	12.994				0.580
	LO8	0.661	11.270				0.437
	LO9	0.710	12.112				0.504
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1	0.736		0.655	0.156	0.905	0.542
	MO2	0.805	14.041				0.648
	MO4	0.832	14.521				0.692
	MO5	0.822	14.349				0.676
	MO6	0.847	14.788				0.717
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1	0.561		0.597	0.101	0.877	0.315
	FR2	0.616	8.669				0.379
	FR3	0.915	10.908				0.838
	FR4	0.892	10.795				0.795
	FR5	0.812	10.298				0.660
Firm Performance (P)	P1	0.792		0.599	0.397	0.855	0.627
	P2	0.783	14.438				0.613
	P3	0.857	15.900				0.734
	P4	0.649	11.597				0.421

AVE = Average Variance extracted, CR = Composit Reliability, R²(R-squared) = Squared Multiple Correlation
MSV = Maximum Shared Variance

4.10.1 Model fit

There are several unique goodness-of-fit (GOF) measures available, which Hair et al. (2014) categorised into three sets namely: (a) absolute measures, (b) incremental measures, and (c) parsimony fit measures. As it is unrealistic to report all the indices (Hooper et al., 2008), Kline (2016, p. 269) suggested four key fit measures as a minimum set of measures that should be reported, which are, (1) “Model chi-square with its degrees of freedom and p-value”, (2) “Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)”, (3) “Comparative Fit Index (CFI)” and (4) “Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)”

Hair at al. (2014) also argued that reporting three to four measures, such as Chi-square, degree of freedom, RMSEA and CFI are adequate and reporting all goodness-of-fit is not required as they are often redundant. Therefore, to assess the

appropriateness of the measurement model and structure model, four fit measures were examined in this study, including overall fit (Cmin/df), CFI of incremental measure, and RMSEA and SRMR of absolute measures of fit. Weston and Gore (2006) also used these four measures to assess their model. Hu and Bentler (1999) cut off criteria is used to assess these fits as shown in table 4.17.

Table 4.17 - Cut-off criteria

Measures	Terrible	Acceptable (Between)	Excellent
Cmin/df	>5	5 to 3	>1
CFI	<0.90	0.90 to 0.95	>0.95
SRMR	>0.10	0.10 to 0.08	<0.08
RMSEA	>0.08	0.08 to 0.06	<0.06
Pclose	<0.01	0.01 to 0.05	>0.05

Source: Hu and Bentler (1999)

The study achieved a good model fit in the measurement model without any re-specification. As shown in Table 4.18 that measurement model (figure 4.4) exhibits good overall fits statistics. The model fit indices were Cmin/df = 2.837, CFI = 0.907, SRMR = 0.076 and RMSEA = 0.077

Table 4.18 - Model Fit Measures of Measurement Model

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	890.836	--	--
DF	314	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.837	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.907	>0.95	Acceptable
SRMR	0.076	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.077	<0.06	Acceptable

Source: AMOS Plugin Output for Model Fit Measures AMOS output (Gaskin and Lim, 2016)

4.10.2 Construct Validity

Construct validity indicates that the items that are designed to measure, actually measure the underlying theoretical latent construct (Kline, 2016) and thus, it is one of the key purpose of conducting CFA (Hair et al., 2014). In this study, convergent validity and discriminant validity was measured to assess the validity of the constructs.

Convergent Validity: It was measured by assessing the factor loadings (Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández, 2018; 2020) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE; Calabrò et al., 2020; Castejón et al., 2020). When the items measure the underlying construct share high factor loading i.e. the loading with 'standardised loading estimates' of above 0.5, on that construct then that common latent construct has convergent validity (Hair et al., 2014). In this research, all standardised loading estimates of the model were found above 0.5. While, AVE is the average of squared standardised correlation of indicators of the same factor and not specified to measure any other factors (Kline, 2016). According to Hair et al. (2014), the cut-off value of AVE is 0.5 or above. Table 4.16 provides the evidence that AVE values for all the constructs of the study are greater than 0.5 and thus, proves the convergent validity.

Discriminant validity: This is to examine if the two different constructs are actually distinct (Hair et al., 2014). There are two ways to assess discriminant validity. The first is to see if the items that are not supposed to measure the same construct are not highly intercorrelated (Kline, 2016), i.e. it should not be higher than the squared root of AVE (Hair et al., 2014). For example, in this study, the items of EO should not intercorrelate with the items of any other construct (i.e. LO, MO, FR and P; Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández, 2018; 2020). Hair et al. (2014) stated that the higher the difference among those items the more valid a construct will be to measure underlying theory as compare to other constructs (Hair et al, 2014). The second is to compare Maximum Shared Variance (MSV) to AVE in which if AVE is greater than MSV then the study has no discriminant validity issues (see, Wang, 2008 and Wolff, Pett and Ring, 2015). Table 4.19 highlights that all AVE values or the square root of all AVE values (diagonally highlighted values on table 4.19) are greater than the intercorrelation of the constructs and all AVE values are greater than MSV. For example, the AVE of EO is 0.743 which is greater than 0.614 (squared correlation of EO and LO), 0.224 (squared correlation of EO and MO), 0.194 (squared correlation of EO and FR) and 0.63 (squared correlation of EO and P). Therefore, the study meets the discriminant validity requirements.

Table 4.19 - CR, AVE, MSV and Squared Construct Correlation

	CR	AVE	MSV	EO	LO	MO	FR	P
EO	0.945	0.743	0.397	0.862				
LO	0.911	0.595	0.377	0.614***	0.771			
MO	0.905	0.655	0.156	0.224***	0.082	0.809		
FR	0.877	0.597	0.101	0.194**	0.270***	0.003	0.773	
P	0.855	0.599	0.397	0.63	0.545	0.395	0.318	0.774

Squared Root of AVEs = Diagonal highlighted Values, CR = Composit Reliability, R²(R-squared) = Squared Multiple Correlation, MSV = Maximum Shared Variance
 Significance of Correlations: † p < 0.100, * p < 0.050, ** p < 0.010, *** p < 0.001

Source: Gaskin et al., 2019 AMOS output for Validity test Plugin

4.10.3 Construct Reliability

Construct reliability (CR) or also known as composite reliability is also an indicator of convergent validity and in AMOS CR is often used rather than Cronbach alpha. A value of 0.7 or above is a good measure of construct reliability (Hair et al., 2014). The construct reliability is observed in this study as all CR values are greater than 0.7 (Cake et al., 2020; see table 4.16 & 4.19).

4.11 Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) – Structural Model

The results of CFA highlighted the relationships between observed and unobserved variables and verified that the measurement model fits the data well. CFA further clarify the pattern of loadings extracted in EFA on a specific factor. The unidimensionality of the constructs, as verified by the overall fit of the measurement model (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988) allowed the researcher to proceed to the structural path model. The measurement model was used to calculate factor scores for the latent variables using regression imputation, which is the most widely used AMOS default approach to impute data. These factor scores were also required to compute the product terms for moderation.

4.11.1 Estimation of the Structural Model

A full structural path model was analysed using the imputed latent variables. It was found that the structural model has good fit measures (see table 20). Using the Hu

and Bentler (1999) cut off criteria it was found that the ratio of Cmin/df, the values of CFI and SRMR were found within excellent range i.e. Cmin/df = 2.155 between 1 & 3, CFI = 0.986 above the threshold value of <0.95 and SRMR = 0.056 less than the threshold value of <0.08. The RMSEA is found within an acceptable range as the value of RMSEA (0.061) was between the threshold value of >0.06 to >0.08. Therefore, overall fit indices indicate that the structural model fits the data.

Table 4.20 - Structural Model Fit Indices

Measure	Estimate	Threshold	Interpretation
CMIN	19.395	--	--
DF	9	--	--
CMIN/DF	2.155	Between 1 and 3	Excellent
CFI	0.986	>0.95	Excellent
SRMR	0.056	<0.08	Excellent
RMSEA	0.061	<0.06	Acceptable

The model is described graphically in figure 4.4 which depict the relationships as hypothesised in the conceptual model and table 4.21 present the detailed information. The constructs naming FR_X_EO, FR_X_MO and FR_X_LO are the computed product terms (latent product variables) that were used to calculate the moderating effects of financial resources (FR) on the relationships of EO→P, MO→P and LO→P and to find out the level of significance of this moderating effect. This method is applied by Calabrò et al. (2020); Hernández-Linares, Kellermanns and López-Fernández (2018; 2020). The figure presents the standardised coefficient of each regression pathway indicating the effect of the relationship. Table 4.21 depict the parameter estimates including (a) standardized coefficient also known as a Beta coefficient (β) and unstandardized coefficient (B), both indicate the strength of the relationship and (b) squared multiple correlations (R^2) which indicates the proportion of variance explained by exogenous variables on endogenous variables (Kline, 2016). Furthermore, table 4.21 also highlights the standard error (S.E), the critical ration (t-value) and the significant value (p-value) which show the level of significance of the coefficient (relationship). The t-value of ≥ 1.96 for a p-value of $\leq .05$ highlights that the parameter (path) is significant.

All paths between independent variables (EO, MO, LO) and moderator variable (FR) to the dependent variable (P) are found significant. However, none of the effects of

latent product variables (FR_X_EO, FR_X_LO, and FR_X_MO) on the dependent variable (P) was found significant, as neither t-value is found beyond the absolute critical value of ± 1.96 nor p-value is found $\leq .05$. Similarly, the value of R^2 was 0.628, which indicate that 62.8% of the variance in firm performance (P) was explained by all the exogenous variables that were tested in this study. These results are discussed in detail in the next (Discussion) chapter.

Figure 4.4 – Structural Path Mode

Table 4.21 – Parameter Estimates, Critical Ratios and p-values

	Relationship	β	B	S.E.	C.R (t-value)	P-value	R^2
P	<--- EO	0.407	0.368	0.042	8.7	***	0.628
P	<--- MO	0.313	0.242	0.028	8.757	***	
P	<--- LO	0.249	0.243	0.045	5.343	***	
P	<--- FR	0.191	0.28	0.053	5.262	***	
P	<--- FR_X_EO	-0.012	-0.006	0.024	-0.247	0.805	
P	<--- FR_X_MO	-0.036	-0.016	0.016	-1.014	0.311	
P	<--- FR_X_LO	0.007	0.003	0.024	0.144	0.886	

Note: R^2 = Squared Multiple Correlations, *** = Significance Value (p-value) <0.001, C.R. (t-value) = Critical ratio, S.E. = Standard Error, β = Standardized Coefficients and B = Unstandardised Coefficients

4.12 Hypotheses Testing

The analyses of the measurement model and the structural model of SEM above lead to the testing of hypotheses. There are altogether seven hypotheses in this study, out

of which four hypotheses are testing the direct relationship between three organisational orientations and firm performance (i.e. $EO \rightarrow P$, $LO \rightarrow P$ and $MO \rightarrow P$) and financial resources (FR) and firm performance ($FR \rightarrow P$). While, three hypotheses are testing the moderating effects of financial resources (FR) on the relationships between three organisational orientations and firm performance (i.e. $FR_X_EO \rightarrow P$, $FR_X_LO \rightarrow P$, and $FR_X_MO \rightarrow P$). The unstandardized coefficient is used to measure the effect of moderation.

To test the moderation effect, a two-stage approach to interaction modelling was adopted based on the work of Kenny and Judd (1984). In the first step of this approach, the values of the variables of interest (EO, LO, MO and FR) were standardized using the IBM SPSS, which created four new standardized variables. In the second stage, standardized variables were multiplied as per the requirement of the study to obtain a single item indicator representing the product of the two measured variables. For example, in this study, the variables of interest i.e. EO, LO, MO and FR were obtained by imputing the factor scores from observed variables. These variables were standardized using the IBM SPSS software, which created new standardized variables naming ZEO, ZLO, ZMO and ZFR. As this study is testing the moderating effect of FR, therefore the product term FR_X_EO , FR_X_LO and FR_X_MO , were produced by multiplying ZFR and ZEO, ZFR and ZLO, and ZFR and ZMO respectively.

4.12.1 Hypothesis 1 - Direct Effect of Entrepreneurial Orientation

This study hypothesised that “entrepreneurial orientation (EO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P)”. Table 4.21 shows that the standardised coefficient of entrepreneurial orientation on firm performance is Beta (β) = 0.407*** with a p-value of less than 0.001 ($p < 0.001$) and a t-value of 8.7, which is above the absolute critical value of ± 1.96 . Therefore, hypothesis 1 is supported along with extant literature, as the results verify the significant direct relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and firm performance.

4.12.2 Hypothesis 2 - Direct Effect of Learning Orientation

It was hypothesised that “learning orientation (LO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P)”. Table 4.21 shows that the standardised coefficient of learning

orientation toward firm performance is $\text{Beta} = 0.249^{***}$. The effect is significant as the t-value of 5.343 is above ± 1.96 and the p-value is < 0.001 . Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected as the results support hypothesis 2.

4.12.3 Hypothesis 3 - Direct Effect of Market Orientation

Hypothesis three that “market orientation (MO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P)” is also supported as the evidence shows that the standardised coefficient of market orientation on firm performance is $\text{Beta} = 0.313^{***}$ with a p-value of less than 0.001 and t-value (8.757) is above ± 1.96 (see table 4.21). Therefore, hypothesis 3 is also accepted, confirming the contemporary literature.

4.12.4 Hypothesis 4 - Direct Effect of Financial Resources

It was also hypothesised that “financial resources (FR) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P)”. Although, the relationship between financial resources and firm performance is found weaker than the relationships between any of the organisational orientations and firm performance, however, this hypothesis (H4) is also supported, because the standardised coefficient of financial resources on firm performance which is $\beta = 0.191^{***}$ is found significant as both t-value (5.262) and p-value (< 0.001) are acceptable.

4.12.5 Hypothesis 5 - Moderated Effect of Financial Resource on Entrepreneurial Orientation

It was hypothesised that ‘the moderating effect of financial resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship of EO and firm performance (P)’. The results show that the moderator product term (FR_X_EO) has a negative effect on performance with an unstandardized coefficient of $B = -0.006$. Therefore, the plot (figure 4.5) for the moderation of FR on the relationship between $\text{EO} \rightarrow \text{P}$ highlights that FR dampens the $\text{EO} \rightarrow \text{P}$ relationship. However, the effect of moderation is not significant because the t-value of -0.247 is between ± 1.96 and the p-value is greater than 0.05. As a consequence of the absence of significant paths, it can be concluded that financial resources have no moderating effects on the relationship between EO and firm performance and thus, hypotheses 5 is not supported.

Figure 4.5 - Moderating Effect of FR on EO → P

Source:- Output of Further Analysis

4.12.6 Hypothesis 6 - Moderated Effect of Financial Resource on Learning Orientation

In hypothesis six it was hypothesised that ‘the moderating effect of financial resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship of LO and firm performance (P)’. The results show that the moderator product term (FR_X_LO) has a positive effect on performance with an unstandardized coefficient of B = 0.003. Therefore, the plot for the moderation of FR on the relationship between LO → P highlights that FR strengthen the LO → P relationship. However, the effect of moderation is not significant because it does not meet the requirements of t-value (0.144) and p-value (.886). As a result, there is an absence of significant paths and thus, it proves that there is no moderating effect of FR on LO → P relationship and the hypotheses six is not supported.

Figure 4.6 - Moderating Effect of FR on LO → P

Source:- Output of Further Analysis

4.12.7 Hypothesis 7 - Moderated Effect of Financial Resource on Market Orientation

Hypothesis seven that ‘the moderating effect of financial resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship of MO and firm performance (P)’ was also rejected as it is not found significant. The results show that the moderator product term (FR_X_MO) has a negative effect on performance with an unstandardized coefficient of B = -0.016. The plot (figure 4.7) for the moderation of FR on the relationship between MO and firm performance highlights that FR dampens the MO→P relationship. Again, the effect of moderation is not significant because it does not meet the requirements of t-value (-1.014) and p-value (0.311). As a result, there is an absence of significant paths, which highlights that FR has no moderating effect on MO→P relationship and hypotheses seven is not supported.

Figure 4.7 - Moderating effect of FR on MO →P

Source:- Output of Further Analysis

Table 4.22 - Summary of Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis	Result
H1: Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	Supported
H2: Learning Orientation (LO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	Supported
H3: Market Orientation (MO) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	Supported
H4: Financial Resources (FR) has a direct and positive effect on firm performance (P).	Supported
H5: The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between EO and firm performance (P).	Not Supported
H6: The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between LO and firm performance (P).	Not Supported
H7: The moderating effect of Financial Resources (FR) strengthen the positive relationship between MO and firm performance (P).	Not Supported

4.13 Chapter Summary

The key aim of this chapter was to outline the process of data analysis and present the research findings. The data was analysed in four stages. In stage one (data screening) the data were coded, entered and initial screening tests were applied to identify any errors and to check the reliability of the data. Then the chapter highlighted the process of identifying and handling the issues of missing data, outliers, normality, collinearity, homoscedasticity and linearity of the data. The response rate and tests of non-response bias were also presented in this stage. The results indicated that the data meets the requirements of normality, collinearity, homoscedasticity and linearity. Altogether, 322 responses were received yielding a response rate of 21.38%, out of which 9 responses were deleted as 5 had missing data and 4 were with outlier values, 313 usable responses. It was found that most of the respondents were male (73.16%), from the age group of 35-54 years (35.06%), have a college-level education (35.46%) and were owner/CEO/proprietor of the firm (49.20%). Similarly, most of the respondent firms were micro firms (63.26%), have an annual turnover of less than €2 million (73.48%), between 6 to 10 years (23.96%) of operations and were from the retail industry.

In stage two (EFA), the chapter presented the process of sampling adequacy tests to assess the appropriateness of the dataset before preceding to EFA. Next, the chapter outlined the EFA in which four questionnaire items were found redundant and deleted

to achieve the right numbers of valid and reliable common latent factors. As the self-reported data on different variables were collected from a single key informant, the Harman's one-factor test was conducted in this stage to statistically examine common method variance. The result highlighted that common method variance was not a threat.

In the third stage, CFA was conducted to examine if the measurement model has an overall good model fit, construct validity (convergent and discriminant) and construct reliability. An overview of these measures was presented in table 4.16 and the model is depicted in figure 4.3. The measurement model was found to be a good fit without any re-specification along with significant construct validity and construct reliability.

The structural path model was analysed in the fourth stage. The factor scores of the latent construct, obtained by regression imputation of the measurement model, were used to analyse the structure (path) model. The results showed that the structure model was a good fit to data and all paths between independent variables (EO, MO, LO) and moderator variable (FR) to the dependent variable (P) were found significant supporting hypotheses 1, 2, 3 and 4. However, none of the effects of latent product variables (FR_X_EO, FR_X_LO, and FR_X_MO) on the dependent variable (P) were found significant, rejecting hypotheses 5, 6 and 7.

5 Chapter Five – Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The identification of factors enhancing firm performance is key to success, particularly for SMEs. The importance of SMEs is enormous in an economy; however, their access to limited financial resources is a potential threat to their performance. This study identified four key factors, entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientation (LO), market orientation (MO) and financial resources, and investigated their relationship with firm performance. This research also examined the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationship between three organisation orientations (EO, LO and MO) and firm performance. The study outlined a conceptual framework and seven research hypotheses following an in-depth literature review in chapter 2. The study applied a survey strategy to collect cross-sectional data from Scottish SMEs to test underlying hypotheses (see chapter 3). The data were analysed using structural equation modeling (SEM) and findings are presented in chapter 4.

This chapter synthesised the findings to draft the critical discussion of the results of the study. First, the discussion of the findings related to the hypotheses of this study outlined. This study hypothesised two types of relationships, direct effect relationship and moderating effect relationship. Second, the discussions on research implications are presented in which the theoretical implications of the findings on organisational orientations, financial resources and firm performance and practical implications of the findings on improving firm performance are discussed.

5.2 Results of Direct Effect on Firm Performance

The conceptual framework depicted in chapter 2 (figure 2.4) proposed four hypotheses to test the direct positive effect between EO and firm performance (EO→P), MO and firm performance (MO→P), LO and firm performance (LO→P) and financial resources and firm performance (FR→P). Figure 5.1 highlighted below, derived from the analysis of the data collected for this research, shows the final model of the relationships between exogenous and endogenous variables.

Figure 5.1 - Final Model

The results of the analysis conducted in chapter 4 indicated that all the hypotheses purposing direct effects (i.e. $EO \rightarrow P$, $MO \rightarrow P$, $LO \rightarrow P$ and $FR \rightarrow P$) were supported as they were found to have a positive and significant effect. Moreover, the model fit of the direct relationships depicted in the conceptual framework was also found significant. The in-depth discussion on these findings is as follows:

5.2.1 Direct Effect of EO on Firm Performance (H1)

Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) was theorised as a firm related internal factor that influences firm performance. In this study, EO is comprised of three key characteristics of an entrepreneur namely innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness. In other words, an entrepreneurial firm is the one that employs and support new ideas, innovation, investigations, creativity, willing to take the risky decisions and has the propensity of introducing new product or service with the ability to make a timely decision of whether or not to launch the new product or service.

In this study, it was found that the entrepreneurial orientation (EO) have a significant direct and positive effect on SMEs performance, which in turn, implies that EO supports higher firm performance in the Scottish SMEs. The results indicate that the participant firms were agreed that Scottish firms with EO can obtain superior performance.

The result of $EO \rightarrow$ Performance relationship in this study is consistent with studies conducted by Acosta et al. (2018); Andersén and Samuelsson (2016); Cake et al.

(2020); Calabrò et al. (2020); Galbreath et al. (2020); Gupta et al. (2020); McGee and Peterson (2019); Morgan and Anokhin (2020). Rauch et al. (2009); Wiklund (1999); Wiklund and Shepherd (2003; 2005); Wolff, Pett and Ring (2015) and Zahra and Covin (1995). This research found that EO is a positive factor that enhances Scottish SMEs performance and the effect of EO→Performance relationship ($\beta=0.41$) was found greater than the other two orientations examined in this study.

5.2.2 Direct Effect of LO on Firm Performance (H2)

The results of this study also supported hypothesis 2, that “LO has a direct and positive effect on firm performance”. In this study, LO is also encompassed of three components, “commitment to learning, open-mindedness and shared vision”. In other words, LO of the firms referred to their value to learning, the unbiased inclination to new ideas that may provoke their existing processes and unify their learning activities.

The effect of LO on performance ($\beta=0.25$) was found to be the lowest as compared to the other two orientations. As argued by Lonial and Carter (2015) that LO→P relationship may vary by company size and the weak LO→P relationship in SMEs may be because they are less committed to learning as compared to the large firms. However, the positive direct relationship of LO→P is found in line with several previous studies such as Baker and Sinkula (1999); Calantone, Cavusgil, and Zhao (2002); Spicer and Sadler-Smith (2006); Wang (2008); Gupta et al. (2020) and Kumar et al. (2020). Wang (2008) found a relatively strong relationship of LO→performance ($\beta=0.53$).

The respondents' positive feedback on LO→P relationship suggests that if Scottish SMEs are to implement learning orientation, they should create and boost a culture that supports learning within the firm. Therefore, Scottish SMEs should create a learning culture to quickly adapt to changing business environment ahead of their competitors to bring a positive impact on performance.

5.2.3 Direct Effect of MO on Firm Performance (H3)

As predicted in hypothesis 3, it was found that there is a significant positive direct relationship between MO and SMEs performance. In this study, MO is referred to as

the extent to which a firm is focused on the generation of market intelligence, dissemination of market intelligence concerning current and future customers needs and being responsive ahead of rivals. The feedback from participant firms of the current study proposed that the direct relationship between MO and Scottish SMEs performance is significant, however, the strength of the effect ($\beta=0.31$) was found lower than the effect of EO on firm performance.

The predominant view reflects the positive link between MO and firm performance as consistent with the finding of this study, The result of the positive relationship of MO→P (financial performance) is consistent with the previous studies of Narver and Slater (1990), Jaworski and Kohli (1993), Pelham and Wilson (1996), Baker and Sinkula (1999) and Kirca et al. (2005). They found a positive effect of MO on the firms' financial performance, such as sales growth and profit, however, not on the market share (non-financial performance) of a firm. This study is also consistent with Abbu and Gopalakrishna (2019) in terms of financial as well as non-financial performance (i.e. customer service performance) and with Morgan and Anokhin (2020) in terms of non-financial performance (i.e NPD performance). Moreover, the findings of this study regarding MO→performance relationship found contrary to the finding of Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009) as they found no support for the positive relationship between MO and subjective performance.

Morgan, Vorhies and Mason (2009) highlighted that the key reason of for the lack of MO and subjective performance relationship may be because respondents believe that marketing capabilities are strongly connected with firm performance. This may increase the strength of the relationship between marketing capabilities and subjective performance and in turn, may reduce the relationship between MO and subjective performance. They found in their study that the MO and subjective performance relationship was stronger and significant in the absence of marketing capabilities which reduced to 0.02 in the presence of marketing capabilities. Furthermore, they adopt a singular market information processing view, which restricts them to fully explain firms' MO as it relates to their marketing capability deployment mechanisms.

In general, firms that generate market intelligence regarding their customers' current and potential needs, disseminate that intelligence across departments and are

responsive to market requirements (i.e. design and offer products or services that meet the current and future needs) can achieve superior performance.

5.2.4 Direct Effect of Financial Resources on Firm Performance (H4)

The positive direct relationships between Financial resources (FR) and Scottish SMEs performance were also found significant, as predicted in hypothesis 4. Financial resources were theorised into two components financial capital and financial literacy, The feedback of respondents supporting FR→P relationship highlights that Scottish SMEs not only have access to financial capital, but they are also financially literate. The literature suggests that the availability of financial capital is a key factor for the success of SMEs and an entrepreneur with more financial knowledge can engage in more financial practices (Wiklund, 1999). Therefore, financial literacy and access to financial capital are those financial resources that enhance Scottish SMEs performance.

The findings of this study regarding the FR→P relationship are consistent with the findings of studies conducted by Binks and Ennew (1996), Bell (1997), Wiklund (1999), Beck and Demirguc-Kunt (2006); Coleman (2007); Fatoki (2011); Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer (2013); Adomakoa, and Danso (2014); Adomakoa, Danso and Damoah (2016); Fowowe (2017) and Li and Qian (2019).

Although, FR→P relationship is consistent with the findings of Wiklund (1999) as it was found significant (p-value = <0.001), however, Wiklund (1999) found that the effect “financial capital availability” on firm performance is stronger than the effect of EO on firm performance. While in this study FR-performance relationship ($\beta=0.19$) was not found stronger than any of the three organisational orientations including EO.

In general, financial resources are important for the success of Scottish SMEs and found consistent with hypothesis 4. However, the effect on SMEs performance is surpassed by organisational orientations.

5.3 Results of Moderating Effect on Firm Performance

Three hypotheses proposed to test the moderating effect of financial resources on the relationship between EO→P, LO→P and MO→P. Figure 5.1 derived from the analysis of the data highlights the final model of the relationships between exogenous and endogenous variables.

The results of the analysis conducted in chapter 4 indicated that none of the moderating effects emerged as significant. In other words, the proposed financial resources do not interact and strengthen (or dampen) the effect of EO→P LO→P and MO→P relationships. The detailed discussion on these findings is as follows.

5.3.1 Moderating Effect of Financial Resources on EO→Performance (H5)

This study hypothesised that “the moderating effect of financial resources strengthens the positive relationship between EO and firm performance” (Hypothesis 5). Against expectation, this study did not find any moderation of financial resources on EO→P relationship. Although, the effect of the moderating product term (FR_x_MO) was found to have a negative effect (B = -0.006) and further analysis of the result shows that financial resources dampen the EO→P relationship, however, no evidence, i.e. p-value = <0.05 or t-value >+/-1.96) was found to support this result. Therefore, it can be concluded that financial resources do not moderate the relationship between EO and firm performance.

This result is in line with the result of a study conducted by Wiklund and Shepherd (2005). They hypothesised that: “The relationship between EO and small business performance is moderated by access to financial capital. Small business performance increases with EO but at a faster rate for those that have greater access to financial capital” (p. 78), however, they also did not find a significant p-value to support this hypothesis. The findings are also consistent with Khan et al. (2020) in terms of EO→financial performance relationship as they found significant moderating effects of access to finance only on the relationship between EO and financial performance and not between EO and non-financial performance.

Furthermore, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) also tested the moderating effect of financial capital by hypothesising that “the relationship between the joint implementation of high levels of EO and MO on export performance increases in strength as levels of the financial capital increases in magnitude”. They found that the higher access to financial capital the stronger the effect of the concurrent implementation of EO and MO on export performance.

Several reasons might be associated with this inconsistent result. First, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) studied the impact of the concurrent implementation of EO and MO on SMEs performance and only examine the moderating effects of financial capital on this relationship. While, the current study tested the moderating effect of financial resources, i.e. financial capital and financial literacy, on simultaneously modelled yet independent EO→P and MO→P relationships. Second, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) study is conducted in Ghana, a developing economy as compared to this study, which is examined in Scotland, a developed economy. Finally, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) examined only export SMEs, while this study is focused on all types of SMEs.

Although the findings of this study are unexpected and inconsistent with the traditional view, however, are consistent with RBV assumption in which EO work on the bases of differentiation mechanism in the situation of limited access to resources and stable market conditions. As compared to the situations of a higher access to resources and dynamic market conditions (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005).

In general, this study found that there is a significant positive direct relationship between EO→P and financial resources→P, however, no moderation of financial resources was found on EO→performance relationship.

5.3.2 Moderating Effect of Financial Resources on LO→Performance (H6)

It is proposed in hypothesis 6 that “the moderating effect of financial resources strengthens the positive relationship of LO and firm performance”. The moderating product term (FR_x_LO) was found to have an extremely low but positive effect (B = 0.003) on performance and further analysis of this effect shows that financial

resources strengthen the LO→performance relationship. However, the moderating effect related to hypothesis 6 is not found statistically significant because the p-value is greater than 0.05 ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$), hence, hypothesis six is not supported. Nonetheless, the LO and financial resources both have an independent direct and positive effect on SMEs performance, however, respondents feedback highlights that to enhance the LO→performance relationship, financial resources are not the key requirement of Scottish SMEs.

These findings are inconsistent with Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson (2019) as they found that access to external finance strengthens the LO and firm performance relationship. Several reasons might be the cause of this inconsistent result. First, Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson (2019) conducted their research specifically on manufacturing SMEs, however, this study is focused on SMEs from all sectors. Second, they conducted their research in Nigeria, which is a developing country, While this study is conducted in Scotland which is a developed country. Finally, Bature, Adeoti and Iragbeson (2019) only investigated the moderating effects of access to external finance and only on the direct relationship between LO→performance. Whilst, this study examined the moderating effects of financial resources which include access to external finance, internal finance and most importantly the financial literacy of the firms. Furthermore, this study tested these moderating effects on EO→Performance and MO→performance alongside LO→Performance simultaneously.

Similarly, a study conducted by Adomako and Danso (2014) examined the moderating role of financial capital availability on the relationship between financial literacy (learning) and firm performance. They found that there is a positive moderating effect of the availability of financial resource on the relationship between financial literacy and firm performance. The findings of the current study are not consistent with Adomako and Danso (2014) findings if financial literacy is considered equivalent to learning. Again, Adomako and Danso (2014) study is conducted in Ghana which is a developing economy. Also, they only tested the moderating role of financial capital availability on financial literacy and performance relationship. In other words, they did not examine the effect of LO on performance and take financial literacy as an independent variable. While, the current study examined the moderating effect of both

financial capital and financial literacy simultaneously modelled EO, LO and MO and firm performance relationship. Adomako and Danso (2014) study was used to compare the result of this study due to the lack of studies on moderating effects of financial resources on LO→performance link.

Therefore, nonetheless, LO→P relationship and 'financial resources→P relationship are both positive and direct, however, the financial resources are not found to moderate the relationship of LO→P.

5.3.3 Moderating Effect of Financial Resources on MO→Performance (H7)

The results of this study also reject the hypotheses seven that "the moderating effect of financial resources strengthens the positive relationship of MO and firm performance". The effect of the moderating product term (FR_x_MO) was $B = -0.016$ which imply that financial resources dampen the MO→P relationship, however, as the p-value is found greater than 0.05 and t-value beyond the absolute value of 1.96, hence, this result is insignificant. Therefore, it can be concluded that financial resources have no moderating effect (neither positive nor negative) on the relationship between MO and firm performance.

The results of this study were found inconsistent with the result of a study conducted by Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016). To test the moderating effect of financial capital Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) hypothesised that "the relationship between the joint implementation of high levels of EO and MO on export performance increases in strength as levels of the financial capital increases in magnitude". They found that the EO and MO when implemented concurrently have a stronger impact on export performance with the increase in financial capital.

The inconsistent results might have several reasons. First, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) studied the impact of the concurrent implementation of EO and MO on SMEs performance and only examine the moderating effects of financial capital on this relationship. While, the current study tested the moderating effect of financial resources, i.e. financial capital and financial literacy, on simultaneously modelled yet independent EO→P and MO→P relationships. Second, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan

(2016) study is conducted in Ghana, a developing economy as compared to this study, which is examined in Scotland, a developed economy. Third, Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) examined only export SMEs, while this study is focused on all types of SMEs. Finally, the result might be inconsistent in general because of lack of empirical studies on moderating effects of financial resources on MO→performance relationship, as Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) is the only study found in the empirical literature that is focused on the role of financial capital as a moderator.

Therefore, the results of the current study imply that financial resources do not boost the relationship between MO and Scottish SMEs performance.

5.4 Research Implications

The section above discussed in detail the findings relating to the direct effect of three organisational orientations (EO, LO and MO) and financial resources on the SMEs performance, and moderation effects of financial resources on the relationship of EO→P, LO→P and MO→P. This section outlines the theoretical and practical implications of this research.

5.4.1 Theoretical Implications

Albeit, this research is specifically focused on Scottish SMEs, however, the theoretical literature on the underlying theme of this study can be generalised. This research contributes to the resource-based view (RBV) theory by refining the current understanding of the bundles of resources utilised uniquely. The study contributes to the fields of entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, market orientations and financial resources. The financial resource/s is relatively a new construct studied alongside organisational orientations. This study validated the findings of existing studies which found that entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, market orientations and financial resources have a direct positive effect on SME performance.

Additionally, the theoretical contribution was further extended through successfully testing the moderating effect of financial resources. Little evidence has been found in the literature regarding the moderating effect of financial resources on the relationship of organisational orientation and firm performance. Wiklund and Shepherd (2005);

Boso, Oghazi and Cadogan (2016) and Khan et al. (2020) tested the moderating effect of financial resources, however, they only examined the effect of access to financial capital on the relationship between EO→P. This study not only replicated the moderating effect of financial capital on EO→P relationship but also extended theory by testing moderating effects of financial literacy on EO→P. Furthermore, this study is not only limited to EO→P relationship as Wiklund and Shepherd (2005) and Khan et al. (2020) but also extend the moderating effects of financial resources (financial capital and financial literacy) to LO→P and MO→P relationships. This study contributed that financial resources do enhance SMEs performance; however, they do not strengthen (nor dampen) the relationship between EO→P, LO→P and MO→P.

This study is in line with the researcher's current understandings of RBV. The key RBV assumption, as discussed by scholars (such as Wernerfelt, 1984 and Barney, 1991. – see section 2.7), that the bundles of resources utilised uniquely can enhance business performance, and this has been approved in this research. The results of the current research highlight that bundles of resources when utilised uniquely (i.e. simultaneous in this study) do have a direct positive effect on firm performance. This study by testing some of the VRIN resources and capabilities provides a piece of empirical evidence on how these VRIN resources and capabilities can help SMEs in achieving competitive advantage and superior performance. Therefore, this study significantly contributes to the RBV theory of the firms.

Additionally, the lack of moderating effects of financial resources on the relationship between three key organisational orientations and SMEs performance does not criticise the RBV assumptions rather emphasize on adopting differentiation strategy. Financial resources specifically financial capital is a generic resource and cannot be VRIN unless it is utilised in a unique way (Barney, 1991). As they found not to enhance the relationship between organisational orientations and firm performance in this study, they must be (a) utilised uniquely and (b) invested to accumulate and develop other resources and capabilities that are unique and different from rivals. This may enable firms to discover and exploit new opportunities which might differentiate them from competitors and create a competitive advantage. Furthermore, the lack of support for hypotheses that financial resources strengthen organisational orientations and firm performance relationship might be emphasizing that organisational

orientations are the differentiator. The results might be highlighting that organisational orientations are not the luxury of firms that have easy access to financial resources rather they may under resources constraint provide a differentiation mechanism (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005).

Therefore, it can be concluded that even though no moderating effect is found, adopting bundles of resources are still necessary to achieve superior performance. Nonetheless, this study consistent with the RBV argument contributes that the unique combination of resources and capabilities affect SMEs performance, however, more research is required to further enhance our understanding of how a combination of resources and capabilities lead SMEs to achieve a competitive advantage and better performance.

5.4.2 Practical implication.

The practical guideline can be derived from the results of each of the relationships investigated in the current study and it would be applicable to SMEs that are seeking to achieve superior performance. Nonetheless, more than 87 per cent of the findings of this study were related to the three types of Scottish SMEs i.e. retail (49.52%), service (21.09%) and hospitality (16.93%) and 60% of the findings are related to micro firms (i.e. firms with less than 10 employees). However, these findings can be used as a guideline by other SMEs in Scotland.

Since the SMEs have limited resources and capabilities, specifically the access to financial resources (Brouthers, Nakos, Dimitratos, 2015), the entrepreneurs must prudently allocate resources and decide which resources and capabilities they should invest in. This study highlighted how different organisational orientations along with financial resources related to firm performance, which in turn, provide a guideline to entrepreneurs on making these decisions, specifically, on the order in which organisational orientations should be applied.

The entrepreneurial orientation was found to be the strongest and most significant dimension of organisational orientations in this study. This result guides the entrepreneurs that they must develop entrepreneurial orientation (EO) over and above any other orientations, as each of its three components namely innovativeness, risk-

taking and proactiveness lead to superior firm performance. Innovative firms can generate extraordinary economic performance through the introduction of new products and/or services. Since SMEs have limited access to funds, they may be less willing to take a risky decision, however, risk-taking is what makes a manager an entrepreneur (Carland et al., 1984) and enhance firm performance in the long run. The proactive firms can create a first-mover advantage (Grant, 2015) which enables firms to charge high prices by targeting high-income market segments (Zahra and Covin, 1995)., which in turn lead firms to achieve sustained high performance. Therefore, the managers with a tendency to engage in new ideas and innovation, willing to take a risky decision, and also have the propensity of introducing new products or services with the ability to make the timely decision of whether or not to launch the new product or service, may lead a firm to superior performance.

Similarly, once the firms established entrepreneurial orientation, they should develop market orientation which is the second strongest factor found in this study that enhances SMEs performance. By implementing the right marketing techniques, a firm can offset the key challenges such as customers' changing preferences and competitors' product offerings. The entrepreneurs of a market-oriented firm must generate market intelligence related to customers need and competitors' actions (Lonial and Carter, 2015). Similarly, market intelligence generated is of no use until it is disseminated across the firm which is the key activity of the marketing department of a firm (Schmidt et al., 2016), thus the firms must disseminate the generated intelligence across the different department. Nonetheless, the dissemination of generated market intelligence is important, however, a firm achieves very little unless it takes actions to respond to that intelligence (Kohli and Jaworski's, 1990), therefore, firms must take actions to respond to that intelligence (Rauch et al., 2009). Accordingly, entrepreneurs of SMEs must endeavour to develop appropriate market orientation as a second key component of their strategy.

Although, the effect of learning orientations on firm performance was not found as strong as the effects of the other two orientations, however, the findings suggest that it was also an influential predictor of the performance of a firm. The finding proposes that the firms must support the value of three components of LO ("commitment to learning, open-mindedness and shared vision") to enhance their performance. As

learning is a process that leads to the acquisition of knowledge, thus, the component 'commitment to learning' considered as the most significant component of LO. Commitment to learning value the need to understand the cause and effect of actions which are vital to detect and correct error (Baker and Sinkula, 2005). This, in turn, lead firms to achieve better performance.

Moreover, firms must be open-minded i.e. they must know how to unlearn (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997). As experiences develop a mental model of how things work, which lost its experiential truth with the change in time (Baker and Sinkula, 1999) and thus, may encourage ineffective learning. This is where firms need open-mindedness, which is a link to the notion of unlearning by challenging their long-held routines, assumptions, and beliefs. Hence, it re-invent the firm in the current dynamic, complex, and challenging environments. Unlearning often replace routines and considered an important condition to successfully adopt changes (Tsang and Zahra, 2008).

Similarly, the shared vision component proposes that there should be an agreement on the vision of the firms across all the department of that firm. The lack of shared vision enhances ambiguity in a firm because individuals are less likely to know the key activities of the organisation (Sinkula, Baker, and Noordewier, 1997) which make it hard for individuals to know what to learn and thus, inhibits the higher-order learning (Baker and Sinkula, 2002). In other words, the higher level of shared vision promotes a sense of direction for the firms, which encourages learning and helps the firms to generate good knowledge and capabilities required to outperform rivals.

Nonetheless, each of the orientation plays a unique role in a firm and also found significant in this study, therefore, entrepreneurs must develop three of them, as lack of any one of them may lead to poor performance. An entrepreneurial oriented firm may have invested huge resources to produce an innovated product or service, but without a market orientation, they may not be capable of identifying and adequately prioritising market opportunities with the greatest potential. On the other hand, entrepreneurs with excessive emphasise on market orientation may facilitate a focus on customers satisfaction without having an innovated product or service in hand because of the lack of enough entrepreneurial orientation. Similarly, firms with both EO and MO but without LO may lead firms to slow and obsolete process of innovation

and marketing. The lack of learning orientation means no new knowledge which hinders to share entrepreneurial and market spirit across the different departments of the firms.

Moreover, financial resources were also found to have a positive effect on SMEs performance. Although, this effect was not found as strong as the effect of organisations orientations on performance, however, its positive significant effect enhances its importance for the success of the firm. In this study, financial resources were not only considered as the access or the availability of funds, but financial literacy was also conceptualised as an element of financial resources. Albeit, the importance of access to capital is enormous as a generic resource that can comparatively easily be transformed into other resources (Grimmer, Miles and Grimmer, 2013), however, financial literacy is equally important. The positive effect of financial resources on firm performance found in this study shows that firms to achieve superior performance must be financially literate alongside having access to long-term and short-term funds. Only the financial literate firms can know their financial needs, where to invest and what should be the rate of return.

Nonetheless, financial resources have not been found to moderate the relationship between organisational orientations and firm performance, however, its importance cannot be ignored as an independent factor that is required by the firms to obtain other resources and to implement capital intensive strategies. Therefore, entrepreneurs must attempt to gain financial capital and must be financially literate.

Furthermore, this study also provides a guideline for policymakers. It suggests that policymakers must organise seminars, training and workshops to encourage SMEs to develop organisational orientations. Government and public sector must support SMEs to enhance innovation and sustainability of the industrial sector. They must facilitate SMEs in gathering market intelligence so that they know the potential needs of customers and focus only on the development of key innovative products and services. They must also enhance the importance of learning in firms to enable them to cope with complex and changing business environment and thus, achieve superior performance.

Most importantly policymakers must enhance the availability of finance for SMEs and must provide financial knowledge to CEOs/owners/managers of SMEs. As one of the key reasons for limited access to finance is the failure in the financial market due to asymmetric information and agency problem (OECD, 2017a). The policymakers must arrange conferences and training programs to make firms financially literate specifically in terms of making key financial investment decisions and the ability to predict potential outcome. Financial literacy helps in preparing timely, useable financial information, reduce the issue of asymmetric information and thus, enables lenders to make lending decisions by analysing the resilience of SMEs (Hussain, Salia and Karim, 2018).

Access to finance is harder for micro firms as they get charged a higher interest rate and required more strict security conditions as compared to the larger firms (Storey, 2016). The government must ease access to debt finance for micro firms by offering state-backed loans with minimum interest rate and no repayment for the first three years. In Scotland, 83% of SMEs are not inclined to apply for external finance and are less motivated to grow their business (The Scottish Government, 2019). This will encourage these reluctant 83% of Scottish SMEs to apply for external finance and motivate them to grow their businesses.

5.5 Chapter Summary

This chapter synthesises the results obtained from the analysis of the data in chapter four to draft the discussion of the results of the study. It first discussed the findings underpinning each of the hypotheses and then, presented a discussion on the theoretical and practical contribution of the findings.

The study theorised two types of relationships, direct relationship and moderating relationship. Four hypotheses were proposed to test the direct relationships i.e. EO→Performance, LO→Performance, MO→Performance and FR (financial resources)→Performance relationships. All the direct effect relationships were found to have a positive and significant effect with a satisfactory model fit.

EO was conceptualised as a combination of three components, innovativeness, risk-taking and proactiveness and found to have the strongest positive effect on Scottish

SMEs performance with $\beta=0.41$. MO was also conceptualised into three components, i.e. market intelligence generation, market intelligence dissemination and responsiveness and found to have the strongest positive and significant effect after EO ($\beta = 0.31$) on SMEs performance. LO was also conceptualised into three components, commitment to learning, open-mindedness and shared vision and found to have the lowest effect as compared to the other two orientations ($\beta = 0.25$) in this research, which may be because SMEs are less committed to learning as compared to large firms. Similarly, financial resources (FR) was theorised into two components financial capital and financial literacy. Although the study found a positive direct effect of FR→Performance relationship, it was the lowest (i.e. $\beta=0.19$) of all direct relationships in this study.

Moreover, three hypotheses were proposed to test the moderating effect of financial resources on the relationship between EO→P LO→P and MO→P. The results of the analysis conducted in chapter 4 indicated that none of the moderating effects relationships emerged as significant, i.e. financial resources do not strengthen or dampen the relationship between EO→P LO→P and MO→P of the Scottish SMEs.

The second aim of the chapter was to present a discussion on the research theoretical and practical contribution of the findings. Theoretically, this study (a) validated the findings of existing studies which argued that EO, LO, MO and financial resources all directly and positively effect on SMEs performance and (b) further extended the theory by successfully testing the moderating effect of financial resources. This study challenged the researcher's current understandings of RBV as the key RBV assumption, i.e. the bundles of resources utilised uniquely can enhance business performance, has only been partially approved, as no moderating effect of financial resources was found on the relationship of three organisational orientation and SMEs performance. Although, no moderating effect was found, however, adopting bundles of resources are still necessary to achieve superior performance.

Practically, a guideline can be derived from the results of each of the relationships examined in the current study that would be relevant to SMEs seeking to achieve superior performance. SMEs' limited access to funds suggests that entrepreneurs must prudently allocate financial resources and decide which resources and capabilities they should invest in. This study guides the entrepreneurs to develop

entrepreneurial orientation (EO) over and above any other orientation as EO was found to be the strongest and most significant dimension of organisational orientations followed by the MO and LO.

Nonetheless, each of the orientation plays a unique role in a firm and also found significant in this study, therefore, entrepreneurs must develop three of them as lack of any one of them may lead to poor performance. A firm may not have an innovated product or service with the lack of EO, the lack of MO may not identify and prioritise market opportunities adequately with the greatest potential and the lack of LO means the firms gain no new knowledge which hinders to share entrepreneurial and market sprite across the different department of the firms.

Similarly, a positive financial resources and firm performance link, as found in the study, shows that firms to achieve superior performance must be financially literate alongside having access to long-term and short-term funds. Only the financially literate firms can know their financial needs, where to invest and predict the potential rate of return. The lack of the moderating effects of financial resources does not eliminate its importance as an independent factor.

Furthermore, policymakers must organise seminars, training and workshops to encourage SMEs to develop organisational orientations and to enhance their access to financial capital and financial knowledge.

6 Chapter six – Research Summary, Limitations, Recommendations for Future Research and Conclusion

6.1 Introduction

This chapter concluded the current research undertaken in this thesis, by reviewing and connecting the key elements of the research. The chapter first presented a summary of the overall research by revisiting all the stages of the thesis. Next, It linked the results of each of the hypotheses to the research question. The chapter then discussed the research limitations and presented the recommendations for future research, followed by the a conclusion.

6.2 Summary of the research

Building on the theoretical foundation of this research, i.e. the resource-based view theory, this study identified that three key organisational orientations; entrepreneurial orientation (EO), learning orientation (LO) and market orientation (MO), positively affect SMEs performance. However, the literature highlights that to develop organisational orientations is a capital-intensive strategy and SMEs have limited access to financial resources (Brouthers, Nakos and Dimitratos, 2015), which may influence the level of the effects of each of the organisational orientations on firm performance. Therefore, a gap has been identified to investigate the moderating effects of financial resources (financial capital and financial literacy) on the direct relationships between simultaneously modelled EO and firm performance, LO and firm performance, and MO and firm performance.

Altogether, the study proposed seven hypotheses, four represent direct effect relationships i.e. $EO \rightarrow P$, $LO \rightarrow P$, $MO \rightarrow P$ and $FR \rightarrow P$ and three represent moderating effect relationships i.e. the moderating effects of FR on $EO \rightarrow P$, $LO \rightarrow P$, $MO \rightarrow P$ relationships.

Altogether, seven hypotheses were developed in this study. Four hypotheses proposed direct effects of each of the organisational orientations and financial resources on firm performance, i.e. $EO \rightarrow P$, $LO \rightarrow P$, $MO \rightarrow P$ and $FR \rightarrow P$. While three hypotheses proposed the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationship between each of the organisational orientations and firm performance. A conceptual framework (figure 2.4) was developed which illustrates these relationships.

To test the relationships depicted in the conceptual framework, this study adopted a survey strategy and quantitative data collection method in a cross-sectional time horizon, underpinning the positivism research paradigm. Existing measurement scales were used to develop the survey questionnaire instrument and 7-point Likert scale items were utilised to obtain the responses. Altogether, 322 (21.38%) responses were obtained from Scottish SMEs, out of which 78 were collected online (internet-mediated access approach) from firms identified using the FAME company database and 244 were obtained by approaching firms personally (traditional access approach). A total of 313 (20.78%) responses were found usable.

A four-stage structural equation modelling (SEM) technique was adopted to analyse the data: including data screening, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and the analysis of the structural path model. The data is cleansed, coded, and the issues of missing data, outliers, normality and collinearity were dealt with in the data screening stage. EFA was conducted to identify common latent factors, to ensure their validity and reliability and to identify the common method variance. CFA was implemented to confirm the factor structure extracted in EFA and to assess the measurement model based on overall good model fit, construct validity and reliability. The structural path model was implemented to test the hypotheses.

The findings supported all the direct effect relationships i.e. EO, LO, MO and FR all found to have direct positive and significant effects on Scottish SMEs performance. However, the findings did not support any of the moderating effect relationships, i.e. FR was not found to strengthen the positive effects of EO, LO and MO on Scottish SMEs performance.

Theoretically, this study contributed to the field of organisational orientations and financial resources underlying the resources-based view in two ways. First, the study

contributed to the theory by confirming that entrepreneurial orientation, learning orientation, market orientation and financial resources all have a significant direct and positive effect on SMEs performance. Second, the study contributed to theory by extending the theory through testing the moderating effects of financial resources, in which it was found that financial resources do not enhance the effect of any of the organisational orientations on firm performance.

Practically, SMEs' limited access to funds suggests that entrepreneurs must prudently allocate financial resources and decide which resources and capabilities they should invest in. This study guides the entrepreneurs to adopt all three orientations, however, entrepreneurial orientation (EO) must be preferred over and above any other orientation as being the strongest and most significant dimension of organisational orientations followed by the MO and LO. Similarly, SMEs to achieve superior performance must be financially literate alongside having access to long-term and short-term funds. Only the financial literate firms can know their financial needs, where to invest and potential rate of return. The lack of the moderating effects of financial resources does not eliminate its importance as an independent factor.

Furthermore, policymakers are suggested to organise seminars, training and workshops to encourage SMEs to develop organisational orientations and to enhance their access to financial capital and financial knowledge

6.3 Research questions

This section discusses how the research answer each research question and what are the results. This study proposed three investigative questions.

Question 1. What are the effects of different organisational orientations on SMEs performance?

The study identified three organisational orientations EO, LO and MO. Three hypotheses (H1, H2 and H3) were developed to answer this question suggesting the direct positive effect of each of the orientations on firm performance. The findings showed that all three orientations (EO, LO and MO) have a positive and direct effect

on firm performance. The effect of EO on performance was found to be the strongest followed by MO and LO respectively.

Question 2. What are the effects of financial resources on SMEs performance?

Financial resources as a construct is relatively a new construct studied alongside organisational orientations. This question is answered by testing hypothesis four which proposed the direct and positive effect of financial resources on firm performance. The findings indicated that financial resources and firm performance are positively directly related, however, this relationship was not as strong as the effect of the organisational orientations on firm performance.

Questions 3. What are the moderating effects of financial resources on the relationships between organisational orientations and SMEs performance?

Financial resources were further theorised as a moderator. Three hypotheses were developed to answer this question. The hypotheses posited the moderating effect of financial resources on the relationship between each of the organisational orientations and firm performance. It was found that financial resources do not affect the relationship between any of the organisational orientations and SMEs performance.

6.4 Limitations and future research.

Despite the contributions discussed in chapter five (see section 5.4), there are some limitations of this research that should be considered, as discussed in this section. It is important to recognise and admit the existence of the limitations to properly assess the validity, reliability and generalisability of the findings. Following are the limitations of this research and recommendations for future research

6.4.1 Financial Resources Construct

The study uses the financial resources construct which is relatively a new construct. This construct is conceptualised into two elements; financial capital and financial literacy. Financial literacy referred to the importance of financial knowledge and capabilities which play a fundamental role in financial decision making. Nonetheless, investigating direct and moderating effects of financial resources confirms and extends

current financial resources literature, however, there is a lack of robust empirical evidence of moderating effect of financial resources in the literature. Therefore, it is suggested that future research should adopt those measures that can reflect the financial resources construct better.

6.4.2 Unite of Analysis

The study collected self-reported data from a single subject within a firm, risking common method variance, which can bring bias to the findings of the research. Nonetheless, this method is consistent with the previous studies, for example, Lonial and Carter (2015); Baker and Sinkula (2009); Wang (2008) and Wiklund and Shepherd (2005). Furthermore, “Harman’s one-factor test” specified that the common method variance is not a threat, however, as the surveys were responded by a single subject who may have magnified his/her firm, therefore, the results must be interpreted in consideration of this limitation. Future research may collect data from several key informants to reduce the possible response bias and to increase the level of confidence in the findings.

6.4.3 Research Measures.

Another key limitation of this study is the use of subjective measures. As CEO/Owner/Managers most commonly highlight their firm in a positive context to protect their firm performance, which in turn, hinders the researcher to portray the true position of the firm. Although, these kinds of measures were adopted in previous studies (Wiklund and Shepherd, 2005; 2012; Wang 2008; Santos and Brito, 2012; Vij and Bedi, 2016; Gupta et al., 2020), however, subjective performance measures may lead to bias results. This study was inclined to use subjective measures as there were limited resources and time to complete the study. However, future studies may consider using objective measures for firm performance. This may provide a wider picture of the firms’ positions.

6.4.4 Time Horizon

This research was conducted in a cross-sectional time horizon in which the data was collected at a given point in time. Additionally, the same survey instrument was used

for exogenous and endogenous variables, risking common method variance and causal inference. Albeit, these methods are consistent with the majority of the research in the field of organisational orientations and no evidence of common method variance has been found, however, the causal links between exogenous and endogenous variables cannot be verified. Therefore, to mitigate this concern and to enhance confidence in the findings, future research must consider alternative approaches such as longitudinal design and the use of a separate survey instrument for collecting data on independent and dependent variables.

6.4.5 Research Sample

This research is conducted in Scotland and the data is collected specifically from Scottish SMEs from multiple industries. Furthermore, the data is collected using a hybrid access approach i.e. using a mix of the internet-mediated access approach and the traditional access approach. In the traditional access approach, the researcher collected data personally which limits the researcher's access to the wider population. Although, the research has still collected data from SMEs located in several different cities of Scotland such as Glasgow, Edinburgh, Aberdeen, Dumfries, Sterling and Livingston, however, most of the data is collected from SMEs located in Glasgow. Therefore, recognising the type of data the generalisability of the results can be a major research limitation. This fact raises the need to be caution in generalising the findings to any particular industry, areas beyond Scotland and to larger firms. The future research should focus on a wider range of samples to examine key research areas. The broader research settings, i.e. beyond Scotland and to larger firms, enhance the generalisability of the findings.

6.4.6 Data Collection Method.

The study used a quantitative data collection method and it is mostly used in studies related to organisational orientations. However, as financial resources is comparatively a new construct studied alongside organisational orientations, this may not be measured properly because of the lack of literature, and thus, findings should be observed in light of this limitation. Therefore, to examine a relatively new construct, it is suggested to adopt a qualitative or mixed data collection method in future research. The qualitative method enhances the measurement of a new construct, by

asking open-ended questions knowing exactly how respondents measure that specific new construct. Furthermore, the mixed-method approach may produce in-depth insights than a single method.

6.5 Concluding remarks

The importance of SMEs is enormous in the economy of a country as they are the key source of employment, innovation, technological development and enhance industrialisation. However, they are vulnerable to poor performance and eventually fail to be in operations due to the lack of resources as compared to large firms. The resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, imperfectly imitable and non-substitutable (VRIN) enable firms to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage, which in turn enhance firm performance. Three organisational orientations' such as EO, LO and MO are identified as those specific capabilities that generate a sustainable competitive advantage/s. Similarly, financial resources are crucial for small firms and access to financial resources is correlated with higher levels of firm performance. Financial resources are considered to be one of the most visible and generic resources, which can be converted into other resources easily and thus, allows firms to implement capital-intensive strategies and in turn improved firm performance (Cooper, Gimeno-Gasconand and Woo, 1994).

To develop organisational orientations is capital intensive for SMEs as they have limited access to financial resources (specifically, access to funds), which may obstruct them to become organisational-oriented firms and ultimately to achieve superior performance. Therefore, it was proposed in the hypotheses that alongside having a direct effect on SMEs performance financial resources strengthen the positive effect of EO, LO and MO on SMEs performance. However, the analysis of the data, collected from Scottish SMEs in a cross-sectional setting delivered unexcepted but valuable contributions. The empirical results of this study demonstrated that (a) EO, LO, MO and financial resources all directly and positively effect Scottish SMEs performance and (b) financial resources **do not** strengthen (nor dampen) the effect of EO and Scottish SMEs performance, LO and Scottish SMEs performance and MO and Scottish SMEs performance.

To sum up, Scottish SMEs do need to develop organisational orientations and they do need financial resources as these resources and capabilities were found to enhance their performance. However, Scottish SMEs must not rely on financial resources to strengthen the relationship between organisational orientations and performance because it is not evident that financial resources strengthen the effect of organisational orientations on Scottish SMEs. The results were found unexpected as null hypotheses related to moderating effects cannot be rejected. Therefore, certain limitations must be considered to interpret the findings of this study as discussed in section 6.4.

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Appendix 01 (Survey Instrument)

DOCTORAL RESEARCH SURVEY

Doctor of Business Administration (DBA)

*Required

Information Sheet

Hello:

You are invited to participate in a Doctoral Research Survey. The aim of the research is to investigate the impact of financial capital on the relationship between organisational orientations and Scottish SMEs performance.

PARTICIPATION:

You will not be asked to provide any personal information and/or personal records. You may refuse to take part in the research, exit the survey at any time or decline to answer any particular question, without any explanation.

BENEFITS:

You will receive no direct benefits from participating in this research study.

RISKS:

There are no apparent or hidden risks in participating in this survey.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your survey answers will be analysed for this project and may appear in publication. However, complete confidentiality is assured. The results will be reported in a manner which does not enable you to be identified. The data may be share with the supervisor for the purpose of analysis.

CONTACT

If you have any question at any time about the study, you may contact the;

Researcher: Muhammad Wasim

Email: [REDACTED]

Supervisor: Dr. Adebisi Adewole

Email: [REDACTED]

University of the West of Scotland Personal details withheld.

Paisley Campus

Paisley

PA1 2BE

Scotland

United Kingdom

Tel: +44 (0)141 848 3000

Email: ask@uws.ac.uk

Consent Form

1. If you are willing to participate in this survey, please give your consent below by ticking all the boxes: *

	Agree
I have read the above information	[]
I am over 18 years of age	[]
I voluntarily agree to participate	[]

Questionnaire:

This questionnaire consists of five (5) parts. Part 1 is related to the business background (personal profile and business profile). Please answer all questions by ticking the most relevant box in the part 1. In part 2 to 5, the questions are asked in the form of descriptive statement. Please rate your answer from 1 to 7, by ticking the most appropriate number on the scale as shown below.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neither	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Part 1 - Business Background

Personal Profile

1. What is your Gender?

Male []

Female []

Prefer not to say []

2 What is your age group?

Below 20 years []

20 to 30 years []

31 to 40 years []

41 to 50 years []

51 to 60 years []

61 or above []

3. What is your highest education level?

Primary School []

High School []

College []

Undergraduate degree []

Master's Degree []

Doctoral degree []

Professional Qualification (CA, ACCA, CIMA) []

4. What is your position in your firm?

Business Profile

5. How many full-time employees work in your firm?

Note: Please include owner/managers and part-time employees?

Less than 9 []

10 to 49 []

50 to 249 []

249 or over []

6. what is your annual turnover?

Less than €2 million []

€2 million to €10 million []

12. We value the orderly and risk-reducing management process much more than leadership initiatives for change.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Proactiveness:

13. We firmly believe that a change in market creates positive opportunities for us.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

14. Members of our company tend to talk more about opportunities rather than problems.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Part 2 (b) - Market Orientation

Information acquisition:

15. We are slow to detect changes in our customers' product preferences.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

16. We frequently review the likely effect of changes in our business environment on customers.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Information dissemination:

17. When something important happens to a major customer or market, the whole business unit is informed about it within a short period.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

18. When one department finds out something important about competitors, it is slow to alert other departments.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Responsiveness:

19. For one reason or another, we tend to react slowly to changes in our customers' product or service needs.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

20. Several departments get together periodically to plan a response to changes taking place in our business environment.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Part 2 (c) - Learning Orientation

Commitment to learning:

21. Managers basically agree that our company's ability to learn is the key to our competitive advantage.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

22. The sense around here is that employee learning is an investment, not an expense.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

23. The collective wisdom in this enterprise is that once we quit learning, we endanger our future.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Shared vision:

24. There is a well-expressed concept of who we are and where we are going as a company.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

25. All employees are committed to the goals of our company.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

26. Top leadership believes in sharing its vision for the entire company.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Open-mindedness:

27. Managers in our company do not want their “view of the world” to be questioned.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

28. Managers encourage employees to “think outside of the box.”

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

29. Original ideas are highly valued in this organisation.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Part 3 - Financial Resources

Financial Capital

30. Our firm is satisfied with the access to long term funds for the development of the firm.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

31. Our firm is satisfied with the access to cash (working capital) for day to day financial needs.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Financial Literacy

32. Our firm is usually well-informed about its overall financial needs.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

33. Our firm is well aware of its investment prospects.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

34. Our firm knows the rate of return associated with each investment.

Part 4 - Firm Performance

Financial Performance

35: The return on investment of your firm has increased as compare to the past three years.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

36: The sales of your firm have increased as compare to the past three years.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Non-Financial Performance

37. The market share of your company has significantly increased as compare to the past three years.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

38. The level of customer satisfactions in your company has increased as compare to the past three years.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

39. New product/process innovation rate is higher in your firm as compare to the past three years.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Part 5 - Environment dynamism

40. The industry in which your firm operates is highly competitive.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

41. Market activities of your competitors have become more hostile.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

42. The taste and preference of your customers have become much more stable and predictable in your principal industry.

Strongly Disagree 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 Strongly Agree

Appendix 2 – Coding Sheet

Part 1 - Business Background

Personal Profile

1. What is your Gender?

[Gender]

Male

[1]

Female

[2]

Prefer not to say

[3]

2 What is your age group?

[Age]

Under 18

[1]

18-24

[2]

25-34

[3]

35-44

[4]

45-54

[5]

54+

[6]

3. What is your highest education level?

[Education]

Primary School

[1]

High School

[2]

College

[3]

Undergraduate degree

[4]

Master's Degree

[5]

Doctoral degree

[6]

Professional Qualification

[7]

4. What is your position in your firm?

[Position]

Owner/CEO/Proprietor/Owner and Manager

[1]

Director

[2]

Manager (Any)

[3]

Supervisor

[4]

Business Profile

5. How many full-time employees work in your firm? [Employees]

Note: Please include owner/managers and part-time employees?

Under 10	[1]
10 to 49	[2]
50 to 249	[3]
Over 249	[4]

6. what is your annual turnover? [Turnover]

Under €2 million	[1]
€2 million to €10 million	[2]
€10+ million to €50 million	[3]
Over €50 million	[4]

7. For how many years is your firm in operation? [Firm-age]

Under 3 Years	[1]
3 to 5 years	[2]
6 to 10 years	[3]
11 to 15 years	[4]
Over 15 years	[5]

8. Which industry best describe your business? Please specify

[Industry]

Retail [1]

Wholesale [2]

Service: [3]

Customer services

Legal Services

Personal Services

Professional Services

Financial Services (including Accountancy)

Social Care

IT (SOFTWARE)

Print communications

Distribution, Supplier [4]

Hospitality: [5]

Food

Café, Restaurant, Catering (Coffee Shop)

Tourism

Accommodation

Leisure (Hi Rel Aerospace)

Manufacturing [6]

Fashion (Cosmetic) [7]

E-commerce [8]

Property [9]

Part 2 - Organisational Orientations

Likert Scale

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Neither	Slightly Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree

Part 2 (a) - Entrepreneurial Orientation [EO]

Innovativeness: [Innova]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
EO1	Q9	We are usually first-to-market with new products and services.	7 Point	Scale
EO2	Q10	We (Top management) in the company encourage the development of innovative marketing strategies, knowing well that some will fail.	7 Point	Scale

Risk Taking: [Risk]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
EO3	Q11	Our company like to “ <u>Play it safe.</u>	7 Point	Scale
EO4	Q12	We value the <u>orderly and risk-reducing</u> management process much more than leadership initiatives for change.	7 Point	Scale

Proactiveness: [Proact]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
EO5	Q13	We firmly believe that a change in market creates positive opportunities for us.	7 Point	Scale
EO6	Q14	Members of our company tend to talk more about opportunities rather than problems.	7 Point	Scale

Part 2 (b) - Market Orientation [MO]

Information acquisition: [Info Gen]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
MO1	Q15	We are <u>slow</u> to detect changes in our customers’ product preferences. R	7 Point	Scale
MO2	Q16	We frequently review the likely effect of changes in our business environment on customers.	7 Point	Scale

Information dissemination: [Info Dis]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
MO3	Q17	When something important happens to a major customer or market, the whole business unit is informed about it within a short period.	7 Point	Scale
MO4	Q18	When one department finds out something important about competitors, it is <u>slow</u> to alert other departments. R	7 Point	Scale

Responsiveness: [Response]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
MO5	Q19	For one reason or another, we tend to react <u>slowly</u> to changes in our customers' product or service needs. R	7 Point	Scale
MO6	Q20	Several departments get together periodically to plan a response to changes taking place in our business environment.	7 Point	Scale

Part 2 (c) - Learning Orientation [LO]

Commitment to learning: [Commit]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
------	--------------	-------------	-------	---------

LO1	Q21	Managers basically agree that our company's ability to learn is the key to our competitive advantage.	7 Point	Scale
LO2	Q22	The sense around here is that employee learning is an investment, not an expense.	7 Point	Scale
LO3	Q23	The collective wisdom in this enterprise is that once we quit learning, we endanger our future.	7 Point	Scale

Shared vision: [Shr Vis]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
LO4	Q24	There is a well-expressed concept of who we are and where we are going as a company.	7 Point	Scale
LO5	Q25	All employees are committed to the goals of our company.	7 Point	Scale
LO6	Q26	Top leadership believes in sharing its vision for the entire company.	7 Point	Scale

Open-mindedness: [Open]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
LO7	Q27	Managers in our company do <u>not</u> want their "view of the world" to be questioned. R	7 Point	Scale

LO8	Q28	Managers encourage employees to “think outside of the box.”	7 Point	Scale
LO9	Q29	Original ideas are highly valued in this organisation.	7 Point	Scale

Part 3 - Financial Resources [FR]

Financial Capital [Capital]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
FR1	Q30	Our firm is satisfied with the access to long term funds for the development of the firm.	7 Point	Scale
FR2	Q31	Our firm is satisfied with the access to cash (working capital) for day to day financial needs.	7 Point	Scale

Financial Literacy [Finan Lit]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
FR3	Q32	Our firm is usually well-informed about its overall financial needs.	7 Point	Scale
FR4	Q33	Our firm is well aware of its investment prospects.	7 Point	Scale
FR5	Q34	Our firm knows the rate of return associated with each investment.	7 Point	Scale

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Part 4 - Firm Performance [P]

Financial Performance [Financial]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
P1	Q35	The return on investment of your firm has increased as compare to the past three years.	7 Point	Scale
P2	Q36	The sales of your firm have increased as compare to the past three years.	7 Point	Scale

Non-Financial Performance [Non-financial]

Code	Question No.	Description	Value	Measure
P3	Q37	The market share of your company has significantly increased as compare to the past three years.	7 Point	Scale
P4	Q38	The level of customer satisfactions in your company has increased as compare to the past three years.	7 Point	Scale
P5	Q39	New product/process innovation rate is higher in your firm as compare to the past three years.	7 Point	Scale

Appendix 3 – EFA

EFA Before Modifications

Table A3.1 - SPSS Output for Communalities and Rotated Factor Matrix*

		Rotated Factor Matrix						Communalities
Construct	Items	Factor						Extraction
		1	2	3	4	5	6	
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	0.720						0.665
	EO2	0.785						0.794
	EO3	0.858						0.838
	EO4	0.875						0.869
	EO5	0.796						0.722
	EO6	0.705						0.628
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1			0.733				0.551
	MO2			0.776				0.657
	MO3							0.186
	MO2			0.816				0.690
	MO5			0.810				0.688
	MO6			0.853				0.738
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1		0.658					0.612
	LO2		0.816					0.791
	LO3		0.865					0.865
	LO4							0.186
	LO5		0.725					0.693
	LO6		0.719					0.623
	LO7	0.624						0.596
	LO8		0.540					0.497
	LO9		0.622					0.589
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1					0.593		0.649
	FR2				0.455	0.704		0.796
	FR3				0.886			0.829
	FR4				0.904			0.840
	FR5				0.792			0.666
Firm Performance (P)	P1					0.570		0.597
	P2					0.638		0.652
	P3					0.756		0.788
	P4					0.527		0.504
	P5							0.146

*a Extraction Method: Maximum Likelihood.

*b Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

*c Rotation converged in 6 iterations.

EFA After Modifications

Table A3.2 - Rotated Factor Matrix (After Modification)*

Rotated Factor Matrix							Communalities	Cronbach's Alpha
Constructs	Items	Factor						
		1	2	3	4	5		
Entrepreneurial Orientation (EO)	EO1	0.702					0.665	0.945
	EO2	0.779					0.794	
	EO3	0.860					0.838	
	EO4	0.874					0.869	
	EO5	0.780					0.722	
	EO6	0.682					0.628	
Market Orientation (MO)	MO1			0.732			0.551	0.903
	MO2			0.777			0.657	
	MO2			0.819			0.690	
	MO5			0.814			0.688	
	MO6			0.853			0.738	
Learning Orientation (LO)	LO1		0.649				0.612	0.908
	LO2		0.818				0.791	
	LO3		0.863				0.865	
	LO5		0.724				0.693	
	LO6		0.721				0.623	
	LO8		0.553				0.501	
	LO9		0.628				0.589	
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1				0.501		0.649	0.878
	FR2				0.560		0.796	
	FR3				0.910		0.829	
	FR4				0.894		0.840	
	FR5				0.804		0.666	
Firm Performance (P)	P1					0.599	0.597	0.851
	P2					0.672	0.652	
	P3					0.726	0.788	
	P4					0.539	0.504	

Source: SPSS Output of EFA

Appendix 4 – CFA

Figure A4.1 - Standardised Measurement Model

Figure A4.2 – Unstandardised Measurement Model

Table A4.1 - Untandardized Loading Estimates, Critical Ratio, P-Value of Measurement Model

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
EO1	<---	EO	1				
EO2	<---	EO	1.066	0.055	19.361	***	par_1
EO3	<---	EO	1.133	0.056	20.267	***	par_2
EO4	<---	EO	1.125	0.054	20.753	***	par_3
EO5	<---	EO	1.032	0.058	17.758	***	par_4
EO6	<---	EO	0.982	0.062	15.79	***	par_5
LO1	<---	LO	1				
LO2	<---	LO	1.086	0.076	14.323	***	par_6
LO3	<---	LO	1.17	0.078	14.973	***	par_7
LO5	<---	LO	1.08	0.078	13.779	***	par_8
LO6	<---	LO	1.07	0.082	12.994	***	par_9
LO8	<---	LO	0.978	0.087	11.27	***	par_10
LO9	<---	LO	0.953	0.079	12.112	***	par_11
MO1	<---	MO	1				
MO2	<---	MO	1.012	0.072	14.041	***	par_12
MO4	<---	MO	1.021	0.07	14.521	***	par_13
MO5	<---	MO	1.07	0.075	14.349	***	par_14
MO6	<---	MO	1.174	0.079	14.788	***	par_15
FR1	<---	FR	1				
FR2	<---	FR	1.394	0.161	8.669	***	par_16
FR3	<---	FR	2.348	0.215	10.908	***	par_17
FR4	<---	FR	2.306	0.214	10.795	***	par_18
FR5	<---	FR	2.246	0.218	10.298	***	par_19
P1	<---	P	1				
P2	<---	P	0.86	0.06	14.438	***	par_20
P3	<---	P	1.109	0.07	15.9	***	par_21
P4	<---	P	0.795	0.069	11.597	***	par_22

Table A4.2 - Standardized Loading Estimates of Measurement Model

			Estimate
E01	<---	EO	0.811
E02	<---	EO	0.89
E03	<---	EO	0.916
E04	<---	EO	0.929
E05	<---	EO	0.841
E06	<---	EO	0.775
LO1	<---	LO	0.714
LO2	<---	LO	0.84
LO3	<---	LO	0.88
LO5	<---	LO	0.808
LO6	<---	LO	0.762
LO8	<---	LO	0.661
LO9	<---	LO	0.71
MO1	<---	MO	0.736
MO2	<---	MO	0.805
MO4	<---	MO	0.832
MO5	<---	MO	0.822
MO6	<---	MO	0.847
FR1	<---	FR	0.561
FR2	<---	FR	0.616
FR3	<---	FR	0.915
FR4	<---	FR	0.892
FR5	<---	FR	0.812
P1	<---	P	0.792
P2	<---	P	0.783
P3	<---	P	0.857
P4	<---	P	0.649

Appendix 5 – SEM

Figure A5.1 – Structural Model

Table A2.1 - Unstandardized Loading Estimates, Critical Ratio and P-Value of Structural Model

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
P	<---	EO	0.368	0.042	8.7	***	
P	<---	MO	0.242	0.028	8.757	***	
P	<---	LO	0.243	0.045	5.343	***	
P	<---	FR	0.28	0.053	5.262	***	
P	<---	FR_X_EO	-0.006	0.024	-0.247	0.805	
P	<---	FR_X_M O	-0.016	0.016	-1.014	0.311	
P	<---	FR_X_LO	0.003	0.024	0.144	0.886	

Table A2.2 - Standardized Loading Estimates of Structural Model

Relationship			Estimate	P
P	<---	EO	0.407	***
P	<---	MO	0.313	***
P	<---	LO	0.249	***
P	<---	FR_X_EO	-0.012	0.805
P	<---	FR_X_M O	-0.036	0.311
P	<---	FR_X_LO	0.007	0.886
P	<---	FR	0.191	***

Model Fit Summary

CMIN					
Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	27	19.395	9	0.022	2.155
Saturated model	36	0	0		
Independence model	8	750.05	28	0	26.788
RMR, GFI					
Model	RMR	GFI	AGFI	PGFI	
Default model	0.031	0.985	0.94	0.246	
Saturated model	0	1			
Independence model	0.14	0.633	0.528	0.492	
Baseline Comparisons					
Model	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
	Delta1	rho1	Delta2	rho2	
Default model	0.974	0.92	0.986	0.955	0.986
Saturated model	1		1		1
Independence model	0	0	0	0	0
Parsimony-Adjusted Measures					
Model	PRATIO	PNFI	PCFI		
Default model	0.321	0.313	0.317		
Saturated model	0	0	0		
Independence model	1	0	0		
RMSEA					
Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE	
Default model	0.061	0.022	0.098	0.276	
Independence model	0.287	0.27	0.305	0	
AIC					
Model	AIC	BCC	BIC	CAIC	
Default model	73.395	74.999	174.543	201.543	
Saturated model	72	74.139	206.863	242.863	
Independence model	766.05	766.526	796.02	804.02	